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Master's Thesis

**Detection of Sensitive Data Exposures
in JVM Applications
with Bidirectional Text Correlation Analysis**

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I hereby declare that I have written this Master's thesis independently and have not used any sources, resources, or aids apart from those stated. I used GitHub Copilot¹ to generate short code passages and fragments of sentences, which I then revised manually. I used LanguageTool² and Grazie³ to identify and correct spelling, style, and grammatical mistakes.

Munich, November 04, 2024

..... Leonard Ganz
(Signature)

¹See <https://github.com/features/copilot>
²See <https://languagetool.org>
³See <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/16136-grazie-pro>

Abstract

In modern software development, ensuring the security of sensitive data is paramount. Poor logging practices can inadvertently expose sensitive information, posing significant security risks. Therefore, it is crucial to detect sensitive data exposures early in the development process. Traditional static analysis tools, however, often fall short in detecting such exposures, especially if data is exposed before its sensitivity can be determined. To address this issue, our thesis introduces JVM-BidText, a tool designed to detect sensitive data exposures in JVM applications using bidirectional text correlation analysis. With bidirectional analysis, JVM-BidText can handle scenarios where a tool can only infer the sensitivity of data after the data has already been exposed. Moreover, JVM-BidText infers the sensitivity of data automatically by analyzing static strings in the source code, reducing the need for manual input. JVM-BidText generalizes the capabilities of the existing tool BidText [35], originally developed for Android applications. Our main objective is to make the benefits of BidText available to a broader range of applications. First, we refactor and upgrade the codebase of BidText to support Java up to version 23. Second, we modify the setup of the analysis engine, remove Android-specific components, and adapt propagation rules and sink definitions. Furthermore, we generalize the text analysis and other components to support JVM applications. To find keywords suitable for inferring the sensitivity of data in JVM applications, we conduct a study on a real-world application. By supporting JVM bytecode, we extend the scope of supported applications even beyond Java and make JVM-BidText capable of analyzing applications written in other JVM languages like Kotlin. In general, JVM languages are very heterogeneous. We identify that libraries and frameworks pose additional challenges for JVM-BidText because essential parts of the program flow are hidden in external code. To aid the analysis of libraries and applications built on top of the popular Spring framework, we implement different strategies for the detection of entry points, including the identification of callback methods and controller endpoints. Furthermore, we enhance JVM-BidText to support dependency injection in the Spring framework. To this end, we model Inversion of Control on an intermediate representation level and perform bytecode modification, enabling JVM-BidText to analyze data flow through Spring managed classes. Thereby, we extend JVM-BidText’s applicability to enterprise-grade applications. Our evaluation includes multiple case studies, comparing JVM-BidText to GitHub CodeQL, a state-of-the-art static analysis tool. The results demonstrate that JVM-BidText effectively detects sensitive data exposures with little manual input, outperforming CodeQL in specific scenarios. In comparison to CodeQL, a significant advantage of the approach we implement in JVM-BidText is the ability to analyze data flows that involve standard or third-party library methods. Furthermore, in contrast to CodeQL, our tool can detect sensitive data exposures that require bidirectional reasoning. This capability is especially useful for the detection of insecure whole-object logging—the most common root cause for sensitive data exposure vulnerabilities [40].

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1. Introduction

The threat caused by *Exposure of Sensitive Information to an Unauthorized Actor* is recognized as a category in the Common Weakness Enumeration as CWE-200¹. Over the last five years it has been part of the “CWE Top 25 Most Dangerous Software Weaknesses” list or the extended Top 40 “On the Cusp” list².

Logging systems can pose various security risks if sensitive information is written into log files. Ray, Belyaev, Strizhov, Mulamba, and Rajaram state that log files can become an important target for malicious attackers because log files contain information on most of the events in the system and on user activity [30]. By definition, logs are meant to be a “record of the events occurring within an organization’s systems and networks” [19]. For this reason, compromised log files can give valuable guidance to attackers [40, 30]. Zhi, Yin, Han, and Deng explain why log files in particular are a threat to the security of a system. They state that the security posture of logging systems is usually much laxer than that of other storage systems [40]. Logging systems often rely on poorly protected storage spaces such as local file systems with wide access privileges, while only the application data is stored in a secure database. Log files containing sensitive information can easily lead to confidentiality and privacy breaches [30]. The specific problem of *Insertion of Sensitive Information into Log File* is recognized as a common weakness in CWE-532³ which is a transitive child of the aforementioned CWE-200.

If logging is that dangerous, why do we not simply stop logging? We assume that any practitioner would agree that this is not a viable solution. Logging allows collecting important runtime information of a software system [42]. Zhou, Hamdaqa, Cai, and Hamou-Lhadj summarize the purpose of logging as an essential practice to debug, diagnose and audit software systems [41]. Ray, Belyaev, Strizhov, Mulamba, and Rajaram add that logging is also important for the identification of policy violations and for the investigation of malicious activities [30]. They further explain that often forensically sound preservation of information is required for legal reasons [30]. In summary, logging is a crucial part of any software system. We agree with Li, Shang, Adams, Sayagh, and Hassan that it is necessary to balance the benefits and costs of logging [42].

If logging is a necessary part of software systems, another question arises: How can we protect sensitive information from attackers? One strategy is to improve the security of the log files themselves or make them harder to access. Schneier and Kelsey present an approach to secure log files on untrusted machines using cryptographic techniques [12]. They aim to provide as little information as possible to an attacker who has compromised a machine that stores log files. Ray, Belyaev, Strizhov, Mulamba, and Rajaram propose a different approach to secure log files. To reduce costs and complexity, they suggest implementing secure logging as a service, thereby delegating the log management to the cloud [30].

Both of these approaches have in common that they aim to secure the log files. One could argue that these approaches are reactive and do not address the root cause of the problem. A

¹See <https://cwe.mitre.org/data/definitions/200.html>

²See <https://cwe.mitre.org/top25/archive/>

³See <https://cwe.mitre.org/data/definitions/532.html>

fundamentally different strategy to reduce the risk associated with logging is to prevent sensitive information from being written to log files in the first place. While it is certainly necessary to include a lot of information in log files to make them useful, it is often not necessary to include sensitive information. There is a fine line between including enough information to make the log files useful and not including too much information that could be harmful. Chuvakin and Peterson try to provide a balanced guide on what type of information should be included in log files [24].

Still, in practice, it is often challenging to determine what information to log. It is therefore all the more important to have tools that can help developers to identify if their logging practice is reasonable. A category of tools that can help with this task is static analysis tools that can detect whether sensitive information is exposed through logging. Such tools can help developers to identify potential security risks in their code early in the development process. The tools can analyze the source or bytecode of a program and identify data flow paths that expose sensitive information. If a tool can identify such data flow paths, developers can take action to prevent the exposure of sensitive information.

For detecting exposure of sensitive information through logging in particular Zhi, Yin, Han, and Deng identify the need for research into practical solutions with reduced manual input requirements in comparison to previous solutions based on taint analysis [40]. They conduct a study on real-world vulnerabilities in the category of sensitive data exposures through logging. In this study, they identify the most prominent root cause for such vulnerabilities to be insecure whole-object logging. Many traditional techniques in the area of taint analysis will fail to detect insecure whole-object logging because these techniques can only analyze forward data flow. When a whole object is logged, typically a tool has had no chance to infer the sensitivity of the object before the data is exposed. Traditional taint tracking can only monitor the *usage* of an object identified as sensitive, but cannot track the information back to the container, i.e., the whole-object, that might have been logged.

In this thesis, we present JVM-BidText — a tool for the detection of sensitive data exposures, especially suited to detect vulnerabilities caused by insecure whole-object logging. JVM-BidText builds on an approach introduced by Huang, Zhang, and Tan in the tool BidText [35]. By using this approach, JVM-BidText can perform bidirectional analysis, allowing for basic reasoning along the lines of “If the object extracted from this container is sensitive, then the container itself must also be sensitive”. As we will discover, this feature is crucial for the detection of insecure whole-object logging.

The objective of this thesis is to research a specific and mostly automated approach for the ***Detection of Sensitive Data Exposures in JVM Applications with Bidirectional Text Correlation Analysis***. We implement this approach in the tool JVM-BidText. JVM-BidText exploits information in static strings inside the source code to derive the sensitivity of data. Thereby, we generally do not require user input. We analyze the data flow of the program and propagate sensitivity information forward and backward in a typing graph constructed from the program’s bytecode. The goal is to identify data flow paths from sources to sinks that expose sensitive information.

Prior work on this topic is available in the context of Android applications. We use the analysis tool *BidText* [35] introduced by Huang, Zhang, and Tan as the basis for our development. The thesis will focus on adapting BidText for the analysis of JVM applications instead of Android applications. Our goal with JVM-BidText is to make the benefits of BidText available to a broader range of applications. By using JVM bytecode, we extend the scope of supported applications even beyond Java. We want to answer the following research question: **How can**

the approach to sensitive data exposure detection used in BidText be transferred to JVM applications? (RQ 1) Next, we aim to get a more in-depth understanding of the capabilities of the approach and try to answer the question: **How well can the transferred BidText approach be applied to JVM applications? (RQ 2)** To answer this question, we conduct multiple case studies on hand-crafted examples and a small real-world project from GitHub.

In practice, Java is often used in large-scale enterprise applications. Such applications are frequently built on top of frameworks which hold additional challenges for static analysis. We aim to extend the capabilities of JVM-BidText by adding support for dependency injection in the popular Spring framework⁴. Thereby, we increase the scope of supported applications once again to include enterprise-grade applications. We want to answer the question: **How can we extend JVM-BidText to support the analysis of applications built on top of the Spring framework? (RQ 3)**

Finally, we would like to compare JVM-BidText to GitHub CodeQL, a state-of-the-art static analysis tool. We will discuss the strengths and weaknesses of both tools and answer the question: **How does JVM-BidText compare to GitHub CodeQL? (RQ 4)**

⁴See <https://spring.io>

2. Approach of BidText to the Detection of Sensitive Data Exposures

With BidText Huang, Zhang, and Tan propose a new approach to detecting sensitive data exposures in the source code of Android applications [35]. Their approach tries to exploit information stored in static strings inside the bytecode to derive which data is to be considered sensitive. Locations where sensitive data is first detected are called *sources*. BidText analyzes the data flow in a program to find paths that lead from sources of sensitive data to *sinks* where the data is disclosed. Sinks are locations in the program where sensitive data is written to a log file, sent over the network, or stored in a database, etc. In terms of sinks, we will focus on logging. We have discussed the importance of logging for sensitive data exposures and the risks associated with logging in the introduction. We should keep in mind, however, that BidText can be configured easily to detect other types of sinks as well. Once BidText has identified data as sensitive, BidText propagates sensitivity information through a custom typing graph. BidText derives this typing graph from bytecode with the system dependence graph and call graph as intermediate steps. BidText uses the typing graph to implement a custom type system, which defines propagation rules for different language constructs. If BidText can find a propagation path from a sensitive data source to a sink, it reports a potential sensitive data exposure.

BidText propagates information bidirectionally, i.e., not only forward in the direction of program execution but also backward. This technique enables the discovery of the sensitiveness of data through paths that do not lead to sinks themselves. In practical terms, BidText can find sensitive data exposures even if BidText can only detect the sensitivity of the data after the data has already been passed to a sink. This is an advantage in comparison to classical taint analysis. Furthermore, the approach aims at the automatic discovery of sensitiveness by processing discovered strings with a natural language parser and predefined keywords such that no user input (e.g., for declaring sensitive data sources) is required. Automatic scanning improves scalability but comes at the cost of soundness.

After an illustration of the approach with an example, we describe the steps necessary to prepare the analysis. This includes the discovery of entry points and the construction of call and system dependence graphs. In total, BidText uses three types of graphs to support the analysis: a call graph, a system dependence graph, and a custom typing graph. We construct each graph based on the previous one. The custom typing graph finally enables the propagation of sensitive data and tracking of paths between sources and sinks. Finally, we describe the processing of data at the discovered sinks.

2.1. Example of BidText Analysis

To get an idea of how BidText works, let us look at an abstracted example first. We present an excerpt from a simplified Java program with some sort of message handling system in listing 1. This program has two data flow paths that will highlight the necessity of bidirectional data flow analysis.

```

public void handleMessage(Message msg){
    String dt = msg.getRawData();
    LOG.info("Got message data: " + dt);
    JSONObject json = parseJson(dt);
    switch (json.get("message_type")) {
        case DATA_RETRIEVAL:
            doWork(json);
            break;
            // ...
    }
}
private void doWork(JSONObject json){
    String pw = json.get("password");
    // ...
}

```

Listing 1: Example Java Program with Message Handling

The first flow path consists of just one statement which prints the complete raw message data stored in variable `dt` to the log. Independently of this operation, the second flow path processes the raw message data. We parse a JSON map from `dt` and hand variable `json` as an argument to the method `doWork`. The invoked method uses the static string `"password"` as a key to retrieve a value from the JSON map.

Figure 2.1 shows a diagram of these two flow paths and abstractly visualizes what happens in the BidText analysis of this code snippet. We do not visualize intermediate steps and show a graph that is a simplification of the actual typing graph used by BidText. Using a graph as a data structure allows BidText to stay close to the data flow model of the program and to track paths between sources and sinks.

In the diagram, we see that BidText constructs a graph containing the relevant variables (local variables, fields, parameters, etc.) to model the data flow (solid arrows). BidText is configured to detect logging statements as sinks during the construction process. This enables BidText to mark the only node in the first data flow path as a sink (red node).

Let us shift our attention to the second data flow path. Using regular expressions and keywords, BidText identifies the string `"password"` as a potential indicator for sensitive data. As a consequence, BidText can mark the bottom right node (blue node) as a source and type it with the string `"password"`. BidText propagates this type information (dashed arrows) backward through the graph to the raw message data in variable `dt`. Next, it propagates the type information forward through the other data flow path to the logging statement. Because the logging statement is a sink and the corresponding node is typed with a sensitive string, BidText reports a potential sensitive data exposure. This alarm would not have been possible without bidirectional propagation, as the sink is discovered first and in a separate data flow path from the source.

Now that we have a basic understanding of how BidText works, we can look at the steps necessary for the complete analysis in the following sections. We start with the preparation of the analysis in section 2.2 and provide some background information on the relevant technologies.

Figure 2.1.: Diagram of Data Flow and Type Propagation in Message Handling Example from listing 1

2.2. Preparation of Analysis

Before BidText can start propagating sensitivity information, it needs to prepare the analysis. Data structures that represent the program and how methods and statements depend on each other are necessary for the discovery of paths. We start by looking at entry point discovery and continue with the construction of call and system dependence graphs.

2.2.1. Entry Point Discovery

As a first step, BidText needs to discover entry points into the application. They are necessary as a starting point for building call graphs, which are the basis for analyzing the program structure. For both the analysis of Android applications like in the original approach and for the analysis of the program used for the case study later in this thesis (section 4.3), entry point discovery is non-trivial.

While standard Java programs in general have only one entry point—the main method—libraries and programs in the context of a framework can have a multitude of entry points. Let us take a quick look at how BidText discovers entry points for Android applications because we will adapt this approach for the analysis of JVM applications in a later chapter. The Android framework dictates the use of different kinds of components, which are considered the building blocks of an application. According to the Android documentation [54] a component cannot directly activate another component but only the Android system itself can. For this reason, we can consider components the entry points from an application perspective. More specifically, some concrete methods of components like the lifecycle callbacks `onCreate` or `onPause` of Activities act as entry points. Lu, Li, Wu, Lee, and Jiang define application entry points as “the methods that are defined by the app and intended to be called only by the framework” [28].

BidText implements the entry point discovery algorithm introduced by Lu, Li, Wu, Lee, and Jiang [28] which extracts information on entry points based on the means the framework

itself uses to find entry points. Entry points for Android applications are either listed in the manifest file, or override specific framework methods, or implement framework interfaces. For the analysis of our real-world application, we will adapt this entry point discovery algorithm in section 4.3.1. But before we get to that, we want to understand how BidText constructs the graphs necessary for the analysis.

2.2.2. Construction of Call Graph

Once BidText has discovered entry points, BidText sequentially processes each entry point and constructs a call graph per entry point using the WALA analysis framework (T.J. Watson Libraries for Analysis)¹. Commonly, a call graph is defined as a directed graph of nodes representing methods and edges that model calls between methods. Grove and Chambers provide uniform vocabulary for describing call graph construction algorithms and extend this definition to better suite the needs of static analysis. They define call graph nodes as *contours*—representations of a method at analysis-time— instead of just methods [18].

We can specify a method contour by the triple (*call site identifier*, *contour key*, *additional analysis information*). To get a more in-depth understanding of what a contour could look like, let us consider the following example. We imagine a program doing calculations with shapes that are organized in a class hierarchy. An example contour for one specific call to an *area* method could look like this: (call to *shape1.area()* at line *x*, $\langle Util::sumArea(shape1, shape2), Main::processCircles \rangle$, —) where *x* is a line in a utility method that performs calculations on any type of shape. The first element of the triple identifies one concrete method invocation at line *x* also known as a call site. The second element is the contour key, which in this example is a vector of method names. We use this vector of method names to distinguish different contexts of the same method. The vector contains the names of the methods that are on the call stack when the method is called. We can call this vector a call string. This contour contains no additional information. Using the context information of the contour, it might be possible to derive that this specific call site actually executes the *area* instance method from the *Circle* class. If no contour, but only the method was known, we would possibly have to consider dependency relationships to all possible *area* methods of different shape subclasses at this call site. The contour key allows narrowing down the possible targets of the call and therefore building a more precise call graph.

With this information in mind, let us get back to the construction of the call graph. There exist many call graph construction algorithms that differ in precision and performance. To understand why BidText uses different algorithms depending on the size of the program under evaluation, the following paragraphs provide an overview of the most relevant call graph construction algorithms and their characteristics. For object-oriented programming languages with dynamic dispatch like Java, the call graph construction problem is more complex than for procedural languages. According to Tip and Palsberg the main challenge is to compute a conservative approximation of the set of methods that can be called at a given call site using dynamic dispatch [17]. They further identify that the main point of difference between call graph construction algorithms lies in the number of sets used to approximate run time values of expressions. For example, an algorithm could track the set of types that a variable can point to. A more sophisticated algorithm could track the set of allocation sites that a variable can point to. The number of sets increases when we track this information in a context-sensitive manner,

¹See <https://github.com/wala/WALA>

e.g., using different sets depending on the surrounding method calls of a specific call site.

Basic Class Hierarchy Analysis (CHA) [8] uses no sets for approximation and only matches candidate methods at call sites by name. Rapid Type Analysis (RTA) [9, 10] has improved precision by using one set for the whole program. Variants of Control Flow Analysis (CFA) [4, 11] use one set (for 0-CFA) or several sets (for k -CFA) per expression. The authors of WALA—the analysis engine used by BidText—recommend to use CFA call graph construction algorithms with flow-insensitive Andersen-style pointer analysis [6]. According to the documentation, WALA’s implementations of these algorithms are more precise and run faster in most cases than those of RTA.

Andersen-style pointer analysis is sound [6], i.e., all possible execution paths possible at runtime are contained in the call graph. It has been shown, however, that perfectly precise pointer analysis is undecidable in general as the problem can be reduced to the halting problem [5, 7, 16]. As a result, call graphs can have edges that do not occur at runtime. In practice, this means that the call graph can be larger than necessary, but it is guaranteed to contain all possible edges.

WALA has implementations for different variants of pointer analysis. In the most basic case, one can use a 0-CFA algorithm to build a context-insensitive call graph with a class-based heap model. Because the algorithm is context-insensitive, there is only one contour per method. Precision can be increased by employing a 0-1-CFA algorithm which is still context-insensitive but uses an allocation-site based heap model [25]. One can achieve more precision at the cost of space and performance by using context-sensitive algorithms, where an arbitrary number of contours per method can exist representing different analysis-time views of the same method. WALA offers k -CFA algorithms that use call string-based context-sensitivity. For these algorithms, WALA uses a vector of length k for tracking the enclosing method calls of a call site and to build a contour [18].²

By default, BidText uses a 1-CFA call graph builder with call-string length limited to one. If the size of the call graph exceeds a certain threshold³, BidText reduces the call-string length to zero and uses a 0-CFA, more specifically 0-1-CFA algorithm. When call-string length is reduced to 0 the k -CFA algorithm degenerates to a context-insensitive 0-CFA algorithm [18]. With this approach, BidText aims to balance precision and performance.

2.2.3. Construction of System Dependence Graph

The call graph is an abstracted view of a concrete program, showing when and where methods are called. The program may call a specific method repeatedly and at very different locations. For further analysis, BidText needs to understand how methods and statements depend on each other in a summarized view. Because this information is only indirectly available in the call graph, the next step is to construct a system dependence graph (SDG) [2] from the call graph. The SDG is a directed graph where nodes represent statements and predicates of a program and edges represent dependencies between them. An SDG contains a procedure dependence graph (PDG) for each method, describing the data processing and control flow of the method. The SDG links these PDGs with additional synthetic nodes and edges for modeling parameter passing and result returning. We distinguish two main types of dependencies for the edges in the SDG: control and data dependencies. For two nodes n_1 and n_2 , n_2 is control-dependent

²The opening example of this section demonstrated what such a contour could look like.

³More specifically, if the node count of the system dependence graph built from the call graph exceeds a certain threshold

on n_1 if the evaluation of n_1 controls the execution of n_2 . n_2 is data-dependent on n_1 if the relative order of n_1 and n_2 can affect the program’s computation [2], i.e. if the computation of n_2 may use a value of the computation at n_1 [26]. Horwitz, Reps, and Binkley differentiate further types of dependencies [2] which are not relevant for the BidText approach.

BidText constructs an SDG from the call graph described in the previous section, once again using WALA. Huang, Zhang, and Tan choose to ignore control dependencies completely and only consider data dependencies for BidText. They do not analyze all data dependencies either. They disable options to inspect base pointers for indirect memory accesses and dependencies from throw to catch blocks. This decision leads to the SDG being unsound but more scalable. Graf shows that ignoring the additional data and control dependencies from exceptions can cut the average node count of an SDG approximately in half [26]. Graf determines that the precision of the pointer analysis only has a moderate impact on the precision of an SDG. Precision and scalability of an SDG could be affected more by adapting the parameter passing model. By disabling the analysis of base pointers and control dependencies, Huang, Zhang, and Tan instruct WALA to apply Thin Slicing [20]. Sridharan, Fink, and Bodik argue that, in practice, not all statements appear equally relevant in the construction of an SDG. Thin Slicing reduces the number of nodes in the SDG by removing statements that do not directly contribute to the computation of a value [20]. Livshits, Sridharan, Smaragdakis, Lhoták, Amaral, Chang, Guyer, Khedker, Møller, and Vardoulakis make a strong case for accepting unsoundness in static analysis tools to a certain extent [33].

After SDG construction, BidText prunes the SDG to remove synthetic method entry and exit statements. To focus the sensitive data exposure analysis on application code, pruning also removes most statements from the Java standard library and Android framework. BidText handles the possibility, that the SDG is not a connected graph after the pruning operation, by iterating over all resulting subgraphs later in the analysis.

2.3. Construction of Typing Graph

To fully understand how BidText can find sensitive data exposures, we need to look at what data structures are used to support the type system responsible for the propagation of strings. BidText uses the means described in the previous sections to construct an SDG, which contains information on data flow dependencies between different parts of the program. Based on this information, BidText will analyze how the program passes sensitive data between variables. In the context of BidText, variables are not only local variables but also fields, parameters, and return values of methods. To collect all the information in a way suitable to support type propagation, BidText constructs yet another graph —a custom typing graph.

Before we look at the typing graph in detail, let us first understand what *typing* is. In the context of BidText, typing is the process of associating variables with a set of types. Our goal with the types is to derive which variables contain sensitive information. In practice, types are strings that have a relation based on data flow to the variable. In other words, we correlate texts with variables, hence the name *text correlation analysis*. In the beginning, only string constants have a type. We define the string itself as the type of the string constant.

Depending on how the program uses these string constants, we can gain information on other variables. E.g., if we add a string constant to a list, we know that the list contains the string constant. If the string was sensitive, the list containing it is also sensitive. Therefore, we can propagate the type information forward from the string constant to the whole list.

2. Approach of BidText to the Detection of Sensitive Data Exposures

This reasoning works the other way around as well. If we know that a program variable is derived from a previous variable, we can infer information on the previous variable from our knowledge of the current variable. E.g., if we extract an element that *later turns out to be sensitive* from a container, we can infer that the container must have been sensitive as well. We model this inference of information by propagating information backward. In a program, *data* itself cannot flow backward. But in the analysis, *information on data* can flow backward.

Over time, variables can accumulate multiple types. In section 2.5 we will see how BidText uses this type information to detect sensitive data exposures. BidText has a set of rules—formally represented in a type system—that define relationships like we have just discussed for different language constructs. Huang, Zhang, and Tan provide a formal definition of the type system in the original paper on BidText [35].

Before we are ready to propagate type information, we need to construct the typing graph. But even before that, we want to understand the purpose of the typing graph. Let us, therefore, summarize the three main goals of the typing graph and get an overview of the typing graph’s structure. To enable the accumulation of types for variables, BidText needs to build a structure that can hold the type information. Every time BidText encounters a variable in the SDG, BidText creates a corresponding node in the typing graph. A node can hold a set of types⁴. This is the first purpose of the typing graph.

The typing graph is further responsible for modeling how nodes, i.e., variables, relate to each other in terms of “sharing” type information. We remember the example with the sensitive string that is added to a list where we need to propagate the type information from the string to the list. In the construction of the typing graph, we apply the rules of the formal type system to the statements of the SDG. The application of a rule can result in the creation of constraints between two nodes of the typing graph. These constraints are the edges of the typing graph and define how BidText should later propagate type information.

The third purpose of the typing graph is to collect path information. When BidText propagates type information, it is important to know where the type information comes from. This is necessary to output a meaningful report to the user after the analysis. The report should contain information on the data flow path that leads to a sensitive data exposure. Therefore, we need to store path information for each type correlated with a node.

Let us now look at how WALA represents code so that we can understand how BidText constructs the typing graph which we will discuss in the next paragraph. The WALA framework takes Java bytecode as input but operates neither on bytecode nor Java source code directly. Instead, WALA translates the bytecode to an intermediate representation (IR) that is more suitable for static analysis. IR has many similarities to bytecode, but differs in some aspects. The most important observation is that IR is in Static Single Assignment (SSA) form, which means that every variable is only assigned exactly once [45]. This eliminates the stack abstraction [46] which makes a lot of analysis tasks easier. Programs can efficiently be converted to SSA form [3]. When converting a program to SSA form additional variables are introduced to represent different versions of the same variable. When multiple versions of a variable reach a use point, ϕ -functions are inserted to select the correct variable version. BidText needs to treat ϕ -functions with extra care during the propagation of the type information.

⁴In practice, BidText uses a map relating types to path information. In essence, a map is just a set of key-value pairs. For simplicity, we will continue to use the term *set of types* in our explanations.

2. Approach of BidText to the Detection of Sensitive Data Exposures

With that information in mind, we can now finally look at how BidText constructs the typing graph. We remember from the previous section that pruning the SDG can result in multiple subgraphs. BidText iterates over all nodes of the SDG but only acts on top-level nodes, i.e., roots of the subgraphs. For each top-level node, BidText uses a breadth-first approach to first process the node itself and then its successors. Iterating over all nodes of the SDG ensures that BidText does not miss any node, even if not all nodes of the pruned SDG are connected. The main routine of the construction algorithm determines the type of the node and delegates to specific handlers. We will now look at some of these handlers to understand how BidText realizes the rules of the type system.

Nodes in the typing graph are connected by constraints that define how type information is to be propagated. For assignment-like operations like `checkcast` or `arrayload`, BidText adds equality constraints between the values on the left and right side of the operation to the typing graph. This means that sets of types of the left and right side are to be merged during propagation.

For some operations, BidText needs to cache nodes to later establish a relationship between them. As an example, the parameter of a method (callee side) and the corresponding argument (caller side) should receive a constraint in the typing graph that indicates that the two values share the same sensitivity information. To achieve this, BidText caches the nodes of the caller side and connects them when processing the callee side.

Binary operations like $v_{res} = v_1 \oplus v_2$ and ϕ -functions cannot use equality constraints between all variables. In general, no data flow occurs between the operands v_1 and v_2 which means that no type information should be propagated between them. Instead, Huang, Zhang, and Tan define special rules where the result v_{res} is typed with the union of the types of v_1 and v_2 . v_1 and v_2 receive the types of v_{res} excluding types of the respective other right hand side variable.

When processing parameter passing or result returning nodes, BidText makes a distinction between calls to API methods and calls to local methods of the application itself. For a local call, BidText connects the parameter node to the corresponding argument node with an equality constraint and leaves further processing for when BidText processes the instructions of the called method. Because the SDG does not contain the instructions of API methods and BidText will never step into them, BidText handles API calls differently. We require special handling for many API calls, especially because BidText does not only use forward but also backward propagation. While it is not possible to define rules for every API method, BidText provides a default configuration file that contains rules for common API methods like map accesses. For generic API calls, that do not have a rule in the configuration file, BidText models the data flow on a best-effort basis. To this end, BidText constructs equality typing constraints between the parameters on the one side, and the return value of the method on the other side. Additionally, if the call is an instance method, BidText places equality constraints between the parameters and the target of the call, i.e., the object reference / `this` reference. BidText constructs no constraints between the parameters themselves, as in general, no information is passed between them.

When BidText is done processing all nodes of the SDG, the typing graph is complete and almost ready for propagation. To support the task of propagation, the typing graph provides the complete information on how all variables relate to each other in terms of “sharing” type information.

2.4. Propagation of Sensitive Strings

The typing graph with its propagation constraints is the basis for the propagation of sensitive data information. But there are still two more steps necessary before we can start the propagation: the detection of sources and sinks.

Let us first look at how BidText detects sources. Sources are locations in the program where BidText finds static strings that correlate with a variable and where such a string indicates that the variable might contain something to consider sensitive. A classic example is a string used as a key to retrieve a value from a map. If the map accessor key is `"password"` it is likely that the value retrieved is a password and should be treated with care. However, not only the retrieved value is sensitive, but also the data structure that contains it. If the whole map was printed to the log for unthoughtful debugging, sensitive data would be exposed even before a tool can detect that the map contains such data.

When BidText iterates over the nodes of the typing graph during its propagation procedure, it looks for text constants. BidText adds the discovered strings as type information to the corresponding nodes. At this point, only a rudimentary keyword-based check is performed to determine if the string indicates sensitivity. More rigorous checks are left for later when processing the sinks.

Additionally, BidText scans UI layout files of Android applications and associates strings found in these files with the corresponding nodes in the typing graph. Further processing does not differ from the processing of strings found in the source code.

There is a third mechanism in place that adds artificial strings to nodes of the typing graph. BidText associates some predefined API methods with sensitive data sources, e.g., system calls retrieving geographic information or device identifiers. When BidText detects the invocation of such a method during typing graph construction, BidText adds an artificial constant node to the typing graph and links this node to the method return value. The artificial node is typed with a predefined string that indicates sensitive data. This approach allows manually fine-tuning the analysis to the specific needs of an application.

Next, we shift our attention to sinks. The detection of sinks happens exclusively during the construction of the typing graph. When processing method invocations, BidText checks if the target method is a sink by looking up the method's signature in a predefined list of sinks. If the check is positive, BidText records the method as a potential sink. It is important to note that not the entire method is a sink. Instead, sink definition rules can configure which parameters of the method actually expose data. For example, a logging method might have a parameter that is the message to be logged and a parameter containing the log level. Only the message parameter is a sink in this case.

Now that we have identified sources and sinks, and have built one typing graph per entry point, we can finally start the propagation procedure. At this point, most of the heavy lifting has already been done. In the introduction to the previous section, we have already discussed the idea of type propagation. Therefore, we will now only look at the implementation of the propagation procedure in BidText. In preparation for the propagation, BidText initializes a work list with all nodes that are string constants. The string constant nodes are assigned the string itself as type information. This is the initial type information that will be propagated.

BidText uses an iterative approach to propagate type information through the typing graph until a fix point is reached, i.e., until further propagation does not lead to changes. BidText

uses the work list to track which nodes need further processing. In each iteration, BidText executes a forward and a backward propagation step. Forward propagation means that BidText propagates type information from the current node to its successors in the direction of program execution. BidText uses the collection of typing constraints to define succession. We remember that the typing graph construction algorithm has specifically defined these constraints in places where it determined that type information should be propagated.

Backward propagation works analogously but in the opposite direction. Backward propagation means that BidText propagates type information against the direction of program execution. BidText propagates type information from the current node to its predecessors. As with forward propagation, a set of constraints links a node to its predecessors in the typing graph. These constraints only exist if the typing graph construction algorithm has identified that type information should be propagated.

When BidText merges type information for two nodes, BidText not only unions the sets of strings but also concatenates path information. This is necessary to track the origin of type information and to be able to report paths from sources to sinks. If the type information of a node changes during propagation, BidText puts the node back in the work list for further processing. When the work list is empty, we have reached a fix-point, and the propagation procedure is finished. The only thing left to do is to process the type information that has reached the sink nodes.

2.5. Processing of Data at Sinks

All the steps described in the previous sections happen on a per-entry-point basis. Once the last step where BidText propagates data is completed for all entry points, BidText processes the information on sinks. For each sink, BidText analyzes the interesting parameters, i.e., the parameters that leak information when the program executes the sink. BidText extracts the texts and paths from the typing graph for the nodes that resemble the interesting parameters. It then analyzes the extracted texts to check if they indicate sensitive information. If BidText identifies any of those strings as indicating sensitivity, it reports a potential sensitive data exposure. Each report contains information on one sink, the extracted text and crucially the path from the source to the sink. If no strings or only non-sensitive strings reach a potential sink, BidText does not create a report for it.

For analyzing whether strings indicate sensitivity, BidText primarily uses keyword- and regular expression-based checks. But BidText also employs a natural language parser to extract more information from the text. A central part of this analysis is the identification of negations, which is especially useful for UI strings that give instructions to the user. For example, a string “Do not enter your password here” does not indicate that the following input field is sensitive even though the string contains the keyword “password”. This mechanism is an attempt to reduce false positives.

We will discuss complete examples and the structure of reports when we look at case studies on the adapted version of BidText in chapter 4.

3. Transfer of the BidText Approach from Android to JVM Applications

Huang, Zhang, and Tan demonstrate their approach on detection of sensitive data exposure with a prototype implementation for Android applications [35]. Chapter 2 describes their approach and relevant background information in detail. Inspired by the core idea of bidirectional text propagation, their tool is called BidText.

The best way to protect sensitive data is to avoid its exposure in the first place. This rule applies to all applications, not just Android applications. As Java is still a widely used language, especially in the enterprise sector¹, the approach of BidText originally developed for Android could be useful for a broader audience. Because Android’s Dalvik bytecode has a lot in common with JVM bytecode, adapting the approach for JVM applications seems feasible. In this chapter, we focus on the question, how the approach to sensitive data exposure detection used in BidText can be transferred to JVM applications (**RQ 1**). We present the necessary changes to the approach and the implementation. The generalization makes the approach not only applicable to standard Java applications but also to programs written in other JVM languages like Kotlin.

We start by discussing the differences between Android and JVM applications and how they affect the approach. With this knowledge, we can understand the required refactoring and upgrade of the codebase. Finally, we look at the changes to the approach and implementation necessary for the transfer to JVM applications.

3.1. Differences between Android and JVM Applications

Our goal is to transfer the approach of BidText from Android to “standard Java applications”. But first, we need to disambiguate the term *Java*. In general, Java is just the name of a language specification. But occasionally, the term is also used to refer to the runtime environment of Java applications. Most often, it is correct to infer that the runtime environment of a Java application is the Java Virtual Machine (JVM). In the context of Android, however, specialized runtime environments are used, namely the legacy Dalvik Virtual Machine (DVM) and the Android Runtime (ART). To avoid confusion, we will always refer to “standard Java applications” as JVM applications.

Let us now discuss the key differences between Android and JVM applications. Android applications are written in Java or Java-like languages and compiled to Dalvik bytecode while JVM applications are compiled to JVM bytecode. The JVM and the DVM/ART share similarities but differ in some key aspects like a stack-based architecture for the JVM and a register-based architecture for the DVM. This difference is important for static analysis because the bytecode needs to be handled differently for both architectures. Analysis frameworks like

¹Cass published an analysis of the most important programming languages at IEEE that as of August 2024 ranks Java in second or third place depending on the metric [47].

WALA ease the handling of these differences by providing tools that abstract from the bytecode format.

When comparing Android and JVM applications, another important difference is the availability of standard libraries. Android is a framework that enforces a specific architecture for applications and provides a lot of functionality out of the box. This includes libraries for user interface design and data storage specially tailored for mobile applications. Parts of the Java standard library are not available on Android, e.g., Swing/AWT or `System.out`. When transferring the BidText approach to JVM applications, we need to consider that some parts of the approach might not be applicable because they rely on Android-specific libraries or concepts. At the same time, new possibilities arise because the full Java standard library is available and other libraries or frameworks can be used.

3.2. Upgrade of the Codebase

To be able to analyze modern JVM applications written in current Java versions up to version 23, we have to upgrade the codebase of BidText. The reason that changes to the code base are necessary is that BidText relies on WALA for working with bytecode and constructing call and system dependence graphs. Only newer versions of this library support the latest Java versions. Newer versions of the library only run on Java 17 or higher. With the required compatibilities of libraries in mind, we choose Java 21 —the latest long-term support version— as the target version for our upgraded version of BidText. For comparison, the original implementation of BidText is written in Java 7. As part of this thesis, we upgrade the codebase to enable support for the analysis of modern JVM applications up to Java 23. Because the jump between versions is so large, many APIs of the required libraries have changed. Dependency management and build tools are also updated to work with the new Java version.

After the updates, the codebase still needs further attention to get to a runnable state. The original implementation of BidText is a prototype intended for research purposes. Therefore, it is written in a way that enables the demonstration of its new approach, but the code is not designed to be easily maintainable or extendable. To execute the tool on systems besides the one it was developed on, we change hard-coded paths and configurations. Afterward, the upgraded tool can reproduce the results of the original implementation when executed on the provided sample Android applications.

3.3. Refactoring of the Codebase

Even though the upgraded tool runs successfully on the provided sample applications, the codebase is still not in a state that would allow for easy adaptation, not to mention extension. As it later turns out, the original codebase contains bugs that are not immediately apparent and arguably could have been avoided with a cleaner coding style. The goal is to refactor the codebase such that it follows common software engineering principles. In this regard, a major objective is to separate concerns and make the code easier to understand. We achieve this partly by splitting the code into smaller classes and methods that each have a single responsibility. The original implementation contains a lot of script-like code and is monolithic, which leads to a lot of duplicated code. By extracting common functionality into separate classes and methods, the main procedures become more concise and easier to understand. We convert plenty of static methods to object-oriented constructs. Further, we reduce the usage of global variables to a

```

if (const0.isEmpty() || const1.isEmpty()) {
    Set<Object> empty, nonEmpty;
    boolean isZero = true;
    if (const0.isEmpty()) {
        empty = const0;
        nonEmpty = const1;
    } else {
        empty = const1;
        nonEmpty = const1; // should be const0!
        isZero = false;
    }
    // ...
}

```

Listing 2: Discovered bug in the logic for backward propagation of constants. This code structure appears four times in the original implementation, but only at this point, `empty` and `nonEmpty` are assigned the same value. Apart from being the odd one out, this also leads to a logical error.

minimum to prevent side effects and misunderstandings in later adaptations and extensions of the tool.

Let us take a closer look at a few parts of the code that need special attention. The following paragraphs describe where and why we separate the functionality of code that is monolithic in the original implementation. For the startup routine of the tool, we separate code for time and memory measurement from code governing the execution of the analysis. The latter includes the setup of WALA, entry point discovery, starting the analysis for each entry point, and the processing of the results. We extract the control logic for the analysis of a single entry point from the class governing the complete analysis. This separation of concerns makes it possible to easily adapt different parts of the analysis, e.g., the setup of WALA for a different bytecode format.

Next, we extract the post-processing of the typing graph and the logic for propagation of types through the finalized typing graph from the typing graph construction algorithm. During this refactoring step, we also separate the maintenance of the work list used for tracking whether propagation has reached a fix point from the actual propagation logic. We split the propagation logic up to reduce code duplication.

During these refactorings, we discover an obvious bug in the backward propagation logic, likely introduced by copy and pasting. Listing 2 shows the code snippet containing the bug. In the original implementation, the bug appears in the middle of a 240-line long method that consists of a lot of duplicated code. We split the method into smaller methods with specific responsibilities. We introduce helper methods to reduce code duplication and prevent that bugs appear because of copy and paste errors. These are just some of the changes that are necessary to make the codebase more comprehensible. This bug neatly highlights the importance of clean code that is straightforward to understand and follows common software engineering principles.

So far, we have focused on separating concerns and reducing code duplication. We will now look at two other aspects that make the original implementation error-prone. In the construction of the typing graph, the original implementation uses mutable global variables to

3. Transfer of the BidText Approach from Android to JVM Applications

store the state of the construction process, even between the construction of typing graphs for different entry points. This makes it hard to reason about the correctness of the construction process.

The second concern is the way the construction process is controlled. For maintaining a work list of SDG components left to process, the original implementation uses a `List<Object>` that contains nodes and statements without a clear relation between them. A lot of investigation was necessary to understand the construction process in the original implementation. During the manual analysis of debug logs that we added to the construction process, we detected supposedly unwanted behavior. We discovered in the original implementation that in rare cases, the construction process mixes up the statements modeling parameter passing: The target of an invocation (caller perspective) can be matched to a wrong method (callee perspective). See listing 28 in appendix A for a log excerpt showing this behavior. The mismatch occurs due to insecure handling of shared global variables used for caching in conjunction with the not type-safe work list.

We replace the error-prone work list mechanism with a custom object-oriented work list implementation that is tailored to the needs of the construction process. The new work list implementation encapsulates caching functionality to clearly link which statement belongs to which cached node. It also tracks matching caller and callee statements for parameter passing and returning values.

Now that we have refactored the construction process, we will highlight the changes necessary for one of the most important subroutines of the construction process: the handling of method invocations. We remember that section 2.4 describes that the handler for invocations of API methods, i.e., methods not available in the local codebase, has special responsibilities. It is the places where BidText applies rules for propagation in special API methods. The original implementation for handling invocations to API methods packs a lot of functionality into a single method of 164 lines of code. For the refactored version, we split this method into multiple smaller methods that each have a single responsibility. The flow of all the steps necessary to handle an invocation of API methods is now clearly visible in the main `handle` method shown in listing 3. Apart from the invocation handler itself, we refactor the rule systems used by the invocation handler to be more expressive and harder to misuse both by the developer and the user of the tool.

We refactor other aspects of the application in a similar manner to the approaches described so far in this section. Furthermore, we improve the logging system to provide more detailed information about the construction process. Where the bytecode retains the necessary information, we use variable names to provide more meaningful log messages.

While there is still a lot of room for improvement, the refactored codebase is in a state that enables comprehension of how BidText works and how it can be extended. The bugs that surfaced during the refactoring process highlight the importance of clean code.

3.4. Changes to the Approach

The refactored codebase enables more profound understanding of the approach and makes it possible to adapt and extend the tool. Refactoring also revealed parts of the approach that need to be changed to make the tool more versatile and in particular work with JVM applications. In this section, we highlight the most important changes. These changes concern various parts of BidText and range from adaptations of the setup to the generalization of the text analysis.

```

public void handle() {
    // Check if this invocation is a sink
    preprocessPotentialSink();

    if (hasNeitherParametersNorReturnValue()) {
        // No propagation needed
        return;
    }

    // Prepare propagation handling by categorizing parameters
    // as constants and non-constants
    analyzeMethodParameters();
    if (isStringBuilderInvocation()) {
        // Special handling for StringBuilder methods
        // (Texts used for typing are constructed over multiple calls)
        processStringBuilder();
    } else if (matchesPropagationRule()) {
        // Set up rule-based handling for propagation through special API
        // methods
        handlePropagationByRule();
    } else if (matchesSourceCorrelationRule()) {
        // Introduction of artificial source nodes based on API method
        // signature
        handleAPISourceByRule();
    } else {
        // Set up generic propagation for all other invocations
        handleGenericInvocation();
    }
}
}

```

Listing 3: Refactored procedure for handling invocations of API methods, i.e., methods not available in the local codebase.

We start by looking into the adaptation of the WALA setup and analysis configuration. Then we move on to two aspects of the original application that we cannot or do not want to adapt. We rather remove these aspects because they are Android-specific and do not fit into a general-purpose tool. Afterward, we introduce the changes to the text analysis. It is in part Android-specific, but we do not want to remove it as it is a central component of the approach. Instead, we propose a generalization of the text analysis to make it applicable to JVM applications. The text analysis crucially depends on a set of keywords for the detection of sensitive data. Therefore, to wrap this section up, we dive into the topic of finding suitable keywords for JVM applications. To find these keywords, we conduct a study on a real-world application. We will get back to some small adaptations during the case studies in chapter 4 once we identify the need for them.

3.4.1. Adaptation of WALA Setup and Analysis Configuration

We begin by discussing the changes we make for *adapting* parts of the BidText approach to JVM applications. First and foremost, we need to make the tool compatible with JVM bytecode

3. Transfer of the BidText Approach from Android to JVM Applications

by reworking the setup of the analysis engine WALA. Afterward, we focus on adapting the configuration files which specify rules for API methods.

Let us start with the changes to the bytecode processing with WALA. As introduced in section 3.1 JVM applications differ from Android applications in some key aspects. The most important difference is the bytecode format. All the information necessary for the detection of sensitive data exposure is extracted from bytecode. Therefore, it is essential to make BidText compatible with JVM bytecode.

All throughout sections 2.2.2, 2.2.3 and 2.3 we use the WALA library to analyze the bytecode and construct different kinds of graphs. Most of this work is done not on bytecode directly but on the intermediate representation (IR). But before we can work with IR, WALA needs to process the bytecode. WALA's internal processors, especially class loaders, differ strongly for Dalvik and Java bytecode. As it turns out, the WALA developers have put great effort into making both Dalvik and Java bytecode formats translatable to the same IR. For this reason, few changes need to be made to code that is built *on top* of IR —at least not because of the difference in bytecode format of the input.

However, we need to adapt the setup of WALA for working with JVM bytecode. BidText uses a so-called *class hierarchy* to instruct WALA on which classes are in scope of the analysis. To make the tool compatible with JVM applications, we need to build the class hierarchy from the Java standard library together with input provided as *.jar* archives or directories containing *.class* files. We can easily integrate these changes because we clearly separated the setup of WALA from the rest of the tool during the refactoring process.

We just mentioned that we build the class hierarchy with the Java standard library. More specifically, we want to include parts of the Java standard library in the class hierarchy. WALA takes the opposite approach to defining inclusions and uses a blacklist for excluding classes from the analysis. This means that we instruct WALA to build the class hierarchy from the Java standard library and our application classes but exclude classes from certain packages of the standard library.

We cannot abstain from using the Java standard library all together, even if we would rather not analyze internal calls of the library when searching for sensitive data exposures. The reason is that we intend to analyze classes that inherit from library classes. As a consequence, we need to include the relevant superclasses in the class hierarchy. We remember that every Java class implicitly inherits from `java.lang.Object`. All enums inherit from `java.lang.Enum` and exceptions transitively inherit from `java.lang.Throwable`. Therefore, we include or rather do not exclude classes from the `java.lang` package. User code does not typically extend but rather use other parts of the Java standard library like classes from the package `java.time`. To prevent the analysis from being polluted with irrelevant information on library internal calls, we exclude classes from such packages from the class hierarchy all together. To this end, we adapt the definition of exclusions in comparison to the original implementation. Examples of packages that we add to the list of exclusions are `java.nio`, `java.security`, `java.time`, and `jdk.internal`. To work with our real-world test program (section 4.3), we need to allow other classes like `java.util.(*)Exception(*)` that have been excluded in the original implementation. When analyzing JVM applications that use external libraries, we sometimes need to add library files to the class hierarchy first and then fiddle with the exclusions to get meaningful results.

The exclusion definitions are not the only configurations we need to adapt. Some parts of BidText rely on predefined rules for API methods, e.g., the detection of sinks. The original

implementation of BidText contains sink definition rules for different varieties of sinks. This includes sink methods in third-party HTTP libraries, various output streams from `java.io`, and Android-specific classes and methods. We need to adapt these rules to the needs of typical JVM applications.

As mentioned in section 3.1, Android and JVM applications differ in the availability of standard libraries. Rules for `java.io.PrintStream` which is the type of `System.out` are necessary for the analysis of most JVM applications but are not relevant for Android applications. JVM applications use other libraries for logging than Android applications, such that rules for `org.slf4j.Logger` and others are necessary. While it is not possible to provide a complete list of necessary rules for JVM applications, especially not in the scope of this thesis, it is clear that additional rules are necessary in comparison to the original implementation. We define rules for the above-mentioned examples to support the analysis of the programs from our case studies (chapter 4).

There are two more configuration files that support certain concepts of the approach. One is used to define custom rules for the propagation of sensitive data for special API methods (section 2.3). The other determines artificial sources, i.e., it defines artificial sensitive strings to assign to certain system calls to integrate them into the regular type propagation (section 2.4). The adaption of these files is not essential for the transfer of the approach to JVM applications but can be beneficial for improving the analysis results. We only add one custom entry to the propagation rule file to prevent two false positives in our real-world case study (section 4.3.4).

3.4.2. Removal of Android-Specific Parts

We have just seen some aspects of the approach that need to be adapted to JVM applications. Adaptation is not always possible or sensible, especially when parts of the approach rely on Android-specific concepts. In this section, we discuss the removal of Android-specific parts from the approach. We start by looking at the removal of user interface related code. Then we discuss the removal of hard-coded special treatment for certain Android classes and methods.

The original implementation parses the `AndroidManifest.xml` file and XML layout files during the startup routine of the tool. These files define components used in the user interface and can therefore be used to discover entry points for the analysis. Remember that we can consider components in Android applications as entry points (section 2.2.1). Furthermore, static strings are extracted from the XML layout files to be used as artificial sources of sensitive data (section 2.4). It might be sensible to use such a mechanism when analyzing Android applications because all Android applications use the same user interface framework. JVM applications, on the other hand, use numerous other libraries for user interface design. Many JVM applications do not need a user interface at all, or use a separate frontend application that communicates with the JVM backend. Therefore, we can build no general replacement for this mechanism. As a consequence, we remove these processing steps from the tool.

Another part we do not adapt, but rather remove, are some hard-coded Android-specific exceptions in the analysis. The developers of the original implementation seem to have encountered problems during the analysis of Android applications. To quickly fine-tune their results, they introduced hard-coded special treatment for certain classes and methods. For example, the handler for invocations skips parts of the analysis for methods from classes inside `Landroid/app` and `Landroid/content`. Hard-coded exceptions like these are not desirable in a general-purpose tool. We remove these exceptions from the tool, as no exceptions seem necessary for our purposes.

3.4.3. Generalization of Text Analysis

In the previous section, we have discovered that some Android-specific parts need to be removed. In this section, we will focus on the processing of sensitive texts, which is in part Android-specific as well. Still, we definitely do not want to remove this component, as detecting sensitive data through strings is a crucial part of the approach. We do not only adapt this mechanism, but use further potential for generalization.

Let us look into the changes we implement for the text analysis. The original implementation performs text analysis or parts thereof in different places. When the original BidText discovers strings during the processing of invocations, it first checks the strings for some Android-specific criteria and then matches them against a regular expression to check for keywords. The original BidText uses other but related sets of hard-coded keywords for processing sinks in the final analysis after the construction of the typing graph. The authors of the original BidText formalize yet another set of keywords in a collection of regular expressions in an external file. They use these keywords for the analysis of texts from the user interface.

This separation of the text analysis into different parts seems overly complicated. To generalize the analysis and separate it from the construction algorithm, we make our transferred version of BidText process texts in a single location. We analyze the texts at the end, right after collecting the results of the propagation from the typing graphs. Thereby, we completely separate the text analysis from other central parts of the tool. Our mechanism uses a single configurable file that contains regular expressions with keywords. We choose regular expressions over a list of simple keywords to allow for more complex patterns, e.g., for different spellings of the same word.

The decision to postpone the sensitivity analysis means that non-sensitive strings are propagated in the typing graph, too. Therefore, we can include them in the final report and enable users to inspect all strings that are propagated to a sink. Users can then judge whether sensitive strings have been missed by the text analysis, i.e., identify false negatives. This advantage comes at the cost of handling more strings in the propagation procedure. We consider this trade-off acceptable because the runtime and memory overhead is not detectable in our tests with applications up to 3 kLoC.

In the best case, the text analysis can detect all or at least most sensitive strings, and the user does not need to inspect the propagated strings manually to get meaningful results. To achieve this, BidText depends on a good set of keywords in the form of regular expressions. While the original implementation comes with some predefined keywords, we need to investigate whether these are suitable for JVM applications or if we need to find new keywords. We will focus on this topic in the next section.

3.4.4. Finding Keywords for the Detection of Sensitive Data

The previous section discussed the generalization of the text analysis. In this mechanism, we use regular expressions based on keywords to detect whether strings indicate sensitive data. The choice of keywords likely has a significant impact on the quality of the results. If these keywords are that important, one might rightfully ask how they are chosen.

To build the set of original keywords, Huang, Zhang, and Tan extracted strings from 2000 Android applications and manually inspected the results to classify strings as indicating sensitivity or not [35]. A major limitation to the quality of their results is the fact that they only analyzed strings *that reach a sink*. They did not consider strings that were processed but not leaked. One could argue that sensitive strings might more often than not be better

3. Transfer of the BidText Approach from Android to JVM Applications

protected than other strings and therefore less likely to reach a sink. This would render the results of their manual inspection less meaningful. Huang, Zhang, and Tan do not justify their choice to limit the inspection to strings that reach a sink.

Apart from the questionable methodology of their keyword study, the results seem not directly applicable to JVM applications. Many of their keywords are related to the domain of mobile applications. For example, they use keywords like *imei*, *longitude*, or *android_id*.

To address the concerns and gain a more comprehensive understanding of what might indicate sensitivity, we conduct a new study on keywords. In this study, we try to find keywords in a JVM program from the domain which we will later use in a case study (section 4.3). Further, we want to see how well the keywords from the original study perform in comparison to the new keywords.

Because financial applications are known to handle sensitive data, we conduct the study on the *alpaca-java* library² which provides programmatic access to the Alpaca trading platform³. Criteria for the selection of the library were that it is open source, from a domain where sensitive data is handled, reasonably popular on GitHub and that we could compile it without much additional setup or configuration work.

For extracting strings from the code, we consider different methods:

- Using simple regular expressions like "[^"]*" ⁴ to match chars between double quotes in the source files
- Using the string externalization feature of Eclipse IDE
- Inspecting the bytecode constant pool with `javap -verbose`
- Using the WALA library to extract strings from the bytecode

We quickly discard regular expressions applied to the source files because double quotes can also be used inside comments or escaped sequences. We decide against the string externalization feature as it is only available on a per-class basis, which makes it challenging to extract all strings from a project. For option three, processing the output of `javap -verbose` would require parsing a lot of text output, where string constants are challenging to distinguish from other strings like method names. In the end, we chose the last option because it is the most reliable and flexible way to extract strings from bytecode. It further offers the opportunity to become familiar with the WALA library, which is used as a basis for BidText.

Let us now explore briefly how to extract strings from bytecode using WALA. The analysis framework WALA offers tools for instrumenting all classes in a *.jar* archive or directory. We can step through all classes and access their constant pool with a constant pool parser. Without going into too much detail, let us just remark that the constant pool of a class contains symbolic references generated by a compiler and that references are names of variables, methods, and other strings appearing in the program. We will go into more detail on the constant pool in section 5.2.1. With the help of WALA we can query the type of constant pool items and extract all string constants, i.e., strings defined in double quotes in the source code. We collect these strings and write them to a file for further inspection.

²See artifact description in chapter 11

³See <https://alpaca.markets>

⁴All double quotes belong to the regular expression.

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Next, on our way to build a keyword set, we need to classify the extracted strings. Strings that can indicate something potentially sensitive in the variables they come into contact with are of interest. We argue that only strings that contain two consecutive letters are worth inspecting and classify all other strings as non-sensitive. We use the regular expression `".*[a-zA-Z]{2}.*"` to filter out strings that do not match this criterion. For the classification of the remaining strings, we need manual inspection. Out of ~ 3200 strings, we classify 390 as containing some keyword that might indicate sensitivity. Based on the relevant keywords of the 390 strings, we construct regular expressions that we can group into the categories *Account Information*, *Authentication*, *Personal Information*, and *Banking Information*. The regular expressions permit alternative spellings, abbreviations, and different kinds of whitespace. We present our results in listing 29 in appendix B.

To validate the results, we conduct multiple tests with the new patterns that we have just created. First, we run a control test with the new patterns on the program we extracted them from. We develop a sensitivity analysis tool that accepts a pattern file containing the regular expressions as input. The tool extracts all strings from a program, applies pattern matching and reports how the strings are classified. With little fine-tuning in the form of prohibiting a few general pre- and suffixes like “class” all strings from the alpaca-java library, originally used to build the pattern file, are classified correctly.

As this result could be due to heavy overfitting, we run our sensitivity analysis tool with the same pattern file on a different library from the same domain. Following the same selection criteria as for the alpaca-java library, we choose the XChange-core library⁵. This means that another set of over 1000 strings has to be classified manually to build a ground truth to compare to. Manual inspection finds 28 strings that can be classified as indicating sensitivity. We execute the sensitivity analysis on the new library with varying configurations that we will explain shortly. Table 3.1 shows the results of the tests together with some statistical measures. Figure 3.1 might aid in visualizing the statistical measures.

Let us first look at the results with the default configuration, i.e., matching substrings rather than whole words and using the pattern file based on the alpaca-java library. We present the results in column a) of table 3.1. The tool detects 23 out of 28 sensitive strings. It reports only 3 false positives (false positive rate of 0.27%) and 5 false negatives (false negative rate of 18%). This leads to a precision of 0.88 and a recall of 0.82 which can be combined into an F1 score of 0.85. The high scores are very promising and show that the keywords found in our study on alpaca-java can be suitable for detecting sensitive strings in other JVM applications from the financial domain.

By default, the regular expression patterns do not look for keywords as whole words but allow matching substrings. For the second test, we implement and activate an option to match keywords as whole words only. This can be useful to reduce false positives when a keyword is part of a longer word. As an example, consider the word *key* which on its own might hint at some token worth protecting. The string *monkey* on the other hand should not be classified as indicating sensitivity. We present the results of the sensitivity analysis with this option enabled in column b) of table 3.1. The new option indeed reduces the number of false positives from 3 to 1 which results in a very low false positive rate of 0.089%. However, this comes at the cost of detecting only 14 out of 28 sensitive strings and thereby increasing the false negative rate to 50%. Due to the increase in the number of false negatives and thereby a reduced recall,

⁵See <https://github.com/knowm/XChange>

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Table 3.1.: The table shows how the algorithm classifies strings as indicating sensitivity for different configurations of the sensitivity analysis. All results are from the analysis of the XChange-core library performed with patterns based on the alpaca-java library. The results of the manual analysis are presented as ground truth. Best values per row are highlighted in green. See fig. 3.1 for an explanation of statistical measures and their abbreviations.

Measure \ Config	Ground Truth (Manual Analysis)	a)	b)	c)
		Alpaca Patterns Match Substrings	Alpaca Patterns Match Whole Words	BidText Patterns Match Substrings
Total	1146	1146	1146	1146
TP	28	23	14	12
FP		3	1	3
FPR		0.27 %	0.089 %	0.27 %
TN	1118	1115	1117	1115
FN		5	14	16
FNR		18 %	50 %	57 %
Precision		0.88	0.93	0.80
Recall (Sensitivity)		0.82	0.5	0.43
F1		0.85	0.65	0.55

the F1 score drops to 0.65. Nonetheless, we want to make this option available for the text analysis in our adapted version of BidText. We transfer the option to match keywords as whole words to BidText, but disabled by default. If analysis results contain too many false positives, user adoption might suffer because of the high number of false alarms. Therefore, it might be sensible to enable the option in certain cases.

If we think back to the beginning of this section, we remember that the authors of the original BidText provide keywords that they have extracted from numerous Android applications. It is interesting to see how they perform when applied to a new domain in comparison to the patterns found in our own study. We present the results of the sensitivity analysis with the BidText patterns in column c) of table 3.1. The sensitivity analysis tool is configured to match substrings, like in test a). With the original BidText patterns, less than half of the sensitive strings are detected, and the false negative rate is at 57%. Because of a low number of false positives (due to a low number of any positives), the F1 score is still at a moderate 0.55. This value is, however, significantly lower than the F1 score of 0.85 obtained with the patterns found in our study. This result strongly suggests that the choice of keywords is crucial for the success of the approach, and that suitable keywords might very well differ between domains. The choice of keywords further decides which kind of data should be tracked in BidText. Pattern files allow the user to deliberately choose to focus the analysis on certain categories of sensitive data, e.g., security relevant data or personal information.

Figure 3.1.: Diagram relating terms used in binary classification. Left of the vertical line are actual positive results, right are actual negative results. The oval contains all results that are classified as positive by the algorithm. All correct classifications are colored green.

The following terms and abbreviations are defined to describe the areas of intersection between actual and classified results:

FN: False Negatives

TN: True Negatives

TP: True Positives

FP: False Positives

Based on these values, the following measures can be calculated:

FNR = $\frac{FN}{FN+TP}$: False Negative Rate

FPR = $\frac{FP}{FP+TN}$: False Positive Rate

Precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$: Fraction of relevant instances among all instances classified positive

Recall (Sensitivity) = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$: Fraction of relevant instances among all actual positive instances

F1 = $2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$: Harmonic mean of Precision and Recall

Additional information on binary classification is available on Wikipedia [49]. We modified the diagram to match the terms used in this thesis.

4. Case-Studies of the Transferred BidText Approach

So far, we have seen how BidText works and which steps are necessary to transfer the approach to JVM applications. We have refactored the codebase of BidText to make it maintainable and to prepare it for adaptation to JVM applications. Next, we have taken multiple steps to transfer the approach to JVM applications. We have removed all aspects specific to analyzing Android applications and reworked multiple parts of the program to operate on JVM bytecode. We have generalized components like the text analysis. To distinguish between the original approach for Android applications and the transferred approach for JVM applications, we will refer to the latter as *JVM-BidText*.

Let us now examine whether the adaptation work was worth the effort and conduct three case studies to examine how well the transferred BidText approach can be applied to JVM applications (**RQ 2**). We begin with the presentation of tests on small hand-crafted examples. These examples are designed to test specific aspects of JVM-BidText and to study how well JVM-BidText can handle different language constructs. We then move on to a case study on a real-world application. This case study tests JVM-BidText on a larger codebase to discover potential issues that may not arise in the hand-crafted examples. Next, we step out of the Java territory and test JVM-BidText on a small Kotlin application. This case study serves as a proof-of-concept that shows that JVM-BidText can handle applications written in other JVM languages. As modern applications are often built on top of frameworks, we conduct a final case study on a small application built on top of the popular Spring framework. We conclude the chapter with a discussion of the results of the case studies.

4.1. Test Environment

To give context to the case studies, let us describe the test environment briefly. We do not identify special system requirements. We conduct all case studies on a machine with the following specifications:

- CPU: Intel Core i7-4790K CPU @ 4.00 GHz × 4
- GPU: NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080
- RAM: 24 GB

We use the following software to run JVM-BidText:

- OS: Linux Mint 21.2 Cinnamon (Linux 5.15.0)
- JVM: BellSoft Liberica 21.0.1 (Java 21)
- IDE: IntelliJ IDEA 2024.2.2 (Ultimate Edition)

4. Case-Studies of the Transferred BidText Approach

For the hand-crafted examples, we target bytecode version 65.0 (Java 21). We compile the real-world application to bytecode version 61.0 (Java 17) as specified by its author. Regardless of the targeted bytecode version, we compile all programs with BellSoft Liberica 21.0.1. The analysis engine WALA is decisive for the Java version JVM-BidText can analyze; we use WALA 1.6.7, which supports the analysis of Java 23 and requires Java 11 or higher to run.

For sensitive data detection, we use the keyword patterns extracted from the alpaca-java library in section 3.4.4. We present the keyword patterns in appendix B. In terms of configuration, we apply the strategies discussed in section 3.4.1. We will mention major changes when they are necessary, e.g., when we add special propagation rules. In general, we try to make options for enabling or disabling changes available through the configuration files. As an example, we will see that changes to the detection of entry points will become necessary. We make it possible to configure JVM-BidText to use different entry point detection strategies, such that the interested reader can reproduce the results by changing the configurations. The README of the JVM-BidText repository¹ explains how to reproduce the results from the case studies with the latest version of JVM-BidText (commit 3062d747). To run JVM-BidText, we execute the program with the following command:

```
./gradlew run --args=<path-to-compiled-classes>
```

In the README, we include instructions on how to run and configure JVM-BidText for the different case studies.

We can perform the analysis of small real-world JVM applications (~3 kLoC) in a few seconds with memory consumption in the range of a few hundred MB at most. This holds as long as we exclude most of the standard library and external libraries from the analysis. We should consider the statements on memory consumption that JVM-BidText itself provides with caution and consider them as rough estimates. We use the inbuilt tooling for memory consumption that the original BidText provides. The measurements rely on the amount of free memory right after the analysis has finished. Garbage collection can influence the results, and leads to fluctuations in the memory consumption between different runs.

4.2. Case Study on Hand-Crafted Examples

Even though we design JVM-BidText to handle large applications, it is beneficial to evaluate the transferred approach on small examples first. This allows us to understand how well the approach can handle specific challenges and to verify that the transferred approach works as expected. Despite the extensive research conducted on static analysis in Java applications, we could not identify suitable benchmarks for the specific issue of detecting data exposures through logging. Popular benchmarks for security analysis like the Juliet Test Suite [37] developed by the NSA only offer very few examples on data exposure through logging. Relevant test cases of Juliet are for CWE-533 and CWE-534², which are about logging sensitive information to server or debug logs. These test cases are not interesting for the evaluation of JVM-BidText, however, as they do not require any data flow analysis. Instead, the test methods of the test cases pass strings indicating sensitivity directly to logging functions together with the sensitive data.

The lack of standard benchmarks offers the opportunity to create hand-crafted tests that highlight specific challenges. The tests presented in the following sections focus on different

¹See artifact description in chapter 11

²See <https://cwe.mitre.org/data/definitions/533.html> and <https://cwe.mitre.org/data/definitions/534.html>. Both CWEs are deprecated.

```

public class StaticForward {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        String s = "field_oauth_token";
        Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();
        String res = json.get(s);
        System.out.println(res);
    }
}

```

Listing 4: Simple program with a static main method for the demonstration of forward analysis

characteristics of JVM applications and test how well JVM-BidText can handle them. The test programs use different language constructs to expose JVM-BidText to different JVM bytecode instructions. In this section, we will already encounter some bytecode features we will thoroughly discuss later in section 5.2 when we start to extend the approach.

We design the hand-crafted examples to test the following aspects of JVM-BidText: We first look at a simple example that only requires forward propagation to understand the basic functionality of JVM-BidText. We present a variant of this test afterward to test the handling of negated sensitivity indicators. Then we move on to test programs, where the data exposure can only be detected if bidirectional analysis is applied. We will understand the importance of bidirectional analysis for the detection of insecure whole-object logging. To increase the complexity, we then analyze object-oriented programs with instance methods and programs with multiple classes and inheritance.

We go into detail for one example on forward and bidirectional propagation each, and provide an overview of the results for the other examples. The results of the hand-crafted tests will give us an understanding of how well JVM-BidText can handle basic JVM applications.

4.2.1. Forward Propagation in Static Method

To familiarize ourselves with JVM-BidText, we look at a simple program in detail. The program shown in listing 4 only consists of the static `main` method. The `main` method initializes an empty map and tries to retrieve a value from it with a string key. The program prints the result to the console. For testing purposes, it is irrelevant that the map is empty and that the result is `null`. The empty map resembles an unknown data collection that could have been the response from a remote service, for example. JVM-BidText does not check the actual content of the map, but infers information from the context in which it is used.

JVM-BidText runs on the compiled bytecode of the example program. The analysis completes in about 1 second with a memory consumption of 75 MB. The call graph that JVM-BidText constructs consists of 288 nodes for 178 methods. The SDG contains 40,679 nodes. For both graphs, the node count seems surprisingly high for such a small program. This is because we cannot exclude the package `java.lang` of the standard library from the analysis. As mentioned in section 3.4 superclasses like `java.lang.Object` or `java.lang.Enum` have to be present for the construction of the call graph and SDG, as custom classes inherit behavior from them. The high node count is not a problem for the custom analysis of JVM-BidText, however, as the additional nodes for standard library functions are only relevant in the preparation of the analysis, i.e., in the construction of the call graph and SDG. JVM-BidText removes all SDG

```

1 SINK [java.io.PrintStream.println(Ljava/lang/String;)V]
2 in [statics.minimal.Minimal.main([Ljava/lang/String;)V]
3
4 The following texts reached the sink:
5 - field_oauth_token
6 The following sensitivity indicators (keywords in a non-negated context) appeared:
7 - oauth_token
8
9
10 ***** field_oauth_token *****
11 NORMAL_RET_CALLER: Node: < Application, LStaticForward, main([Ljava/lang/String;)V >
12 Context: CallStringContext: [ com.ibm.wala.FakeRootClass.fakeRootMethod()V@5 ][8]
13 7 = invokeinterface <Application, Lj./u./Map, get(Lj./l./Object;)Ljava/l./Object;> 4,3
14 @13 exception:6
15
16 NORMAL main:8 = checkcast <Application,Ljava/lang/String>7 <Application,Ljava/lang/String>
17 Node: < Application, LStaticForward, main([Ljava/lang/String;)V >
18 Context: CallStringContext: [ com.ibm.wala.FakeRootClass.fakeRootMethod()V@5 ]
19
20 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, LStaticForward, main([Ljava/lang/String;)V >
21 Context: CallStringContext: [ com.ibm.wala.FakeRootClass.fakeRootMethod()V@5 ][13]
22 invokevirtual < Application, Ljava/io/PrintStream, println(Ljava/lang/String;)V > 9,8
23 @26 exception:10 v8

```

Listing 5: Report of JVM-BidText for the program in listing 4. We abbreviated some fully qualified names and added some linebreaks and indentations manually to the output.

nodes with classes from package `java.lang` in the pruning step. After pruning, the SDG for our example contains only 10 nodes, which are all from our test program.

If the SDG was even larger and a threshold of one million nodes³ was exceeded before pruning, JVM-BidText would switch to context-insensitive analysis (see section 2.2.2). If we lowered the threshold and forcefully switched to context-insensitive analysis for our example, we would cut both node counts roughly in half to 178 nodes in the call graph and 19,302 nodes in the SDG. The pruned SDG would still contain 10 nodes as before. As analysis time is low anyway, we leave the threshold unchanged.

Now that we know some basic measurements of the analysis, let us look at the results. JVM-BidText identifies a potential data exposure in the program and outputs the report shown in listing 5. We will go through the report to understand how JVM-BidText works and how it presents the results to the user. The report header shows the signature of the identified sink and the method containing it. JVM-BidText identifies `java.io.PrintStream.println(String)` as a sink in the `main` method of our test program. Next, the report lists all strings that reach the sink and which sensitivity indicators are found in the strings. In this example, JVM-BidText propagates the string `"field_oauth_token"` to the sink. This string contains the keyword `"oauth_token"`. Therefore, JVM-BidText reports `"oauth_token"` as a sensitivity indicator.

The next section of the report provides a detailed explanation of the data flow from source to sink. This information is necessary for the user to understand how data can be exposed and to verify that a data exposure is actually present. The report shows a series of SDG statements

³We carry this number over from the original version of BidText.

in WALA intermediate representation (IR). Let us walk through the statements in detail to understand how JVM-BidText constructs an exposure path, and to see what information we can infer from the report. The first statement always describes the point where JVM-BidText identifies the source, and the last statement describes the sink. In this case, the source is the return from the invocation of `HashMap.get(Object)` with the string `s`. Lines 11–14 of the report describe the return from this method invocation from the caller side. In line 11 the IR contains information on the call graph node, describing the origin of the call. For our test program, this is the `main` method of the class `StaticForward`. The IR also includes the context, i.e., the call chain leading to the invocation. For this invocation, the context only consists of the `fakeRootMethod`. This indicates that the `main` method, where this invocation resides, has not been called from another method. WALA introduces the `fakeRootMethod` to represent the entry point of the program. Line 13 finally shows the instruction describing the invocation of `HashMap.get(Object)`. The program uses an `invokeinterface` instruction to execute the invocation. We explain the different kinds of invocations later in section 5.2.2.

Let us continue with the interpretation of this IR statement and look at the numbers at the beginning and end of line 13. WALA IR uses these integers to identify values, e.g., local variables or parameters. We need to look up or infer from the textual context what meaning values at specific locations in the IR have. Value 4 at the end of line 13 maps to the object on which the method is called, in our example the program variable `json`. The parameter of the method is value 3 or variable `s` in the source code containing the string `"field_oauth_token"`. Value 7 at the beginning of line 13 represents the return value of the method invocation. We can use these value numbers to trace data between different statements in the report.

Let us see where the data flow goes next. The following statement in the report at lines 16–18 describes the implicit type cast of the return value from `Object` (type defined as return value in `Map.get`) to `String` (type of the variable `res`). We see how WALA references the return value of the method invocation from the previous statement with value number 7 and assigns number 8 to the result of the type cast.

The last statement in the report at lines 20–23 describes the invocation of the method `PrintStream.println(String)`. The class `PrintStream` is the type of the static object `System.out` which we use to print to the console. For this invocation, the instruction `invokevirtual` is used to call the method at line 22. See section 5.2.2 for an explanation of the different invocation instructions. By looking at the second integer at the end of line 22, we see that the parameter of the method is value 8. Value 8 is, as we remember, the result of the type cast from the previous statement.

For our small test program, these three statements are sufficient to describe the data flow from the source to the sink. With the information of the report, we can understand how data is exposed and verify that the analysis is correct. We can retrace the data flow in the source code in listing 4 by following the chain of instructions in the report.

4.2.2. Forward Propagation in Static Method *with Keyword Negation*

The next example is a slight modification of the previous one. We want to test whether JVM-BidText can handle negated sensitivity indicators. JVM-BidText is supposed to ignore them when identifying data exposures. We perform a test with the same program as in section 4.2.1 and only change the string `s` from `"field_oauth_token"` to `"Do not enter secret here"`. The new string contains the keyword `"secret"`, but the keyword is negated by the word `"not"`. While we would not expect such a string to appear as a key for a JSON map, it can very well

appear somewhere else in an application. For testing, we do not want to change the program structure to be able to compare the results to those of the previous analysis.

We would expect JVM-BidText to not report any data exposure for the adapted example program. The reason is that there is a special natural language processing step in the analysis just like in the original BidText. The special processing can identify negated sensitivity indicators. Therefore, JVM-BidText should treat such strings with negations the same as strings without any keywords. At first, however, JVM-BidText does generate a report for this program just like in the previous example.

Debugging of the string analysis proves that the negation handling is not working as expected, likely because the API of the natural language processing library has changed slightly between versions. Problems did not arise earlier because the library provides an API partially based on constants encoded in strings. We implement a quick fix to the issue and rerun the analysis. This time, JVM-BidText identifies correctly that the string `"Do not enter secret here"` does not indicate sensitivity because of a negation. As a consequence, JVM-BidText does not report any data exposure in the program.

If we remember that we only exchanged the string `s` between this analysis and the previous one, the runtime and memory consumption of this second example seem unusually high. The runtime of just over 2 seconds is twice as long as for the previous example. Memory consumption increases to 120 MB, which is 50% more than before. The reason for the increase is that the expensive natural language processing step is only executed if JVM-BidText detects that a string could be a sentence. In this case, the string `"Do not enter secret here"` contains spaces and is therefore considered a sentence. In consequence, JVM-BidText executes the natural language processing step, which increases the runtime and memory consumption. In contrast, the string `"field_oauth_token"` from the previous example contains no spaces, such that JVM-BidText could skip the natural language processing step in the analysis of the first example.

4.2.3. Bidirectional Propagation in Static Methods

In the previous examples, forward propagation was sufficient to detect the data exposure or lack thereof. The source was always located before the sink. Both the source and the sink were in the same data flow path. Such a problem can be solved with more traditional data flow analysis as well. Following the terminology used for taint analysis, we can call the location where sensitive data is marked as such *tainting* and the exposure of data *leaking*. In examples where we deliberately use certain code to mark data as sensitive, we will use the term *tainting* to describe our intention.

We design the following example, to demonstrate JVM-BidText's special ability of bidirectional propagation. The example consists of the program in listing 6 where the sink is before the source, i.e., where the leak occurs before the tainting. JVM-BidText can therefore identify the sensitivity of the exposed data in our intentional tainting method only after the data has been leaked. Source and sink are in different data flow paths. The program has the same functionality as the one in listing 4, but the order of the statements is reversed. Furthermore, we separate leaking and tainting into two methods, which further complicates the analysis as JVM-BidText needs to process parameter passing.

Let us turn to the results of the analysis of the program in listing 6. JVM-BidText detects the data exposure in this program. The analysis completes in about 1 second with a memory consumption of 75 MB like in the first examples, where JVM-BidText skipped the natural

```

public class StaticBidirectional {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();
        leak(json);
        taint(json);
    }

    private static void taint(Map<String, String> json) {
        String s = "field_oauth_token";
        json.get(s);
    }

    private static void leak(Map<String, String> json) {
        System.out.println(json);
    }
}

```

Listing 6: Simple program with static methods for the demonstration of bidirectional analysis and parameter passing

language processing step. As we use a string without spaces, JVM-BidText skips the natural language processing step in this example as well.

Let us look at the report in listing 7 to understand how JVM-BidText handles the bidirectional data flow and parameter passing. The report header states correctly that the sink is in the method `leak`. If we focus on the description of the path leading to the sink, we see that the first statement at lines 6–8 identifies the source and has the same shape as in the first example. The main difference is that the source is now in the method `taint` and not in the `main` method.

The following two statements describe the parameter passing between `main` and `taint`. The `PARAM_CALLEE` statement at lines 10–11 describes the invocation of `taint` from `main` from the perspective of the callee, i.e., the method `taint`. The `PARAM_CALLER` statement at lines 13–15 describes the same invocation from the perspective of the caller, i.e., the method `main`. We see that the target for `invokestatic` in line 15 matches the signature of the callee in line 10.

Next follow two statements, once again describing the parameter passing for a method invocation —this time from `main` to `leak`. We notice that the `PARAM_CALLER` statement appears before the `PARAM_CALLEE` statement. This is because we switched the direction of analysis. When we start the analysis from the source, we step backward from `taint` to `main`. Once we reach `main`, we follow the forward data flow from `main` to `leak`.

The last statement in the report looks familiar to us from the previous examples. It describes the execution of `System.out.println(json)`; and thereby our sink.

From this example, we can see that JVM-BidText can handle bidirectional propagation. The analysis can identify data exposures even if the data is exposed before JVM-BidText can determine the sensitivity of the data. Let us perform a quick thought experiment to understand the implications of this. Why is this feature important? Imagine that we rename the methods of the example from this case study. We rename the method `leak` to `printDebugInfo` and the method `taint` to `handleAuthentication`. Instead of initializing the map `json` with an empty map, we store the response from a remote service in it, e.g., the result of a login request

```

1 SINK [java.io.PrintStream.println(Ljava/lang/Object;)V]
2   in [StaticBidirectional.leak(Ljava/util/Map;)V]
3   (...)
4
5 ***** field_oauth_token *****
6 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: <(...)StaticBidirectional, taint(Ljava/util/Map;)V >
7   Context: CallStringContext: [StaticBidirectional.main(...)]
8     5 = invokeinterface <(...)Map, get(Ljava/lang/Object;)Ljava/lang/Object; > 1,3 (...)
9
10 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: <(...)StaticBidirectional, taint(Ljava/util/Map;)V >
11   Context: CallStringContext: [ StaticBidirectional.main(...)] v1
12
13 PARAM_CALLER:Node: <(...)StaticBidirectional, main([Ljava/lang/String;)V >
14   Context: CallStringContext: [(...)fakeRootMethod()V@5 ][7]
15   invokestatic < Application, LStaticBidirectional, taint(Ljava/util/Map;)V > 3 (...)
16
17 PARAM_CALLER:Node: <(...)StaticBidirectional, main([Ljava/lang/String;)V >
18   Context: CallStringContext: [(...)fakeRootMethod()V@5 ][5]
19   invokestatic < Application, LStaticBidirectional, leak(Ljava/util/Map;)V > 3 (...)
20
21 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: <(...)StaticBidirectional, leak(Ljava/util/Map;)V >
22   Context: CallStringContext: [StaticBidirectional.main(...)] v1
23
24 PARAM_CALLER:Node: <(...)StaticBidirectional, leak(Ljava/util/Map;)V >
25   Context: CallStringContext: [ StaticBidirectional.main(...)] [2]
26   invokevirtual < Application, Ljava/io/PrintStream, println(Lj./l./Object;)V > 3,1 (...)

```

Listing 7: Abbreviated report of JVM-BidText for the program in listing 6. We abbreviated some fully qualified names and added some linebreaks and indentations manually to the output. We indicate omissions by (...).

to "<https://example.com/api/v1/auth/login>". We present this imaginary application in listing 8. Due to the use of a pseudocode HTTP service, this example will not compile.

Suddenly, the example seems a lot more realistic. In this scenario, the developer might not be aware of the exact structure of the response from the remote service. Therefore, the developer decides to log the whole response object for debugging purposes. Only after the logging, the developer further processes the object. This is a perfect example for whole-object logging. We have mentioned in the introduction that insecure whole-object logging is the most common root cause for sensitive data exposure vulnerabilities [40]. As we only rename the methods and change the initialization of the map in comparison to the original version of this example, the analysis with JVM-BidText would be the same. In the face of this example, we can see the importance of bidirectional propagation for realistic use cases.

At this point, we can conclude that JVM-BidText can handle both forward and backward propagation for basic static programs with multiple methods. This enables JVM-BidText to identify data exposures even if the source and the sink are in different data flow paths. This is a crucial feature for the effective detection of data exposures caused by whole-object logging. It is now time to test JVM-BidText on more complex programs.

```

public class StaticBidirectionalRealistic {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Map<String, String> json = myHttpService.performPostRequest(
            "https://example.com/api/v1/auth/login", credentials);
        printDebugInfo(json);
        handleAuthentication(json);
    }

    private static void handleAuthentication(Map<String, String> json) {
        String s = "field_oauth_token";
        json.get(s);
    }

    private static void printDebugInfo(Map<String, String> json) {
        System.out.println(json);
    }
}

```

Listing 8: Imaginary application for the demonstration of whole-object logging. This example is adapted from listing 6.

4.2.4. Tests with Instance Methods

To increase the complexity of the test programs, we now slowly step into object-oriented territory. We test JVM-BidText on multiple programs that create instances of custom classes and call instance methods on them. Difficulties arise from multiple aspects. The analysis has to handle the creation of objects and passing parameters between different kinds of methods. Furthermore, the analysis has to deal with the fact that the same method can be called on different objects. The analysis must not mix up the data flow between independent objects in such cases. JVM-BidText has to handle field accesses and the corresponding bytecode instructions both for static and instance fields correctly.

Because we discussed how bidirectional propagation in JVM-BidText works in detail in the previous sections, we do not go into detail for the examples with instance methods. The interested reader can reproduce the results by using the provided test suite execution tool with our collection of test programs called `LeakyCode`⁴.

We run JVM-BidText on a collection of test programs with instance methods. These programs contain the challenges we discussed in the introduction to this section. After evaluating the results from the described tests, we can summarize that JVM-BidText can handle propagation with instance methods and field accesses. JVM-BidText identifies data exposures in our example programs correctly, even with convoluted method call chains. If we leak information for one instance and taint it for another, JVM-BidText can distinguish between the two and does not report any data exposure. Methods, not related to the data flow path containing the source and the sink, do not appear in the reports. JVM-BidText handles our most difficult scenario in this part of the test set correctly. In this test program, the leak occurs in an instance method of an object; the tainting happens on a static shared field after the sink has already been executed. For all test programs, runtime and memory consumption are in the same range as for the previous examples without the natural language processing step.

⁴See artifact description in chapter 11

4.2.5. Tests with Multi-Class Programs

As a final step in our collection of hand-crafted examples, we test JVM-BidText on multi-class programs. The analysis has to handle the creation of objects in one class and method calls on them from another class. When analyzing multi-class programs, the analysis has to handle the passing of objects, possibly containing sensitive data, between classes. Leaking can occur in one class and tainting in another if both classes interact with the same objects. As for the other examples in previous sections, JVM-BidText detects data exposures in the multi-class programs as expected. The additional complexity does not seem to affect runtime and memory consumption significantly.

When working with multiple classes, a scenario of special interest is inheritance. If a class inherits from another class, the analysis has to cope with methods that are not directly defined in the class but inherited from a superclass. For invocations of such methods, JVM-BidText has to handle different bytecode instructions, in particular the `invokespecial` instruction. We provide a comparison of different invocation instructions in section 5.2.2. Again, JVM-BidText handles these challenges and identifies data exposures in the test programs correctly. The runtime and memory consumption are in the same range as for the previous examples.

4.2.6. Conclusions from the Case Study on Hand-Crafted Examples

Over the course of the previous sections, we have exposed JVM-BidText to various challenges increasing in complexity. JVM-BidText has analyzed all test programs so far correctly. We can therefore say that JVM-BidText can handle basic object-oriented JVM applications. This result is promising, but before we draw conclusions on the success of transferring BidText to JVM applications, we conduct further tests on a real-world application, an example in another JVM language, and on an application built on top of a framework.

4.3. Case Study on Real-World Application

We designed the hand-crafted examples to test specific aspects of the JVM-BidText approach and to understand how well it can handle different challenges. With the results from the previous sections, we gain confidence that the approach can be applied to generic JVM applications. To further validate this impression, we will now test JVM-BidText on a real-world application. This offers the opportunity to test the approach on a larger codebase and discover potential issues that did not arise in the hand-crafted examples.

The real-world application we use for the case study is the alpaca-java library⁵ used for interacting with the Alpaca trading platform⁶. Remember that we already encountered this library in the study on keywords in section 3.4.4. We choose this library with about 3kLoC because it is from a domain likely to handle sensitive data. Further criteria for the selection of the library are that it is open source and reasonably popular on GitHub. Because JVM-BidText runs on bytecode, we need to be able to compile the test program without much additional setup or configuration work. As this is a case study, we have one additional requirement for the test program: it should contain at least one sensitive data exposure that we can find in a manual analysis. This is necessary to verify the results of the analysis. For a real-world project, we cannot easily prove the absence of sensitive data exposures in a manual analysis.

⁵See artifact description in chapter 11

⁶See <https://alpaca.markets>

Therefore, if JVM-BidText reported no data exposure and our test program contained no manually detectable sensitive data exposure, we could not draw any conclusions from the results of the analysis. We can, however, verify positive findings by manual analysis. For our final choice, `alpaca-java`, we could identify two related data exposures manually in advance. We will discuss the data exposures in section 4.3.3.

In the following sections, we discuss the results of the analysis on the `alpaca-java` library and the challenges we face during the analysis. We start by discussing the detection of entry points, which is non-trivial for libraries. Afterward, we present the results of the first analysis attempt and discuss the issues we encounter. To circumvent these issues, we implement a workaround for a limitation of WALA, rerun the analysis and discuss the discovered data exposures. In the discussion of the discovered data exposures, we also examine false positives. Finally, we draw conclusions from the case study on `alpaca-java`.

4.3.1. Detection of Entry Points into Libraries

When we run JVM-BidText on the `alpaca-java` library, or any library for that matter, we face an additional challenge. Let us remember the discussion on entry points back in section 2.2.1. We noted that libraries do not have a `main` method and therefore no obvious entry point. As our test program for this case study is a library, we have to find a way to detect the entry points for the analysis.

In the case of the `alpaca-java` library, the code defines handlers for incoming HTTP requests from the servers of the trading platform. This is a common pattern for tools that provide an API to interact with a service. Detecting these handler methods as entry points is a similar problem to the one Huang, Zhang, and Tan encountered with Android applications in the original BidText [35]. In the context of Android, an application has to define callback methods for the framework.

Huang, Zhang, and Tan have multiple strategies to detect entry points in Android applications. Among them is one that relies on naming conventions for callback methods. They search for methods that are named `on*`, are public and override a method from a superclass that is not `java.lang.Object`. We can adapt this algorithm to detect entry points into the `alpaca-java` library. We need to implement slight modifications to work with our reworked setup of WALA. Further, we modify the algorithm to reject methods as entry points that override methods from the application code instead of methods from an external library or framework. This way, we eliminate internal calls from being detected as entry points. This is necessary because `alpaca-java` uses the naming pattern `on*` for methods that are called from within the application code and not only for methods called by the HTTP library. Remember that we want to detect the latter as entry points. Internal callbacks, on the other hand, are not relevant as the analysis can reach them when starting at an actual entry point. When we apply the adapted entry point algorithm to the `alpaca-library`, we find the expected callback methods for the HTTP library.

In general, this approach for detecting entry points can find entry points triggered by external controllers. In our example, events from the external trading platform trigger the entry points via the callback mechanisms of the HTTP library. Because the algorithm relies on naming conventions, we might miss entry points that do not follow these conventions. The entry point discovery algorithm does not find entry points triggered by users of the library, i.e., developers who integrate the library. We cannot detect these entry points without additional information if we would rather not include all public methods as entry points. Nevertheless, this approach is a good starting point and sufficient for the case study on the `alpaca-java` library.

4.3.2. Analysis of the alpaca-java Library

Now that we have found entry points into the alpaca-java library, we can continue with the analysis setup and the actual analysis. To get JVM-BidText running on alpaca-java, we have to adapt the analysis configuration slightly. We partially add three external libraries to the analysis scope. This is necessary because some classes in alpaca-java inherit from classes of these libraries. Without the presence of the superclasses, WALA could not process the bytecode of alpaca-java. As an effect of this change, we expect the analysis to run slightly slower because WALA has to construct the call graph and SDG based on more internal calls. Discovered paths between source and sink might contain calls to methods from the external libraries. To limit the impact of the external libraries on the analysis, we set exclusions for many packages of the external libraries. Only the classes used as superclasses need to be present. Remember that we discussed the necessity of superclasses and the process of excluding packages from the analysis in section 3.4.1.

With this configuration change implemented, we can start the analysis. JVM-BidText completes the analysis in about 2.7 seconds with a memory consumption of 105 MB. We can explain the higher runtime with the additional complexity of the significantly larger code base of alpaca-java in comparison to the hand-crafted examples. For many entry points, the size of the SDG exceeds 1000 nodes after pruning. This is two orders of magnitude more than in the hand-crafted examples.

With this in mind it is almost surprising that, the memory consumption is only slightly higher than in most previous examples. The increase is likely due to the higher number of classes that JVM-BidText needs to process; the project itself is larger, but we also include some additional classes from the external libraries for access to super class code. The memory consumption is still below the example from section 4.2.2 where we inspected a program where JVM-BidText could not skip the natural language processing step. As it turns out none of the static strings in the alpaca-java library contain spaces. Therefore, JVM-BidText can skip the natural language processing step for sentences in this analysis as well. We can conclude that the natural language processing step has a larger impact on memory consumption than the increase in the number of classes in the analysis scope. The impact of increasing the project size is higher on runtime than on memory consumption.

Let us turn to the results of the analysis. JVM-BidText does not report any data exposure in the library. This is surprising, as we find at least two data exposures in a manual analysis of the library. We verify that the data exposures can be reached by the entry points detected with our algorithm, and come to the conclusion that JVM-BidText should have discovered them as well.

Let us investigate the unexpected behavior of JVM-BidText. Listing 9 shows an excerpt of the alpaca-java library where we found one of the data exposures. The entry point that leads to the data exposure is the method `onOpen` in the class `AlpacaWebsocket`. We will discuss how the method `onOpen` leads to a data exposure in the next section. When we look at the code snippet, we see that the method `onOpen` uses a lambda expression to call other methods asynchronously. As lambda expressions are generally considered difficult to analyze, we have to contemplate that the issue of not finding the data exposure might be related to the lambda expression in the method `onOpen`. To test this hypothesis, we remove the lambda expression from the method, such that the call to the method `onConnection` is made directly. Afterward, we rerun the analysis. JVM-BidText does still not report any data exposure in the library, which indicates that the issue is not related to the lambda expression.

```

public abstract class AlpacaWebsocket extends WebSocketListener /*(...)*/ {
    private WebSocket websocket;
    @Override // Entry point - called by the HTTP library
    public void onOpen(/* (...) */) {
        // (...)
        commonPool().execute(() -> {
            if (reconnectAttempts > 0) {
                onReconnection();
            } else {
                onConnection(); // Call to abstract method
            }
        });
        // (...)
    }
    protected abstract void onConnection();
    protected void sendWebsocketMessage(String message) {
        // (...)
        LOGGER.trace("Websocket message sent: {}", message); // Sink
        websocket.send(message);
    }
}

public class UpdatesWebsocket extends AlpacaWebsocket /* (...) */ {
    @Override // Implementation of abstract method
    protected void onConnection() {
        sendAuthenticationMessage();
    }
    @Override
    protected void sendAuthenticationMessage() {
        // (...)
        final JsonObject authObject = new JsonObject();
        authObject.addProperty("action", "authenticate");
        final JsonObject authData = new JsonObject();
        if (oAuthToken != null) {
            authData.addProperty("oauth_token", oAuthToken); // Source
        } else {
            authData.addProperty("key_id", keyID); // Source
            authData.addProperty("secret_key", secretKey); // Source
        }
        authObject.add("data", authData);
        LOGGER.info("{} websocket sending authentication message...",
            websocketName);
        sendWebsocketMessage(authObject.toString());
    }
}

```

Listing 9: Excerpt of the alpaca-java library with a data exposure. We added comments for context.

To examine the problem further, we look at the logs of the analysis. We discover that the SDG generated for the relevant entry point, that leads to our manually detected data exposure, is empty. Upon further troubleshooting, we find out that our JVM-BidText analysis is affected by a known issue in WALA. Sridharan —an author of WALA— states in a GitHub issue still unresolved as of the time of writing, that WALA’s implementation of the CHA call graph only contains concrete but no abstract methods [48]. As it turns out, this behavior can explain the problem we encounter in our analysis.

Let us look back at the code snippet in listing 9 to understand the issue. The entry point method `onOpen` does not invoke further methods directly, but rather the abstract definition of `onConnection` defined in the same class, i.e., `AlpacaWebsocket`. The method `onConnection` is implemented in the class `UpdatesWebsocket` which inherits from `AlpacaWebsocket`. Apparently, the CHA call graph construction algorithm in WALA cannot apprehend the call to the abstract method and subsequently make the connection to the implementation in the subclass. As a consequence, the SDG for the method `onOpen` is empty, which renders it impossible for JVM-BidText to conduct further analysis and find the data exposure. To continue with the case study we need to find a workaround for this limitation of WALA.

4.3.3. Detection of Data Exposures in the alpaca-java Library

We have just seen that no data exposure in the alpaca-java library is detected by JVM-BidText due to a limitation in WALA. Even though we subsequently consider this behavior as a limitation of JVM-BidText, we can still study whether JVM-BidText can identify the data exposure in the library correctly if we implement a workaround.

The idea is to skip the abstract method and choose the implementation of the abstract method in the subclass as the entry point. As a workaround, we can modify the entry point detection algorithm introduced in section 4.3.1. The algorithm only considers methods that start with the prefix "on". Previously, we have rejected methods as entry points that override methods from the application code. We now allow methods that override abstract methods from the application code and only reject methods overriding non-abstract methods. With this modification, we can detect the method `onConnection` in the class `UpdatesWebsocket`. Because this method acts as an internal handler for the original entry point `onOpen`, we deem it suitable as an entry point into parts of the library.

When we rerun the analysis with the workaround that includes `onConnection` in the class `UpdatesWebsocket` as an entry point, JVM-BidText identifies data exposures in the library. We want to reconstruct how exactly data is exposed in the alpaca-java library. If we look back at the code snippet in listing 9, we see that the new entry point method `onConnection` calls the method `sendAuthenticationMessage`. The latter creates a `JsonObject` and adds sensitive data to it, e.g., the OAuth token or a secret key used for authentication with the trading platform. We have added comments to the code snippet to indicate these sources. The logging statement directly following the creation of the `JsonObject` does not leak any data as it only logs a generic string and the name of the websocket. Instead, the data exposure occurs when the `JsonObject` is passed to the method `sendWebsocketMessage` inherited from the superclass `AlpacaWebsocket`. The method `sendWebsocketMessage` logs the complete message content before sending it to the server. Logging the complete message might be useful for debugging purposes, but it exposes potentially sensitive data to the logs of the application. We have marked the offending logging statement in the method `sendWebsocketMessage` in the code snippet with a comment. This is a case of insecure whole-object logging, which we remember

as the most common root cause for sensitive data exposure vulnerabilities [40].

JVM-BidText identifies the method `sendWebsocketMessage` correctly as a sink and generates the report we present in listing 30 in appendix C. The report includes a path of IR statements that describe the data flow from the source to the sink. The path matches the data flow we have just described on a source code level.

There is a second data exposure that JVM-BidText reports for the alpaca-java library. This data exposure is very similar to the one we described in the previous paragraph. The main difference is the context of all calls. Apart from that, the path is identical to the one we have just discussed. JVM-BidText reports these two cases as separate exposures because the method `sendAuthenticationMessage` is not only called from `onConnection`, but also from `onReconnection`. As we employ context-sensitive analysis, it is correct to report the two data exposures separately. Listing 31 in appendix C contains the report corresponding to the second data exposure in the alpaca-java library. In the report, we observe a minor second difference. For the second data exposure, JVM-BidText propagates a few additional non-sensitive strings to the sink. This is because the method `onReconnection` executes additional code that contains non-sensitive strings. These strings reach the sink for the same reason that we will discuss in the next section when we talk about false positives.

Apart from these two verifiable data exposures, BidText also reports two more data exposures in the library. We can identify both as false positives upon manual analysis, however. We discuss these false positives and how to handle them in the next section.

4.3.4. Examination of False Positives

The analysis of the alpaca-java library with JVM-BidText reveals two sensitive data exposures that we can verify by manual analysis. In addition to these true positives, JVM-BidText reports two data exposures that we consider false positive. Let us analyze how these false positives occur to judge whether they are expected behavior or arise from issues with the analysis.

The first false positive identifies a data exposure in the method `sendWebsocketMessage` in the class `AlpacaWebsocket`. Listing 32 in appendix C contains the corresponding report. As we have seen in the previous section, the method `sendWebsocketMessage` actually is a sink for sensitive data. The reason we consider this alarm a false positive arises from the fact that JVM-BidText specifies a path from the source to the sink, that should not exist. The path contains statements that concern a seemingly unrelated method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage`. We will discuss the details shortly.

The second false positive concerns a sink in the method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` we just mentioned. Listing 10 contains an excerpt of the class `UpdatesWebsocket` with the method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage`. Manual inspection of the method reveals that it only handles non-sensitive data. Therefore, no leak occurs when `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` calls `sendWebsocketMessage`, which is known to expose all data passed to it. As the method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` handles no sensitive data, the log statement in the message `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` itself is not a sensitive data exposure either. Listing 33 in appendix C contains the corresponding report.

Both false positives occur for the same reason. To understand why the false positives occur, let us first remember how JVM-BidText identifies data exposures. In section 2.5, we discussed that JVM-BidText analyzes the texts that have been propagated to a sink and checks for the presence of sensitivity indicators. This means that for the two reports under investigation,

```

public class UpdatesWebsocket extends AlpacaWebsocket /* (...) */ {
    // (...)
    private void sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage() {
        final JsonObject requestObject = new JsonObject();
        // (...)
        final JsonArray streamsArray = new JsonArray();
        // (...)
        final JsonObject dataObject = new JsonObject();
        dataObject.add("streams", streamsArray);
        requestObject.add("data", dataObject);

        sendWebsocketMessage(requestObject.toString());
        // Sink, but no sensitive data leak
        LOGGER.info("Requested streams: streams={}.", streamsArray);
    }
}

```

Listing 10: Excerpt of the `alpaca-java` library showing the harmless method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` involved in false positives. Listing 9 shows other parts of the class. We added comments for context.

JVM-BidText must have propagated some supposedly sensitive text to the potential sinks. There are two possibilities why this can lead to a false positive. Either the supposedly sensitive text is not sensitive, or the sensitive text is propagated to the sink in a way that we do not consider as reaching the sink in a manual analysis. By looking at the reports and inspecting the sensitivity indicators, we can eliminate the first possibility. Instead, we focus on the paths that JVM-BidText specifies in the reports to investigate the second possibility. We can use the path information in the reports to follow the data flow from the source to the sink and see from where to where JVM-BidText propagates strings.

For both false positives, JVM-BidText identifies the source of sensitive information as the method `sendAuthenticationMessage` in the class `UpdatesWebsocket`. We have already seen that this method indeed handles sensitive data and is a source. In the case of the false positives, the path continues with statements describing how data flows from `sendAuthenticationMessage` to the statement `websocket.send(message);` in the method `sendWebsocketMessage`. We note for a later discussion that both paths reach a bytecode statement that accesses the instance field `websocket` to retrieve the object on which the call `websocket.send(message);` is executed. We have seen a similar data flow path for the true positives and know that the processing of `sendAuthenticationMessage` causes a data exposure. For the two false positives, the data flow paths continue differently. For the first false positive, statements follow that describe how `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` uses `sendWebsocketMessage` to send non-sensitive data. For the second false positive, statements follow that describe how `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` logs its non-sensitive message. In both cases, no sensitive data is passed from `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` to a logging statement directly, or to `sendWebsocketMessage` which would expose the data.

So why does JVM-BidText still report two data exposures that involve the seemingly unrelated method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage`? The issue arises from the way types are propagated and merged in the analysis. If we remember how JVM-BidText handles method invocations,

```
[instance] okhttp3.WebSocket.send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z 0>=1
```

Listing 11: Custom propagation rule for the method `send` of the class `WebSocket`. The rule instructs JVM-BidText not to propagate types between the target of the call (0) and the only parameter (1).

we know that there are multiple ways JVM-BidText can act on invocations. Section 2.3 explains that for generic invocations JVM-BidText merges the types of the parameter and the target of a call, i.e., the object a method is called on. We can use this information to explain the false positives. The sensitive strings appearing in `sendAuthenticationMessage` are propagated to the object `websocket` when sending the message. The seemingly unrelated method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` uses the same object `websocket` to send non-sensitive data. Because the object `websocket` is already typed with the sensitive strings from `sendAuthenticationMessage`, JVM-BidText propagates the sensitive strings to the log statement in `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage`. This explains why the second false positive with the report in listing 33 occurs.

But even if `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage` did not contain the log statement, JVM-BidText would still report a data exposure. At some point, the `websocket` object is tainted with sensitive strings. For any invocation of `sendWebSocketMessage` JVM-BidText builds a connection between the message and the sensitive types of the `websocket` object. Because `sendWebSocketMessage` logs all messages sent through the socket, JVM-BidText reports all calls to `sendWebSocketMessage` as data exposures, regardless of the actual content of the message. This can explain the first false positive with the report in listing 32.

Now that we understand *why* JVM-BidText reports these cases as data exposures, we can discuss, whether this behavior is justifiable or not. Why do we not consider the cases as data exposures in a manual analysis? It all comes down to whether we assume that the `websocket` shares information on its messages between multiple sending instructions. In the manual analysis, we assume the `websocket` to be some sort of communication infrastructure that sends messages directly to its target without storing them or retaining any information. JVM-BidText on the other hand, does not know about the semantics of the `websocket` and treats it as any other generic object. For generic objects, JVM-BidText is designed to propagate all types from parameters of method invocations to the object and to the parameters of further method invocations. This way, JVM-BidText treats the object `websocket` as if it shared all messages it has ever received with all methods that interact with the socket.

If no information about the semantics of a method call is available, the concept of merging types is a valid approach to handle possible internal data flow pessimistically. This means that we assume that all data is shared between all methods that interact with an object. In our case, we know that the object `websocket` (probably) does not share any information between different calls. We can therefore consider the alarms as false positives that arise from a lack of semantic information about the object `websocket` and its `send` instance method.

Even though we consider JVM-BidText's behavior in these cases as correct, preventing the false positives would be desirable. JVM-BidText provides a mechanism to provide semantic information for special methods. In sections 2.3 and 3.4.1, we discussed the concept of custom propagation rules. Such a rule can easily be defined for the method `send` of the class `WebSocket`. In listing 11 we show the rule that we need to add to the file `ApiPropagationRules.txt`.

The rule encodes our semantic knowledge / assumption that the websocket does not share any information between different calls. The rule defines that JVM-BidText should not propagate types from the parameter to the target object or vice versa for this specific method. With this rule in place, JVM-BidText does not report the false positives anymore. The two true positives in the library are still reported because the sensitive data is exposed in the method `sendWebSocketMessage` directly without the involvement of the object `websocket`.

4.3.5. Conclusions from the Case Study on the alpaca-java Library

The case study on the alpaca-java library indicates that JVM-BidText can detect non-trivial data exposures in real-world applications. As long as sufficient semantic information on propagation in special methods is present, we can verify all alarms that JVM-BidText reports by manual analysis. JVM-BidText’s analysis completes quickly and with reasonable memory consumption, even for a program of a few thousand lines of code.

The case study reveals that JVM-BidText is not free of limitations. Let us quickly recapitulate the limitations we have encountered. If libraries do not have a `main` method, we have to detect entry points by other means. One approach is to detect callback methods, that are triggered by external events, based on naming conventions. This approach is not a general way to detect entry points, however, and is likely to not find all methods that could be considered entry points.

The case study also reveals a limitation in WALA that affects the analysis of abstract methods. Depending on how we use abstract methods, this limitation can lead to false negatives or even a complete failure of the analysis.

Further, we have observed that manual configuration can be necessary to prevent false positives in the analysis. While it is impossible to provide propagation rules for all methods of all libraries, one can provide rules for the most relevant methods of popular libraries⁷. Users of JVM-BidText can extend such a list of rules to cover the methods of the libraries they use.

In general, the limitations we have encountered are present in the original approach of Huang, Zhang, and Tan and are not specific to our transfer of the approach to JVM applications. Huang, Zhang, and Tan have not mentioned the issue with abstract methods in their work, but the issue is likely to be present in their approach as well, as they also rely on WALA for the analysis of Android applications. Some limitations like finding entry points into libraries might be of greater importance in the context of JVM applications, however, as JVM applications can be more diverse than Android applications.

Speaking of diversity in JVM applications, we want to test JVM-BidText on a small application written in another JVM compatible programming language.

4.4. Case Study on Kotlin Application

Our focus in this thesis is on the analysis of Java applications. However, JVM-BidText is not limited to Java applications. As JVM-BidText operates on the bytecode level, it can theoretically analyze applications written in any programming language that compiles to JVM bytecode. This is also the reason we call our tool *JVM-BidText* and not *Java-BidText*. While we

⁷We refrain from constructing a list of rules for popular libraries in this thesis and confine ourselves to the example in listing 11.

```

fun main() {
    val map = mapOf("a" to "aValue", "b" to "bValue")
    println(map["field_oauth_token"])
}

```

Listing 12: Kotlin application for the case study on Kotlin applications

```

1 ***** field_oauth_token *****
2 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lorg/example/MainKt, main()V >
3   Context: CallStringContext: [ org.example.MainKt.main([Ljava/lang/String;)V@0 ][20]
4   18 = invokeinterface <Application, Lj./u./Map, get(Lj./l./Object;)Lj./l./Object;> 15,16
5   @33 exception:17
6
7 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lorg/example/MainKt, main()V >
8   Context: CallStringContext: [ org.example.MainKt.main([Ljava/lang/String;)V@0 ][23]
9   invokevirtual <Application, Ljava/io/PrintStream, println(Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 19,18
10  @42 exception:20 v18

```

Listing 13: Excerpt of the report for the Kotlin application. We abbreviated some fully qualified names and added some linebreaks and indentations manually to the output.

know that JVM-BidText can handle Java applications, we have not yet tested it on applications written in other JVM compatible programming languages.

Apart from Java, Kotlin⁸ is one of the most popular programming languages that compiles to JVM bytecode. Kotlin often appears in combination with Java and is fully interoperable with Java. We want to test whether JVM-BidText can handle Kotlin applications as well. To this end, we analyze a basic Kotlin application that is similar to the example from section 4.2.1. We present the Kotlin application in listing 12 and in the repository LeakyKotlin⁹.

We compile the Kotlin application and run JVM-BidText on the resulting class file. The analysis completes in about one second and with a memory consumption of roughly 70 MB. This matches the performance we have seen in the case study on the hand-crafted Java examples. As expected, JVM-BidText reports a data exposure in the Kotlin application. We present the part of the report that contains the path from the source to the sink in listing 13.

The report consists of only two IR statements that describe the data flow from `Map.get` to `PrintStream.println`. We notice that the report mentions methods of the Java standard library, even though the application is written in Kotlin. This hints at the internal implementation of Kotlin and the interoperability of Kotlin with Java. We compare the report to the one for the Java example for forward analysis in static methods from section 4.2.1 (see listing 4 for the Java program and listing 5 for the corresponding report). Both reports share plenty of similarities. In particular, for both applications, JVM-BidText identifies the source as a call to `Map.get` and the sink as a call to `PrintStream.println`. In contrast to the reports of the Java example, the report for the Kotlin example does not contain a `checkcast` IR statement. The reason is that in the Kotlin example, we do not store the result of the `Map.get` call in a variable of type `String`. Instead, we pass the result directly to the `PrintStream.println`

⁸See <https://kotlinlang.org>

⁹See artifact description in chapter 11

method. Upon close inspection of the reports, we see that the examples use different overloads of the `println` method. In the Java example, we use the overload that takes a `String` as an argument. In the Kotlin example, we use the overload that takes an `Object` as an argument. This is why the Kotlin example is typed correctly even without a `checkcast` IR statement.

This example serves as a proof of concept that JVM-BidText can handle JVM applications not written in Java. As this topic is not the focus of our thesis, we decide not to go into detail with this feature. We recognize the need for further testing of JVM-BidText on applications written in Kotlin and other JVM compatible programming languages. Nonetheless, we consider the general capability to analyze JVM applications written in different programming languages as a significant accomplishment of JVM-BidText. Before drawing final conclusions from our case studies, we want to test one more scenario with Java applications that might highlight additional challenges.

4.5. Case Study on Spring Application

After the excursion to Kotlin, we return to Java applications. Despite the limitations we have encountered in the case study on the `alpaca-java` library, we see JVM-BidText as a valuable tool for the analysis of real-world applications possibly depending on external libraries. All the external libraries we have encountered in `alpaca-java` support certain use-cases, but none of them dictate the structure of the application. In reality, many applications go further than using a few external libraries. Especially large-scale applications are often built on top of frameworks which define a standardized architecture that the developer extends.

Frameworks provide solutions for common tasks, such as handling HTTP requests, database access, or dependency injection. Johnson and Foote capture the essence of this concept by defining a framework as “a set of classes that embodies an abstract design for solutions to a family of related problems” [1]. To accomplish these benefits, frameworks guide the developer in the design of an application and enforce certain patterns and structures. In this regard, Mattsson identifies that inversion of control (IoC) is a distinguishing feature of object-oriented frameworks [15]. This means that the framework can control the flow of the application. The framework calls methods in the application code through hooks and template methods, rather than the application code (solely) calling methods in the framework. As a consequence, a lot of essential functionality is implemented in the framework and not in the application code. Because JVM-BidText generally only analyzes the application code and not the framework code, we can expect that the analysis of applications built on top of frameworks will be more difficult than the analysis of applications that only use libraries. To further test the capabilities of JVM-BidText, we now analyze a small application built on top of the popular Spring framework¹⁰.

To test whether JVM-BidText can handle central features of the Spring framework, we develop a simple Spring Boot application¹¹. First, we need to decide what our application should consist of. As Spring is often used to build web applications with REST [14] APIs, e.g., to provide services to other components like a separate frontend, we decide that our test application should use this functionality. A user of the Spring framework can easily define an endpoint for their API by creating a class annotated with `@RestController` containing methods annotated with `@GetMapping`. Using annotations for meta-programming is common in Spring.

¹⁰See <https://spring.io> for details on the Spring framework and related projects.

¹¹See artifact description in chapter 11

```

@RestController
@RequestMapping("/case-study")
public class CaseStudyController {

    private SecretPOJO secretPOJO = new SecretPOJO();

    @Autowired
    private SecretService secretService;

    @GetMapping("/pojo")
    public ResponseEntity<String> onLeakVariantPojo() {
        String result = secretPOJO.getSecrets();
        System.out.println("Handling data: " + result);
        return ResponseEntity.ok("");
    }

    @GetMapping("/service")
    public ResponseEntity<String> onLeakVariantService() {
        String result = secretService.getSecrets();
        System.out.println("Handling data: " + result);
        return ResponseEntity.ok("");
    }
}

```

Listing 14: Controller class for the case study on a Spring application

```

public class SecretPOJO {
    private final Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();
    public String getSecrets() {
        return json.get("field_oauth_token");
    }
}

@Service
public class SecretService {
    private final Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();
    public String getSecrets() {
        return json.get("field_oauth_token");
    }
}

```

Listing 15: Utility classes with secret data sources for the case study on a Spring application

Listing 14 shows the controller of our test application. We see that the controller defines two endpoints. The logic of both endpoints is similar and consists of calling `getSecrets` on an instance of a utility class and printing the result. We present the utility classes `SecretPOJO` and `SecretService` in listing 15. For both utility classes, the method `getSecrets` accesses a field in a map with a string indicating sensitive data. As we have seen in section 4.2.1, JVM-BidText

4. Case-Studies of the Transferred BidText Approach

will detect this as a source. The utility classes only differ in that one is a *plain old Java object* (POJO) while the other is annotated with `@Service` making it a Spring bean managed by the Spring IoC container. We discuss the details of this concept later.

Let us now discuss the differences between the two endpoints and what we want to test with them. Inside the method `onLeakVariantPojo` (endpoint `/case-study/pojo`) we use no special Spring functionality. The method accesses the `secretPOJO` instance field, which we initialize with the `new` keyword as in any other Java application. The method retrieves sensitive data from the utility class and leaks the result. With this test method, we want to see if all the framework code for the setup of the API endpoint functionality hinders JVM-BidText in the analysis of the method.

The second method `onLeakVariantService` (endpoint `/case-study/service`) uses a service class to access the secret. Without going into detail for now, let us remark that a service is not initialized explicitly with `new`. Instead, the framework injects an instance of the class, as indicated by the `@Autowired` annotation on the field. Again, we will discuss the details of dependency injection later. We want to see if JVM-BidText can still analyze the endpoint method if it depends on injected beans.

At first, when we try to execute JVM-BidText on the compiled Spring application, we notice that JVM-BidText does not find any entry point. The reason is that Spring uses meta-programming with annotations for identifying controller methods instead of relying on overriding library methods to define callbacks like we have seen in the case study on `alpaca-java`. As a temporary workaround, we allow all methods named `on*` as entry points without checking whether they are abstract or override a framework method. Now, JVM-BidText detects the two endpoint methods as expected, and we can rerun JVM-BidText.

The analysis of the Spring application completes in about 1.2 seconds with a memory consumption of 100 MB. The analysis shows a clear result. JVM-BidText detects the data exposure in the method `onLeakVariantPojo` without problems, but does not find the data exposure in the method `onLeakVariantService`. For the POJO-method, the logs of the analysis show that JVM-BidText can follow the data flow to and from the method `getSecrets` in the `SecretPOJO` class. We would expect this behavior in a plain Java application as well. For the service-method, however, JVM-BidText cannot analyze the method `getSecrets` in the `SecretService` class. The reason is that JVM-BidText does not know how the `SecretService` instance is created and how it is injected into the controller.

Without going into further detail for now, we can conclude that JVM-BidText in its current state can analyze Spring applications only to a very limited extent. Framework code for setting up the API endpoints does not hinder the analysis. JVM-BidText seems able to detect data exposures in the application code as long as the data flow does not involve Spring abstractions like dependency injection. However, JVM-BidText cannot analyze methods correctly that rely on dependency injection. This is not surprising, as JVM-BidText does not know about the semantics of Spring's dependency injection. The code handling the dependency injection is not part of the application but rather part of the Spring framework, which is not in the scope of the analysis. Dependency injection is a central concept of the Spring framework. Therefore, we conclude that JVM-BidText cannot analyze generic Spring applications correctly without further modifications. To analyze Spring applications correctly, we need to extend JVM-BidText to understand the semantics of framework concepts. We will look into this topic in the next chapter.

4.6. Conclusions from the Case-Studies

Let us summarize briefly and answer the introductory question for this chapter, before we dive into the extension of JVM-BidText to support analysis of Spring applications. We saw that the transferred BidText approach can handle small JVM applications. We created multiple example applications to test different features of the analysis and explore JVM-BidText's behavior for different language constructs.

Next, we looked at the analysis of a real-world application with roughly 3kLoC. We found that JVM-BidText can detect data exposures in real-world applications, but that it is not without limitations. We summarized the discovered limitations in section 4.3.5.

As a proof of concept, we tested JVM-BidText on a small Kotlin application. We found that JVM-BidText can handle JVM applications written in other languages than Java as well.

Lastly, we increased the difficulty by analyzing an application built on top of a framework. By using a framework, some essential code for the application flow is moved out of the scope of the analysis. We found that JVM-BidText in its current state can analyze applications built on top of frameworks only to a limited extent.

We answer **RQ 2** by concluding that BidText can be transferred to JVM applications well but not without limitations, which partially already exist in the original approach. These limitations come into play, especially when analyzing not plain Java programs with a `main` method, but libraries or even applications built on top of frameworks. The limitations can partially be worked around. Nonetheless, with JVM-BidText we provide a tool that can find non-trivial sensitive data exposures in real-world scenarios without the need for user input apart from some optional configuration for fine-tuning. We can bring the benefits of the BidText approach to JVM applications and make them generally applicable to a broader range of applications. By supporting JVM bytecode, we even go beyond analyzing Java applications and can analyze applications written in other JVM languages like Kotlin.

5. Extension of the Transferred BidText Approach

We examined many capabilities of JVM-BidText in the previous chapter. The case studies in chapter 4 show that we can use JVM-BidText to detect sensitive data exposures in various scenarios. However, when we analyzed an application built with the Spring framework, we found that JVM-BidText can only detect sensitive data exposures in parts of the application that do not use Spring’s dependency injection mechanism. This indicates that the analysis of applications built with frameworks holds additional challenges.

In this chapter, we will explore how we extend JVM-BidText to support the analysis of applications built on top of the Spring framework (**RQ 3**). In the case study of the Spring application in section 4.5, we already got an overview of what frameworks are and why they are challenging to analyze, in general. We tie into this discussion and present the specific challenge of dependency injection that Spring poses to JVM-BidText. To prepare ourselves for addressing the issue, we need to look into some specifics on how initialization and method invocation work in JVM bytecode. With this knowledge, we present our approach to extend JVM-BidText to address the challenge of dependency injection in Spring applications.

5.1. Dependency Injection in Spring Applications

Let us begin by understanding a very fundamental concept of Spring. This will enable us to understand the problem that Spring poses to JVM-BidText. For the explanation of Spring concepts, we rely on the official Spring documentation [50]. We remember that section 4.5 introduced Spring as a framework that uses inversion of control (IoC) to manage parts of the application flow. IoC is a design principle that allows the framework to control the creation and configuration of objects and to manage their dependencies. In Spring, objects managed by the *IoC container* are called *beans*. A bean is not special in itself; it is just an object that is instantiated, assembled, and managed by the Spring IoC container. In Spring terms, all beans together make up the *backbone* of the application.

To form a coherent backbone, beans often have relationships with other beans. They need access to other beans to function properly. These relationships are called *dependencies*. In Spring, the IoC container is responsible for establishing the dependencies of beans during their assembly. We have encountered the term *dependency injection* (DI) in the context of the case study before. DI is a specialized form of IoC where beans define their dependencies in special ways. The key idea of DI is that beans themselves define their dependencies but do not create them. Instead, the IoC container creates the beans and injects the dependencies into them, thereby inverting the regular flow of control.

When working with beans, we will encounter two types of so-called *bean scopes* in Spring: *singleton* and *prototype*. A singleton bean is a bean that is created once per IoC container and shared across the application. A prototype bean, on the other hand, is a bean instantiated anew each time it is requested. A developer can define the scope of a bean by annotating a

class with `@Scope("singleton")` or `@Scope("prototype")`. Spring defaults to singleton scope if no scope is defined. We will need to keep these scopes in mind when we adapt JVM-BidText to support DI.

In practice, the developer often uses annotations to define beans and their dependencies. If classes are annotated with `@Component`, `@Service`, etc., they are considered beans. Inside beans, we can use `@Autowired` to mark fields as requiring dependency injection. We can later use these annotations to detect beans and their dependencies in the bytecode.

But why is dependency injection a challenge for JVM-BidText? Ultimately, even the most abstract framework concept configured with annotations as a form of meta-programming is still compiled to regular JVM bytecode. The answer is that not all resulting bytecode is part of the application code and therefore not in scope of the analysis. Simply adding the framework code to the analysis would not be a suitable solution. Even if the fundamentals of DI seem reasonably simple, the actual implementation in Spring is complex. The addition of the entire framework code would lead to an analysis of the framework itself, not the application. If any output was produced at all, no user would be able to interpret it. Therefore, we need to find a way to analyze the application code on its own, while still considering the framework's influence in the form of DI. We need to teach JVM-BidText to understand the DI annotations and recreate the bean relationships in the analysis.

5.2. Introduction to JVM Bytecode

By now, we have a reasonable understanding of the challenge that dependency injection poses to JVM-BidText. As we concluded in the previous section, we need to find a way to process the DI annotations in bytecode and recreate the semantics of DI in the analysis. The fact, that during the analysis, JVM-BidText only has access to the bytecode of the application, makes this task challenging. We need to extract all necessary information from the bytecode and model the bean relationships based on this information. Our solution not only involves analyzing bytecode, but also bytecode manipulation. To prepare for this task, we need to familiarize ourselves with some bytecode fundamentals. With our task of modeling DI in mind, we are especially interested in the initialization of objects and the invocation of methods.

Let us take a step back and make sure we are on the same page on what JVM bytecode actually is. As mentioned in section 3.1 we use the term *JVM bytecode* instead of *Java bytecode* to refer to the bytecode that is executed by the Java Virtual Machine (JVM). This way we avoid confusion with *Dalvik bytecode* also generated from Java source code, which is mentioned in this thesis as well. We summarize some key points of JVM bytecode and recommend looking directly into the specification of the Java Virtual Machine [52] for details. JVM bytecode is an intermediate representation of code written in Java or other JVM compatible languages. We can consider it an assembly language for the JVM. A compiler translates the source code into a platform-independent bytecode. JVM bytecode is either interpreted by the JVM at runtime or compiled to native code by the Just-In-Time (JIT) compiler. When we talk of JVM bytecode in the strict sense, we refer to the set of instructions that the JVM can execute, not the complete class file format. A bytecode instruction contains an operation code (*opcode*) that specifies the operation to be performed. A single byte can describe an opcode, hence the name *bytecode*. Opcodes can consume operands from the operand stack and may push a result back onto the stack. Opcodes can also access constants from the constant pool, which is a table of constants used by the class.

```
public class ObjectCreationDemo {
    private final Dummy dummyField = new Dummy();
}
```

Listing 16: Java source code for a class that creates an object of another class.

We can group the available instructions into categories based on their purpose. For example, we have instructions for arithmetic operations, control flow, loading and storing values, object creation and manipulation, and method invocation. Many instructions have prefixes that specify the types of the operands, e.g., `iload` for loading an integer from a local variable. The JVM specification defines the exact behavior of each instruction. We will need to understand the instructions for field initialization, object creation, and method invocations to model DI.

5.2.1. Field Initialization and Object Creation in JVM Bytecode

We are specifically interested in the instructions for field initialization, object creation, and method invocation. Let us start with field initialization and object creation. In Java source code, we create objects with the `new` keyword followed by a constructor call. In bytecode, creating an object is not quite as simple as calling `new`, even though such an instruction exists and is involved. Let us examine the bytecode necessary for the creation of an object with a small example.

Listing 16 shows a Java class that creates an object of another class. We compile the class and use the JDK tool `javap` with command line option `-verbose` to disassemble the bytecode. Listing 17 shows the complete output of the disassembly process. The output starts with the class file header. Thereafter, we see the constant pool at lines 12–34, which contains different kinds of references. These references can be strings representing class names (e.g., #8) or method names (e.g., #5). They can also be class references (e.g., #7) built from string references like those we have just mentioned. The compiler can combine references to build other references like method references (e.g., #9). There are more types of references in the constant pool, but these are the most important ones for our task. Remember that we have already used the constant pool in section 3.4.4 to extract string constants for deriving keywords.

After the constant pool, we see the definition of the constructor at lines 36–55. Remember that the compiler generates a default constructor for us if we do not define one in the source code. Most interesting to us is the section labeled *Code* starting at line 41. Lines 41–48 contain the bytecode for the constructor. Each line contains a single opcode optionally followed by a reference into the constant pool. Operands have to be on the stack before the opcode is executed.

Let us dismantle the code of the constructor. The first two instructions at lines 41 and 42 are generic for every constructor from a normal class:

```
0: aload_0
1: invokespecial #1
```

First, we load the reference to the object that is being constructed onto the stack, i.e., the `this` reference. Then we invoke the constructor of the superclass which for a normal class is `java.lang.Object`. Note that in bytecode constructors have the well-known name `<init>`.

The next instructions are specific to our class, apart from the `return` instruction at the

5. Extension of the Transferred BidText Approach

```

1 Classfile <local/path/to/ObjectCreationDemo.class>
2   Last modified Oct 16, 2024; size 371 bytes
3   SHA-256 checksum 36943cc6a56b566728176a740077c693b0d07fcde94d6a8300acf000ce65faac
4   Compiled from "ObjectCreationDemo.java"
5 public class demo.ObjectCreationDemo
6   minor version: 0
7   major version: 65
8   flags: (0x0021) ACC_PUBLIC, ACC_SUPER
9   this_class: #11                // demo/ObjectCreationDemo
10  super_class: #2                 // java/lang/Object
11  interfaces: 0, fields: 1, methods: 1, attributes: 1
12 Constant pool:
13   #1 = Methodref                #2.#3      // java/lang/Object."<init>":()V
14   #2 = Class                    #4         // java/lang/Object
15   #3 = NameAndType              #5:#6    // "<init>":()V
16   #4 = Utf8                      java/lang/Object
17   #5 = Utf8                      <init>
18   #6 = Utf8                      ()V
19   #7 = Class                    #8         // demo/Dummy
20   #8 = Utf8                      demo/Dummy
21   #9 = Methodref              #7.#3    // demo/Dummy."<init>":()V
22  #10 = Fieldref                #11.#12  // demo/ObjectCreationDemo.dummyField:Ldemo/Dummy;
23  #11 = Class                    #13      // demo/ObjectCreationDemo
24  #12 = NameAndType            #14:#15  // dummyField:Ldemo/Dummy;
25  #13 = Utf8                    demo/ObjectCreationDemo
26  #14 = Utf8                    dummyField
27  #15 = Utf8                    Ldemo/Dummy;
28  #16 = Utf8                    Code
29  #17 = Utf8                    LineNumberTable
30  #18 = Utf8                    LocalVariableTable
31  #19 = Utf8                    this
32  #20 = Utf8                    Ldemo/ObjectCreationDemo;
33  #21 = Utf8                    SourceFile
34  #22 = Utf8                    ObjectCreationDemo.java
35 {
36 public demo.ObjectCreationDemo();
37   descriptor: ()V
38   flags: (0x0001) ACC_PUBLIC
39   Code:
40     stack=3, locals=1, args_size=1
41     0: aload_0
42     1: invokespecial #1                // Method java/lang/Object."<init>":()V
43     4: aload_0
44     5: new          #7                 // class demo/Dummy
45     8: dup
46     9: invokespecial #9              // Method demo/Dummy."<init>":()V
47    12: putfield    #10                // Field dummyField:Ldemo/Dummy;
48    15: return
49   LineNumberTable:
50     line 3: 0
51     line 4: 4
52   LocalVariableTable:
53     Start Length Slot Name Signature
54     0      16     0  this  Ldemo/ObjectCreationDemo;
55 }
56 SourceFile: "ObjectCreationDemo.java"

```

Listing 17: Bytecode for the class in listing 16.

end that signals the end of the constructor. Let us look at which part of the source code the instructions from lines 43–47 correspond to. In the source code in listing 16, we declare the field `dummyField` of type `Dummy`. We initialize the field with a new instance of `Dummy` in the same line. The compiler transforms this shorthand by moving the initialization to the implicitly generated default constructor. The resulting sequence of bytecode instructions (lines 43–47 in listing 17) is the following:

```

4: aload_0
5: new          #7
8: dup
9: invokespecial #9
12: putfield    #10

```

With `aload_0` we start by loading the `this` reference onto the stack. In the next line, we use the `new` instruction to create a new object on the heap. The created object has the type referenced by constant pool item 7, i.e., `Dummy`. The `new` instruction pushes a reference to the new object onto the stack. At this point, the instance initialization is not yet complete as `new` only initializes the object instance fields to their default values. We need to call the constructor of the object to complete the initialization. But before we continue with that, we need to duplicate the reference to the new object on the stack with the `dup` instruction. This is necessary because the two following instructions will both consume the reference. To complete the initialization, we call the constructor of the object with the `invokespecial` instruction. The constant pool item 9 appearing after the `invokespecial` instruction references the constructor `demo/Dummy.<init>:()V`. The constructor does not take any arguments, as indicated by `()` in the reference. Finally, with `putfield`, we store the reference to the completely initialized object in a field. If we look up reference 10 in the constant pool, we find that it is the reference to the field `dummyField`. This completes the object creation process. What we have written as one line of Java code is translated into five bytecode instructions.

As field initialization and object creation are relevant for the DI process, we will revisit this sequence of instructions when we discuss how to model DI in the analysis.

5.2.2. Method Invocation in JVM Bytecode

The second aspect of JVM bytecode that we need to understand for building a solution for DI is method invocation. We introduced method invocation as a group of bytecode instructions in section 5.2 which suggests that there are multiple ways to invoke methods. In fact, there are five different instructions for method invocation in JVM bytecode.

In the previous section, we have already seen one of them: `invokespecial`. In general, the JVM uses this instruction to invoke instance methods but ignore dynamic binding. This results in the usage of this instruction for invocations of private methods, methods from superclasses and instance initializing methods, i.e., constructors. In essence, constructors are just methods with the special predefined name `<init>`.

If dynamic binding is desired for calling “normal” instance methods, the JVM uses the `invokevirtual` instruction. More specifically, the JVM uses this instruction to call instance methods based on the class of the object.

Then there are `invokestatic` and `invokeinterface`. As the names suggest, the JVM uses `invokestatic` to call static methods and `invokeinterface` to call methods of interfaces.

The last instruction is `invokedynamic` which was introduced in Java 7. The JVM uses this instruction to call methods that are not known at compile time. Programming languages

making use of dynamic typing, like JRuby¹, use this instruction extensively. Java itself uses `invokedynamic` as well, e.g., for the implementation of lambda expressions or records. As we will not need `invokedynamic` for our task of modeling DI, we do not go into further detail here. Let us just mention that the limitation of JVM-BidText we discovered in the case study on `alpaca-java` in section 4.3.2, where we had problems analyzing abstract methods, involves the `invokedynamic` instruction.

We have now covered the features of JVM bytecode most important to understand our approach to modeling DI in the analysis. In the next section, we will present this approach which enables the support for Spring applications.

5.3. Extension of JVM-BidText to Address Dependency Injection

We remember that the case study on the Spring application in section 4.5 showed that JVM-BidText cannot detect sensitive data exposures in parts of the application that use Spring's dependency injection. To understand why this is the case, we discussed the challenges of analyzing frameworks in general. We explained why dependency injection in particular is a challenge for JVM-BidText. We concluded that we need to find a way to model the relationships between beans in such a way that JVM-BidText can produce results without analyzing the framework code itself.

In this section, we present our approach to extend JVM-BidText to address the challenge of dependency injection in Spring applications. We will first discuss our strategy for addressing dependency injection. Then we explain the three parts that make up our approach, starting with the discovery of beans and injections. Afterward, we model the inversion of control container and integrate it with the beans by performing bytecode manipulation at the injection sites.

5.3.1. Strategy for Addressing Dependency Injection

How do we address the challenge of dependency injection in Spring applications? We identify two possible strategies to handle DI. The first option would be to modify the existing analysis in a way that all accesses to fields requiring injection is intercepted. As we do not include framework code in the analysis, the baseline is that there is no connection in *application code* between fields and the objects that need to be injected. If we detect a method invocation on a field marked with annotations indicating injection, we would need to build a link to the correct method of the field's class manually. But our analysis might never discover these methods we need to link because WALA would not have included them in the SDG. WALA cannot include methods in the SDG that are not reachable from the entry points. And with that, we are back at our baseline. To break out of the loop, we would need to find a way to access the code of methods by type and name even if they are not reachable from the entry points. This strategy would require countless changes at different places and would likely not be very robust.

Therefore, we choose the second strategy that we outline in this paragraph. We will model the links between beans and their dependencies, more specifically, between fields marked for injection and the beans that are injected. Importantly, we will model this relationship before the actual analysis for sensitive data exposures starts. In essence, we modify the input of the analysis to include the necessary information to reach all relevant code —without stepping into framework code. This way, we can keep the concerns separated and do not interfere with the analysis process that we have already tested.

¹See <https://www.jruby.org>

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To get an idea of what we need to do, let us compare how a developer uses dependency injection in Spring with how the same code would look without dependency injection. From there we can derive what we need to model in the analysis.

In fact, we have designed the case study on the Spring application in section 4.5 with this comparison in mind. Let us therefore revisit the example from the case study. In listing 15 we define a class `SecretPOJO` that does not use any Spring functionality. We implement exactly the same logic in the class `SecretService` but this time add the annotation `@Service` to mark the class as a bean and make it available for dependency injection. The class `CaseStudyController` of listing 14 declares a field of type `SecretPOJO` and a field of type `SecretService`. We initialize the field of type `SecretPOJO` with the `new` keyword like we would in a regular Java application. We do not initialize the field of type `SecretService` but instead rely on dependency injection from Spring.

Let us collect the differences between the two cases:

- For the type `SecretPOJO`, we call the constructor explicitly. For the type `SecretService`, we do not call the constructor and do not know where the object is created.
- We initialize the field `secretPOJO` by assigning the reference to the object we explicitly created. We do not initialize the field `secretService` but instead mark it with `@Autowired`.
- We do not annotate the class definition of `SecretPOJO`. But we do annotate the class definition of `SecretService` with `@Service`.

These differences give us the necessary clues what we need to model and how we can integrate our model into the existing code.

Let us discuss the findings from above. The instantiation of `SecretService` is completely hidden from the application code. We therefore need to find a way to model the instantiation of beans in the analysis. In preparation for this step, we need to find the annotations that mark classes as beans, to identify which classes actually need custom instantiation.

The second part abstracted away from the application code is the assignment of the correct object reference to the field `secretService`. Therefore, we need to find a way to initialize the fields of the beans in the analysis. Once again, we need to prepare by finding the annotations that mark fields for dependency injection.

The approach we take consists of three parts that generalize the steps we just outlined. We first scan all classes to find annotations indicating beans and fields that require injections. Then we model the IoC container such that it can create beans and provide them if requested. Finally, we modify the bytecode of all classes that require injection. Instead of relying on injection, we initialize the fields explicitly by requesting the beans from the modeled IoC container.

We perform all three parts of the approach during the initial setup of JVM-BidText, and before the actual analysis for sensitive data exposures starts. This way we can encapsulate the modeling of DI and keep it separate from the analysis process. The analysis does not need to know anything about DI, as long as we prepare the graphs the analysis operates on correctly, such that the analysis can reach all relevant code.

Recent work of Chen, Tu, Zhang, Wen, and Wang inspires our approach to modeling DI. They present a tool called Jasmine [43] that aims to bring support for Spring core technologies to static analysis tools based on the Soot [13] and Doop [21] frameworks. As Jasmine does not

support WALA, the framework we use for JVM-BidText, we need to adapt their approach for our use case. For some essential parts, we can follow their approach, e.g., for the identification of beans and injections. But as we use a different framework, we need to find our own solutions for other parts. As an example, we realize the integration of the IoC container with the beans by modifying the actual bytecode of the classes that require injection. Jasmine, on the other hand, performs all of its operations on the IR level of Soot. In the following sections, we will look into the implementation of the three steps we have identified for the approach.

5.3.2. Discovery of beans and Injections

Now, we have a strategy on how to address DI. Before we can model anything though, we need to find the classes that are involved in DI. The process we describe to achieve this is similar to the one Chen, Tu, Zhang, Wen, and Wang use in their tool Jasmine [43].

Remember that JVM-BidText only receives bytecode as input. Therefore, we need to retrieve all relevant information from bytecode only. For working with bytecode, we use the WALA framework once again. We use WALA to scan all classes from the class hierarchy we have discussed in section 3.4.1. WALA collects annotations while parsing the bytecode and stores them in the IR. We can therefore easily access the annotations of a class by querying the IR. We iterate over all application classes and look for any of the class-level annotations `@Component`, `@Service`, `@Repository`, `@Controller`, `@RestController`, or `@Configuration`. All these annotations are used in Spring to mark classes as managed by the IoC container. The scan is based on fully qualified class names of the annotations to avoid misidentification with other annotations of the same name.

During this scan for bean annotations, we also look for classes that are additionally annotated with `@Scope`. We remember from section 5.1 that this annotation is used to determine whether the bean should be managed as a singleton or a prototype. If no `@Scope` annotation is present, we assume the bean is a singleton as this is the default behavior in Spring.

Subsequently, we need to iterate over all fields of the classes we have identified as beans. We look for fields that are annotated with `@Autowired` or `@Resource`. These annotations mark fields that require dependency injection.

We store the information about beans and injection sites and proceed to the next step of the approach.

5.3.3. Model of the Inversion of Control Container

In section 5.3.1 we have identified that we need to model the IoC container. Spring's original IoC container is complex and supports various kinds of configuration for beans, e.g., through XML files or Java configuration classes. The beans that the IoC container creates can differ between application profiles and depending on other forms of context. This functionality is useful in practice but seems not strictly necessary for a basic analysis of the respective classes for sensitive data exposures. To bring basic support for DI to JVM-BidText, we will implement a model of the IoC container that carries out the most important task: creating and providing beans. The only configuration we support is the distinction between singleton and prototype beans. Thereby, we allow the sensitive data analysis to find exposure paths that involve the constructors of prototype beans.

Let us now discuss how the IoC container model should look like in code. Our goal is to construct a class that provides static methods to retrieve beans. For prototype beans, we need

```

public class IoCContainerModel {
    private static final SecretService SECRET_SERVICE = new SecretService();

    public static SecretPrototypeService getSecretPrototypeService() {
        return new SecretPrototypeService();
    }

    public static SecretService getSecretService() {
        return SECRET_SERVICE;
    }
}

```

Listing 18: Example implementation of the IoC container model

to create a new instance each time a bean is requested. This means that we can simply call the constructor of the bean class every time we request the bean. For singleton beans, we need to create the bean only once and then return the same instance every time the bean is requested. We can achieve this by storing the instance in a static final field (constant) of the IoC container class². We call the constructors of singleton beans once during the bootstrapping of the IoC container class and save the created instances in the constant. When a bean requests a singleton bean as its dependency, we return the instance from the constant.

To visualize the structure of the IoC container model, we present an example version of the class in listing 18. The model contains two static getter methods and a constant. The method `getSecretPrototypeService()` returns a new instance of `SecretPrototypeService` every time it is called. The class `SecretPrototypeService` is a prototype bean and is implemented just like the already familiar `SecretService` from listing 15. In contrast to `SecretService`, however, we annotate the class `SecretPrototypeService` with `@Scope("prototype")` to mark it as a prototype bean.

The second method, `getSecretService()`, returns the singleton bean of type `SecretService`. To implement the singleton pattern, the model holds a constant for the type `SecretService`. We initialize the constant with a new object of the respective type. The declaration and initialization in one line is syntactic sugar. In preparation for the modeling of the IoC container, let us look at the deliberate separation of declaration and initialization for this example. We can initialize static fields with a *static block*. The static block is the pendant to the familiar constructor for initializing instance fields. The JVM executes the static block once when it loads the class. Using a static block, we can rewrite line 2 of listing 18 like we show in listing 19.

The problem that arises with this implementation of the IoC container model in source code is that we need to know the types of all beans beforehand. As a consequence, we need to generate the IoC container model dynamically. We execute the annotation scan from section 5.3.2 first and then generate the IoC container model based on the results. As WALA supports the addition of custom classes to the class hierarchy, we realize the generation of the IoC container model on the level of WALA IR. Thereby, we avoid generating and compiling source files which would involve external tools.

²We do not worry about concurrency issues when storing beans in constants. According to Fernoaga and Nagendra, Spring's original IoC container does not implement any support for concurrency either [44]. Developers using singleton-scoped beans need to consider concurrency like in any other Java application.

```

private static final SecretService SECRET_SERVICE;

static {
    SECRET_SERVICE = new SecretService();
}

```

Listing 19: Initialization of the constant `SECRET_SERVICE` with a static block. This is equivalent to line 2 of listing 18.

WALA provides interfaces to represent fields, methods, and classes on IR level. For all custom elements we add to the IR, we need to implement these interfaces. We follow an object-oriented approach to create all necessary elements for the IoC container model. We build the elements in the same way as we have seen with the source code example of the IoC Container Model in listing 18. The challenge is that we need to create the elements dynamically based on the results of the annotation scan. During this process, we need to be careful with all names and identifiers, as consistent selectors and references are essential for WALA to link all components correctly. In the following paragraphs, we discuss how we model the static block that initializes the singleton beans and the getter methods for both types of beans. We do not go into detail with the creation of the static fields for holding the singleton bean instances.

We prepare a class to model the IoC container by implementing the respective WALA interface for classes or, more specifically, by extending the abstract base implementation for synthetic classes. After we create static fields for all singleton beans and add the respective objects to the model class, we need to add code to initialize the fields. As we have discussed when we presented the source code model of the IoC container, we can do this by adding a static block to the class. We can add a static block to a class by creating a special class initializer function. We remember from the introduction to bytecode in section 5.2 that the JVM uses the well-known name `<init>` for constructors. The pendant for class initializers is the name `<clinit>` —an abbreviation for *class initializer*. We create a method with this name and add it to the class.

To construct the body of the class initializer method, we need to add instructions. We operate on the IR level, so we need to use IR instructions instead of bytecode instructions. In general, IR instructions have a corresponding bytecode instruction. For simplicity, we will use the names of the bytecode instructions in the following discussion, as we have already introduced them in section 5.2. Some utility bytecode instructions like `dup` are not available on the IR level. WALA manages their functionality internally. To construct the body of the class initializer, we can follow the object creation process we have discussed for JVM bytecode in section 5.2.1. We follow a similar chain of instructions as in the example from section 5.2.1 but we need to make two differences. We do not need to load the `this` reference because we operate in the static context. For the same reason, we use the instruction `putstatic` instead of `putfield` to store the created bean instance in the respective static field. WALA supports the creation of instructions by providing utility methods. When we add the `new` instruction, for example, WALA automatically inserts the required invocation of the default constructor. We add this instruction sequence to the `<clinit>` method for all singleton beans.

To retrieve singleton beans from the IoC container model, we need to add simple getter methods. Their method bodies consist of two instructions. First, we use a `getstatic` instruction

to retrieve the instance from the static field. Then, we return the reference to the instance with an `areturn` instruction; the prefix `a` indicates that the instruction returns a reference to an object and not a primitive value.

For prototype beans, we do not need to store the instances in static fields. Instead, we create a new instance every time we call the getter. We follow the same process as for the `<clinit>` method to create the instances but refrain from storing them in static fields. Instead, we return the reference to the newly created instance directly from the getter method.

If we execute these steps for all beans we have identified in the annotation scan, we have successfully modeled a basic IoC container. As mentioned, it does not support all features of the original Spring IoC container. But it is sufficient for our purpose of supporting basic linking of beans and their dependencies.

5.3.4. Beans in Relationships

We have now modeled the IoC container and can create beans. The model provides access to the beans via getter methods. What is left to do is to establish the dependencies between beans. We need to initialize the fields of beans that require injection. Our strategy is simple: We call the getter methods of the IoC container model to retrieve the required beans and assign the references to the fields.

The implementation of this task is a lot less straightforward than one might expect. The problem is that WALA does not provide the means to modify the IR of already loaded classes in the class hierarchy. We cannot simply add instructions to the IR of the classes that require injection. To work around this limitation, we need to modify the bytecode of the classes directly and thereby operate on one level lower than for modeling the IoC container with IR. While WALA does not support the editing of existing IR, WALA provides separate tools for the modification of bytecode. WALA Shrike is a library that allows for the instrumentation and manipulation of bytecode. With Shrike, we can parse an existing class file, apply patches to the bytecode, and write the modified class file back to disk. We can then load the modified class file into the class hierarchy, such that JVM-BidText uses the modified bytecode for the analysis.

As the class hierarchy does not support unloading classes, we need to make sure that the original version of the class is not loaded into the final class hierarchy. In practice, we need to perform the required steps in the following unintuitive order: We first create a class hierarchy with all original classes to run the annotation scan described in section 5.3.2. After the scan, we modify the injections via bytecode instrumentation and write the modified files to disk. We then create a new class hierarchy with the modified classes. Only at this point do we model the IoC container and add it to the final class hierarchy. The final class hierarchy is then used for the actual analysis. We see no reasonable way to avoid creating the class hierarchy twice.

With the overview of the process in mind, let us now discuss how we modify the bytecode of the classes that require injection. First, we discuss the process in general; afterward we look at an example. To start the process, we use Shrike to traverse all classes of the input. For each class, we query the results of the annotation scan to see whether the class contains fields that require injection. If the check is positive, we look for the `<init>` method of the class, i.e., the constructor. We then create a patch for the constructor that initializes the fields requiring injection. To build the patch, we specify the required bytecode instructions to invoke a getter method of the IoC container model and assign the reference to a field.

The patch consists of only three instructions. First, we load the `this` reference onto the stack

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with `aload_0`. For work with Shrike, we need to manage the stack manually. When operating on the bytecode level, WALA cannot provide the same convenience as for IR. No helper method creates augmenting stack management instructions if the main instructions like invocations require them. One might think that the correct stack management is not essential because we do not intend to execute the modified code. Execution would not be possible anyway, as after all, the IoC container model is never available as bytecode but only exists in the IR. But if we were to omit the `aload_0` instruction, Shrike would throw a *Stack underflow* exception when writing the modified class file.

After `aload_0` we invoke the static getter method of the IoC container model. We remember from section 5.2.2 that we call static methods with the `invokestatic` instruction. We further remember from earlier in this section that, in practice, we create the IoC model and getter methods after we create this patch. Therefore, we cannot access the names of an actual getter object. Instead, we need to make sure that both sides use a uniform naming pattern. Otherwise, the analysis will not be able to find the linking we are trying to establish.

As the final instruction of the patch, we use `putfield` to store the reference to the bean returned by the getter. We know the name of the target field from the annotation scan. Between the getter invocation and the field assignment, we do not need any stack modifications. `putfield` consumes the reference pushed to the stack by `invokestatic` in the step before.

Once we have added all instructions to the patch, we apply the patch to the constructor. We repeat the process for all fields of the class that require injection. Once we have iterated over all classes, we complete the processing of injections by writing the classes to disk.

To see the results of this process, let us once again look at the example from the case study on the Spring application in section 4.5. We use `javap -verbose` to decompile the class file of the `CaseStudyController` before and after we have processed it with the approach described above. We try to find the sections of bytecode that we modified. As a baseline, we inspect the unmodified class. We present an excerpt of the output from `javap` executed with the unmodified class in listing 20. The excerpt shows the bytecode of the constructor of the `CaseStudyController` class. We see the instructions we have discussed in section 5.2.1 to create an object of the type `SecretPOJO` for the field `secretPOJO` at lines 8–12. The constructor does not contain any instructions for initializing the field `secretService`.

After we have applied the patch to the constructor, we decompile the modified class file. We present an excerpt of the output from `javap` in listing 21. We see that the instructions for creating an object of type `SecretPOJO` are still present at lines 8–12. Next, follow the instructions we patched for the initialization of the field `secretService` at lines 13–17. `javap` annotates the symbolic references stored in the constant pool with class and field names. We see that the instruction at line 14 calls the getter method of the IoC container model to retrieve the bean of type `SecretService`. The reference to the bean is then stored in the field `secretService` with the instruction at line 16. We note that WALA Shrike fully qualifies the name of the field in line 16 while the instruction in line 12 does not contain the class name of the field. This difference does not seem to have any impact on the analysis of the bytecode, however. We therefore conclude that WALA Shrike has successfully added the instructions for injection to the bytecode.

```

1      public demo.leaky_springs.CaseStudyController();
2      descriptor: ()V
3      flags: (0x0001) ACC_PUBLIC
4      Code:
5      stack=3, locals=1, args_size=1
6      0: aload_0
7      1: invokespecial #1 // Method java/lang/Object."<init>":()V
8      4: aload_0
9      5: new          #7 // class demo/leaky_springs/SecretPOJO
10     8: dup
11     9: invokespecial #9 // Method demo/leaky_springs/SecretPOJO."<init>":()V
12    12: putfield     #10 // Field secretPOJO:Ldemo/leaky_springs/SecretPOJO;
13    15: return

```

Listing 20: Bytecode of the constructor of the `CaseStudyController` class **before** modification

```

1      public demo.leaky_springs.CaseStudyController();
2      descriptor: ()V
3      flags: (0x0001) ACC_PUBLIC
4      Code:
5      stack=3, locals=1, args_size=1
6      0: aload_0
7      1: invokespecial #1 // Method java/lang/Object."<init>":()V
8      4: aload_0
9      5: new          #89 // class demo/leaky_springs/SecretPOJO
10     8: dup
11     9: invokespecial #9 // Method demo/leaky_springs/SecretPOJO."<init>":()V
12    12: putfield     #10 // Field secretPOJO:Ldemo/leaky_springs/SecretPOJO;
13    15: aload_0
14    16: invokestatic #90 // Method bidtext/extension/SpringIOCMoel.getSecretService:
15          ()Ldemo/leaky_springs/SecretService;
16    19: putfield     #91 // Field demo/leaky_springs/CaseStudyController.secretService:
17          Ldemo/leaky_springs/SecretService;
18    22: return

```

Listing 21: Bytecode of the constructor of the `CaseStudyController` class **after** modification

5.3.5. Discussion of the Approach

We have just seen the involved process necessary to model DI. The process is complex and involves multiple steps. We need to scan all classes for annotations, model the IoC container in IR, and modify the bytecode of classes that require injection. To make all aspects of the process work together, we need to carefully orchestrate the steps. In particular, we need to create the class hierarchy twice, which implies that we need to parse all classes twice. This is an overhead we cannot easily avoid. Running the analysis on a small demo Spring application that consists of the classes from the case study on the Spring application in section 4.5 and some additional test cases takes about 3.6 seconds. Memory consumption is about 160 MB. In comparison, the same analysis without the DI extension takes about 3.1 seconds and consumes about 120 MB of memory.

Let us consider whether we could have simplified the process. The question might arise, why

we do not initialize fields by calling the constructors directly. Why go through the hassle of modeling the IoC Container if we are going to modify the bytecode at injection sites anyway? The answer is that initializing new instances of beans by calling the constructor directly would have an unwanted effect on the analysis for sensitive data exposures. We remember that most beans are singletons and therefore only one instance is created for the entire application. We further remember that our analysis associates sets of types with variables and establishes constraints between them. If the original unmodified application uses a singleton bean, sensitive data can flow through the only instance of the bean to all places that access it. To ensure that the analysis can find all paths of sensitive data flow, we need to enable our analysis to establish the same link. All places that access the bean instance need to contribute to the same type set. If we were to create new instances of beans at injection sites, the analysis would not be able to establish the link between the instances. The analysis would treat the instances as separate objects and not find the paths of sensitive data flow. Therefore, we need an entity to manage singleton instances and ensure that the same singleton instance is returned every time a bean is requested. This is the role of the IoC container model.

The only exceptions to this requirement are prototype beans. As we create new instances of prototype beans every time they are requested through a getter, we could also create new instances at injection sites. But we decide to keep the process uniform and somewhat close to Spring's behavior. We create all instances of beans through the IoC container model, no matter whether they are singletons or prototypes.

We also need to consider the other direction. Did we make too many simplifications? We have already mentioned that our IoC container model is a simplified version of the original Spring IoC container. Further, there are some Spring concepts that we do not support at all. For example, we do not support aspect-oriented programming (AOP) in our approach. A complete reimplementaion of the Spring IoC container and other features would defeat the purpose of our approach. If we were to implement the full functionality of the Spring framework, we could just as well add the framework code to the analysis. Therefore, we need to find a balance between the complexity of the implementation and support for various Spring features. Chen, Tu, Zhang, Wen, and Wang have identified that DI support in an analysis tool has a high impact on the results for many of their test applications and at least some impact for all of them [43]. AOP can add value to the analysis for some applications but is not relevant for others. The modeling of other dynamic features of Spring has varying importance for different applications. We believe that our approach of supporting the central concept of DI sets a good baseline for the analysis of Spring applications with JVM-BidText.

5.4. Detection of Entry Points into Spring Applications

Before we are ready to test the effectiveness of the enhancements we made to JVM-BidText for supporting dependency injection, we want to address another issue. We remember from the case study on the Spring application in section 4.5 that JVM-BidText struggles to detect entry points into Spring applications. As a temporary solution, we have disabled the checks for identifying call back methods and accepted all non-private methods with a specific prefix as entry points. From our personal experience with the development of Spring applications, we know that this naming convention is often not followed, and definitely not enforced by the framework. Developers might use different naming conventions or might not use any naming

convention at all. Therefore, we need to find a more reliable way to detect entry points into Spring applications.

We remember the structure of a typical Spring Boot application like we have seen in listing 14 for the case study. Such an application consists of controller classes that handle incoming requests. The controller defines methods that are mapped to specific endpoints. We remember from our discussion in the case study that we can consider the methods of the controller classes as entry points into the application. For our strategy to detect entry points reliably, we will therefore implement an algorithm that identifies the respective methods of the controller classes without relying on naming conventions.

As part of the enhancements for supporting dependency injection, we have already implemented a scan for annotations that indicate beans and fields for dependency injection (section 5.3.2). We can reuse and extend parts of this scan to identify the entry points in the controller classes. We remember that the annotations `@Controller` and `@RestController` mark classes as controllers. The scan already collects the classes that are annotated with these annotations because controllers are beans that we need to consider for dependency injection. Therefore, the identification of the controller classes is already part of the scan.

To identify the methods of the controller classes that are entry points into the application, we utilize certain annotations that mark methods as request handlers. Specifically, we look for the annotations `@GetMapping`, `@PostMapping`, `@PutMapping`, `@DeleteMapping`, and `@PatchMapping`. These annotations instruct the framework to map methods to specific HTTP request methods. Once the framework receives a request, it routes the request to the method that is annotated with the respective mapping annotation. Once we have identified the methods that are annotated with these annotations, we can integrate them into our set of application entry points.

We execute this scan in addition to the other strategies for discovering entry points. Spring Boot applications always have a traditional `main` method as well. Depending on the use of third-party libraries, a scan for call back methods might identify additional entry points. We can, however, enable the `overrides superclass` check for call back methods again, as we have now found a more reliable way to identify the controller methods.

With the implementation of the scan for entry points and the modeling of dependency injection, we have addressed both issues we identified in the case study on the Spring application. We are now ready to revisit the case study and see the impact of our enhancements.

5.5. Case Study on Spring Application — Revisited

In this section, we revisit the case study on the Spring application from section 4.5. We want to evaluate the effectiveness of the enhancements we made to JVM-BidText, specifically for supporting dependency injection (DI) but also for detecting entry points into Spring applications. We previously identified that JVM-BidText without an adaptation for Spring struggles to detect sensitive data exposures in parts of the application utilizing Spring's DI. By extending JVM-BidText to model the relationships between beans and their dependencies, we aim to improve its analysis capabilities.

We remember that the case study consists of a simple Spring application that contains a controller class (listing 14), a service class, and a POJO class (both in listing 15). The controller class declares two fields, one of type `SecretPOJO` and one of type `SecretService`. We initialize the field of type `SecretPOJO` with the `new` keyword. We do not initialize the field of type

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`SecretService` but instead rely on dependency injection from Spring. The controller class contains two methods with the same logic. They both handle sensitive data and leak it to the console. To retrieve the sensitive data, one method relies on the field of type `SecretPOJO` and the other on the field of type `SecretService`. We have identified that JVM-BidText without support for DI cannot detect the sensitive data exposure in the method that relies on the field of type `SecretService`. As we do not initialize the field in the application code, JVM-BidText cannot establish the link between the field and the bean that is injected. The analysis therefore does not find the path of sensitive data flow.

We have now extended JVM-BidText to support DI. In section 5.3.1 we have outlined our approach to modeling DI specifically for the controller class of the Spring application from the case study. We have modeled the IoC container and added the necessary instructions to the bytecode of the controller class to initialize the field of type `SecretService`. We presented the bytecode of the constructor of the controller class *before* and *after* the modification in listing 20 and listing 21 respectively.

Now, all that is left to do is to run JVM-BidText with the extension for DI on the Spring application. We disable the temporary solution for detecting entry points via naming conventions and rely on the new annotation-based scan for the detection of the two endpoint methods in the controller class. We can confirm that JVM-BidText detects both methods of the `CaseStudyController` as entry points into the application. Between multiple runs, memory consumption is either slightly above 70 MB or close to 145 MB. The analysis runs for about 1.6 seconds in all cases. We hypothesize that the difference in memory consumption is due to the garbage collection process. We remember that the analysis loads the class hierarchy twice to enable the modification of bytecode. It might come down to whether the garbage collector frees the memory of the intermediate class hierarchy before the end of the analysis.

We add a call to `System.gc()` after JVM-BidText has completed the necessary processing of the intermediate class hierarchy, but before JVM-BidText creates the second class hierarchy. Although `System.gc()` is only a hint to the garbage collector, we observe that memory consumption is consistently between 45 MB and 55 MB in all runs using the change. This is even lower than the lowest memory consumption we have observed before. This might be a shortcoming of the memory measurement process. We use the measurement functionality originally implemented in BidText. The measurement uses the amount of free memory right after the analysis to estimate the memory usage. The garbage collector might heavily influence this measurement. As the large fluctuations by 100% are resolved, we conclude that the garbage collector is likely responsible for the differing memory consumptions in the previous runs. Our call to `System.gc()` seems to have no significant effect on the runtime of the analysis.

Let us now look at the results of the analysis. When we run JVM-BidText with the extension for DI on the Spring application, we find that the analysis reports two sensitive data exposures for the controller class. Upon inspection of the reports, we see that the analysis has found the paths of sensitive data flow in both methods of the controller class. The analysis has successfully established the link between the field of type `SecretService` and the bean that is injected. We have therefore successfully addressed the issue we identified in the original case study.

For completeness, we also run the new version of JVM-BidText without the DI modeling step. In the design of the extension for Spring, we made sure that the extension can be disabled. If disable the extension via the configuration file, the analysis will completely skip the Spring preprocessing step and run as it would without the extension. As expected, the analysis without DI processing only finds one sensitive data exposure in the controller class —just as in the

5. *Extension of the Transferred BidText Approach*

original case study. The analysis does not find the path of sensitive data flow that involves the field of type `SecretService`.

The analysis with the disabled DI step completes in about 1.2 seconds and consumes about 95 MB of memory. This matches the results we have observed in the original case study. We observe that the Spring processing step adds about 0.4 seconds to the runtime of the analysis. If we enable the garbage collection hint, the reported memory consumption is lower for the analysis with the DI extension enabled. This result seems unintuitive to us, as the DI extension adds additional classes to the analysis. Further investigation into the effects of the garbage collection process and possibly an external memory measurement tool might be necessary to understand the memory consumption of the analysis better.

6. Comparison of JVM-BidText and CodeQL

We already conducted some comprehensive case studies with JVM-BidText in chapter 4 and section 5.5. In this chapter, we want to hook into this evaluation and answer the question of how JVM-BidText compares to GitHub CodeQL (RQ 4). GitHub CodeQL¹ [34] is a powerful semantic code analysis engine used to find security vulnerabilities and other issues in codebases. Its capabilities include the detection of sensitive data exposures through log files. We introduce and compare the two tools in terms of their capabilities. We then move on to the evaluation of both tools on some concrete examples. First, we compare CodeQL to JVM-BidText based on the programs we already know from the case studies. As these programs are designed to demonstrate certain aspects of JVM-BidText, we develop further test cases to compare the strengths and weaknesses of both tools. We evaluate the support for dynamic invocations, bidirectional analysis, and different variants of sensitivity detection. Finally, we discuss the results and draw conclusions on the comparison of JVM-BidText and CodeQL.

6.1. Comparison of Capabilities

Let us start with an introduction to the capabilities of GitHub CodeQL and JVM-BidText. Both tools analyze code, but they focus on different aspects and use different methodologies.

GitHub CodeQL primarily performs semantic code analysis to find security vulnerabilities and other issues in codebases. The analysis of sensitive data exposures through logs is only one of the many capabilities of CodeQL. CodeQL supports multiple programming languages, including Java in the current version 23, JavaScript, Python, and more, making it a versatile tool for analyzing codebases written in different languages. CodeQL integrates seamlessly with GitHub workflows, making it ideal for continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipelines. CodeQL is available as a standalone tool, as well. In preparation for its analysis, CodeQL creates a database with a full hierarchical representation of the codebase. The database also contains information on the control and data flow. The database allows querying using an SQL-like language to detect specific code patterns. Developers can choose to write custom queries to locate specific issues in their codebase. But CodeQL also provides predefined queries for common security vulnerabilities and code quality issues, including a rule to find data exposures through log files. If developers choose to rely on the predefined queries, CodeQL integrated into the GitHub platform requires minimal setup. In general, the CodeQL analysis efficiently scales to handle large projects, but its performance depends on the complexity of the queries and the size of the codebase.

JVM-BidText, on the other hand, is a specialized tool for detecting sensitive data exposures in JVM applications. We focus on data exposures through log files in this work, but JVM-BidText can analyze other types of sinks as well. JVM-BidText uses static analysis techniques to detect sensitive data exposures by propagating type information through a custom typing graph derived from the system dependence graph. JVM-BidText propagates type information both

¹See <https://codeql.github.com/>

forward and backward. JVM-BidText can thereby detect sensitive data exposures unidentifiable by other tools using forward-only analysis. Huang, Zhang, and Tan introduce this approach for the original BidText [35], and call the approach *bidirectional text correlation analysis*. JVM-BidText uses basic natural language processing and predefined keywords to automatically detect sensitive data sources without user input. JVM-BidText targets JVM applications, i.e., applications written in languages that compile to JVM bytecode. Through its use of the WALA analysis engine, JVM-BidText supports Java 23. JVM-BidText provides an extension to support the analysis of libraries and applications using the popular Spring framework. To aid the analysis of libraries and Spring applications, JVM-BidText implements different strategies for the detection of entry points. Further, JVM-BidText models the semantics of dependency injection in Spring applications. Thereby, JVM-BidText’s data flow analysis can find connections between framework-managed classes. By supporting libraries and frameworks, JVM-BidText sets itself apart from CodeQL, which does not provide specialized support for libraries or frameworks. Tests on various Java applications prove that JVM-BidText can detect sensitive data exposures in diverse scenarios. JVM-BidText can handle real-world applications and scales well from small demos to codebases in the order of a few thousand lines of code.

In summary, GitHub CodeQL serves as a versatile tool for code analysis and security vulnerability detection across multiple languages. Detecting sensitive data exposures is only one of the many capabilities of CodeQL. CodeQL provides no specialized support for libraries or Spring applications. JVM-BidText, on the other hand, offers a specialized approach for detecting sensitive data exposures in JVM applications, including libraries and Spring applications, by employing bidirectional text correlation analysis.

6.2. Evaluation on Case-Studies

Now that we have introduced the capabilities of GitHub CodeQL and JVM-BidText, we will evaluate both tools on the case studies from chapter 4. We apply both tools to the same set of applications to compare their effectiveness in detecting sensitive data exposures. We remember that the case studies include hand-crafted examples in Java and Kotlin, a real-world application, and an application built on top of the Spring framework. By analyzing these diverse scenarios, we aim to build a comprehensive understanding of the capabilities of JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL.

As we have already discussed the evaluation of JVM-BidText on the case studies in chapter 4, we will now look at the evaluation of GitHub CodeQL on the same case studies. CodeQL is integrated into the GitHub platform and can be used to analyze codebases hosted on GitHub. We will use this integration to analyze the case studies by uploading the code of all case studies to GitHub. We create one repository for the hand-crafted Java examples in total and one repository each for the real-world application, the Kotlin application and the Spring application². For all repositories, we enable CodeQL analysis in the repository settings. We configure the CodeQL analysis mostly with default settings, but we choose the extended query suite and allow remote and local sources in the threat model. Only the extended query suite contains the test for CWE-532³ titled “Insertion of Sensitive Information into Log File”. This query is the only one in the provided query suite that is relevant for our evaluation.

²See artifact description in chapter 11

³See <https://cwe.mitre.org/data/definitions/532.html>

```

public static void main(String[] args) {
    String s = "password";
    Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();
    json.put(s, "1234");
    String res = json.get(s);
    System.out.println(res);
}

```

Listing 22: Adapted test program for forward analysis. The program contains sensitive data in the map.

6.2.1. Evaluation on Hand-Crafted Examples

We will now present the results of the evaluation of GitHub CodeQL on the case studies. For the repository containing hand-crafted examples, the CodeQL analysis completes in just under 2 minutes. The analysis finds no issues in the codebase. This result is surprising as we designed the examples specifically to contain sensitive data exposures.

In section 4.2.1 we explained that we use empty maps to represent unknown data from remote services. While JVM-BidText does not check the content of maps but infers sensitivity information from the context, CodeQL might work differently. CodeQL might analyze the map content and does not find any sensitive data in the empty map. To investigate the problem, we adapt the code of the introductory example for forward analysis (listing 4) to contain sensitive data in the map. We also change the string `s` of the program to `"password"`, as this term is used in the demonstration of CodeQL in the documentation. We show the new `main` method in listing 22.

When we rerun the analysis with the updated example program, CodeQL does still not find any data exposure. Therefore, we need to conclude that CodeQL likely cannot exploit information in static strings or does not understand the semantics of a map.

The documentation of CodeQL discloses that CodeQL cannot analyze data flow through standard library functions [51]. The documentation states that it is impossible to compute data flow through standard library functions, where source code is unavailable. While we agree that accurate data flow cannot be calculated, we believe that it is reasonable to model data flow on a best-effort basis.

We know from section 4.2.1 that JVM-BidText can find the data exposure in the original example program. We verify that the adaptations we have made to the program do not affect the detection of the data exposure by JVM-BidText. JVM-BidText can find this data exposure by modeling data flow on a best-effort basis when source or bytecode is not available. We discussed the handling of API invocations in section 2.3. To fine-tune this modeling of API functions, JVM-BidText supports propagation rules that a user can specify as input. JVM-BidText includes rules for some of the most relevant standard library functions like map accesses. Even if no rule is present, JVM-BidText does not fail at the analysis but uses a default strategy to propagate type information. This strategy increases the likelihood of false positives or negatives but enables many detections that would not be possible otherwise.

Such a scenario that JVM-BidText can analyze because of its best-effort modeling is the example for whole-object logging we discussed in the case study for bidirectional analysis. As we mentioned in section 4.2.3, this example where an incoming JSON map is first logged for

debugging purposes and then processed is a realistic scenario. That CodeQL cannot detect this data exposure is especially disappointing, as we remember that whole-object logging is the most common root cause for sensitive data exposures [40].

CodeQL does not find any data exposure in the other hand-crafted examples either. As elements from the standard library are widely used in Java programs, we consider the observed behavior of CodeQL a significant limitation. Entirely ignoring data flow through standard library functions limits the effectiveness of CodeQL in practice. JVM-BidText, on the other hand, can detect data exposures in scenarios where standard library functions are involved.

6.2.2. Evaluation on Real-World Application

After we have had no success with CodeQL on the small hand-crafted examples, we have little confidence that CodeQL will perform better on alpaca-java, the real-world application from section 4.3. We enable scanning with CodeQL in the respective GitHub repository and wait for the analysis to complete. The analysis of the alpaca-java repository takes about 3 minutes. CodeQL reports three relevant problems in the codebase which are, however, not related to sensitive data exposures through log files.

Once again, we need to consider that CodeQL might fail to detect sensitive data exposures due to the use of library functions. When we look back at listing 9, we see that alpaca-java does not use any standard library functions in the path of the data exposure. But instead, alpaca-java uses `JsonObject`s from a third-party library to handle sensitive data. Although the documentation of CodeQL only mentions the incapability of analyzing data flow through standard library functions, we can assume that CodeQL has similar problems with third-party libraries. For all types of libraries, CodeQL does not have access to the source code.

From this case study, we conclude that the limitations we observed in the hand-crafted examples also apply to real-world applications. CodeQL cannot detect sensitive data exposures in data flows that involve libraries. This limitation is a significant drawback for CodeQL, as libraries are widely used in Java applications.

We remember from section 4.3 that JVM-BidText can detect the sensitive data exposure in alpaca-java. Therefore, we conclude that JVM-BidText's approach of modeling data flow on a best-effort basis where concrete information is missing can be beneficial in practice. With JVM-BidText, we can detect real data exposures that established tools like CodeQL cannot detect.

6.2.3. Evaluation on Kotlin Application

While CodeQL does not support all JVM languages, it does support Kotlin. We test CodeQL on the Kotlin application from section 4.4. The analysis with CodeQL does not find any data exposure in the Kotlin application. This is consistent with the results we have seen in the hand-crafted examples and the real-world application. Just like the hand-crafted examples, the Kotlin application uses a map accessed with a sensitive key which CodeQL cannot analyze.

Even if we ignored the fact that CodeQL has problems with this specific example, we would still need to consider that CodeQL does not support all JVM languages. By operating on JVM bytecode, JVM-BidText is more versatile in this regard and has an advantage over CodeQL. CodeQL, on the other hand, supports a set of completely unrelated languages like C, Python, and JavaScript. This broad support for non-JVM languages is an advantage of CodeQL over JVM-BidText.

6.2.4. Evaluation on Spring Application

Unsurprisingly, CodeQL fails at the analysis of the Spring application from section 4.5 as well. In an application built on top of a framework, even more parts of the code are not available to the analysis. We remember that frameworks go as far as managing the dependencies between objects. All of this management code is not available in the application code. An analysis tool like CodeQL therefore cannot understand the whole data flow.

Our extension for JVM-BidText to support Spring applications is a significant advantage in this case. We can model the semantics of dependency injection in Spring applications to ensure that data flow analysis can find connections between classes. While our model might not always be perfectly accurate, it enables us to detect sensitive data exposures in Spring applications at all. CodeQL does not provide specialized support for frameworks like Spring, and therefore cannot analyze data flow in Spring applications effectively. With a wide range of security analysis features, CodeQL brings other value to the table. For our demo Spring application, CodeQL once again found other relevant vulnerabilities. CodeQL seems, however, not to be the right tool for analyzing sensitive data exposures in many circumstances.

6.3. Exploration of Strengths and Weaknesses

All of our case studies indicate that CodeQL cannot detect sensitive data exposures in Java applications effectively. We need to consider, however, that at least all the hand-crafted examples are designed to demonstrate certain aspects of JVM-BidText. The hand-crafted examples all use a similar setup with a map to represent unknown data from remote services. As we know that CodeQL cannot handle standard library functions properly, we want to evaluate both tools on further tests. We upload the test programs we present in this section to a new GitHub repository⁴ and enable the CodeQL analysis. For our test cases, we use the term "password" to indicate sensitive data because we know from the documentation that CodeQL can detect this term. We did not find this term in our study on keywords in section 3.4.4. We add the term to the list of keywords in JVM-BidText. Therefore, we can guarantee that both tools have a chance to detect the sensitive data in the test cases.

In this section, we want to see if CodeQL can detect sensitive data exposures in scenarios where JVM-BidText fails and vice versa. We remember from the conclusions of our case study on alpaca-java in section 4.3.5 that JVM-BidText is not without limitations either. We develop test cases that we specifically design to exploit the limitations of both tools. We start with an investigation into the support for dynamic invocations — a known weak point of JVM-BidText. Then we move on to evaluate the support for bidirectional analysis — a feature that sets JVM-BidText apart from other tools. Finally, we investigate the support for different variants of sensitivity detection.

6.3.1. Support for Dynamic Invocations

In our case study on the real-world application alpaca-java in section 4.3, we encountered issues with dynamic invocations. To further investigate this problem, we develop a test case to study the capabilities of JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL in handling dynamic invocations. The test case, we show in listing 23, involves an interface `Leaky` with a method `exposeData`. We implement the interface using a lambda expression. Inside the lambda expression, we

⁴See artifact description in chapter 11

```

public class DynamicInvocation {
    private static final Logger logger =
        LoggerFactory.getLogger(DynamicInvocation.class);
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Leaky leaky = () -> {
            String password = "Pass@0rd";
            Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();
            String key = "user_password";
            json.put(key, password);

            String res = json.get(key);
            logger.debug("User password is " + res);
        };
        leaky.exposeData();
    }

    interface Leaky {
        void exposeData();
    }
}

```

Listing 23: Test case for dynamic invocations

produce a data exposure. We verify in advance that JVM-BidText and CodeQL can detect the sensitive data exposure if not placed in a lambda expression. Bytecode inspection shows that the compiler translates the call `leaky.exposeData()` to an `invokedynamic` instruction. This is the same instruction that causes problems in the analysis of `alpaca-java` as discussed in section 4.3.2 where we invoke abstract methods.

When we analyze this test case, JVM-BidText fails to detect the sensitive data exposure. We can attribute this failure to the known limitation of WALA in handling dynamic invocations.

In contrast, GitHub CodeQL successfully identifies the sensitive data exposure. The dynamic invocation does not pose a problem for CodeQL. This result highlights a limitation of JVM-BidText in dealing with dynamic invocations, whereas CodeQL proves to be more robust in this aspect.

6.3.2. Support for Bidirectional Analysis

One novel technique in BidText and thereby JVM-BidText is the bidirectional analysis of data flow. This technique promises to detect sensitive data exposures that are not identifiable by other tools using forward-only analysis. We have seen bidirectional analysis in action in the case studies, e.g., in section 4.2.3. In this section, we want to evaluate whether this feature is indeed an advantage of JVM-BidText over CodeQL. As CodeQL cannot handle the hand-crafted examples from the case studies because of their use of standard library functions, we develop a new test case.

To be specific, we develop a pair of test cases. The first test case shown in listing 24 requires only forward analysis to detect the sensitive data exposure. This program serves as a control. In the code, we retrieve data of unknown sensitivity. In this example, we retrieve it from the

```

public class ForwardPropagation {
    private static final Logger logger =
        LoggerFactory.getLogger(ForwardPropagation.class);
    private static final Map<String, String> json = new HashMap<>();

    public static void main(String[] args) {
        String s = getUnknownData();
        String password = s;
        json.put("password", password);
        logger.debug("String is " + password);
    }

    private static String getUnknownData() {
        return "Pass@0rd";
    }
}

```

Listing 24: Test case for forward analysis that serves as a control for the bidirectional analysis test case

```

public static void main(String[] args) {
    String s = getUnknownData();
    logger.debug("String is " + s);
    String password = s;
    json.put("password", password);
}

```

Listing 25: main method of test case for bidirectional analysis

local static method `getUnknownData`, but we can also imagine that we get this data as input from an external service. Next, we provide clues to the sensitivity of the data. We rename the variable `s` to `password`, as this might help CodeQL detect the sensitivity of the data. We also add `s` to a map with a sensitive key, as we know that this will indicate the sensitivity of `s` to JVM-BidText. Finally, we leak the data to the log.

For the second test case, we modify the first test case to require backward analysis to detect the sensitive data exposure. To this end, we switch the order of statements in the `main` method. We present the modified `main` method in listing 25. In the updated routine, we leak the sensitive information before we provide clues to its sensitivity. To find the data exposure, a tool must be able to propagate type information backward from the clues (variable rename and map access). In an abstracted view, we can think of this task as reasoning that if variable `password` is sensitive, then `s` is sensitive as well because `s` is assigned to `password`. Once we know that `s` is sensitive, we can follow the forward data flow to the log statement and detect the data exposure.

We analyze both test cases with JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL. JVM-BidText successfully detects the sensitive data exposure in both test cases. This result confirms that JVM-BidText can handle data exposures that require bidirectional analysis. CodeQL, on the other hand,

```

public static void main(String[] args) {
    String s = "ljkkljlkklj";
    String message = "User password is: " + s;
    logger.debug(message);
}

```

Listing 26: Test case for detecting sensitivity using static strings

```

public static void main(String[] args) {
    String s = "ljkkljlkklj";
    StringBuilder sb = new StringBuilder();
    sb.append("User password is: ");
    sb.append(s);
    logger.debug(sb.toString());
}

```

Listing 27: Test case for detecting sensitivity using static strings with a `StringBuilder`

finds the sensitive data exposure only in the first test case. This result indicates that CodeQL cannot perform backward analysis to detect sensitive data exposures. The inability to perform backward analysis is a significant limitation of CodeQL compared to JVM-BidText.

6.3.3. Variants of Sensitivity Detection

There are different approaches to detecting the sensitivity of data. In JVM-BidText, we use static strings to infer the sensitivity of data. We remember that a fundamental principle of JVM-BidText is to correlate variables with static strings as type information. Another approach is to use variable and method names to infer the sensitivity of data.

We already know from many tests with map accesses that JVM-BidText can exploit information in static strings. In this section, we want to test whether CodeQL can exploit information in static strings as well. Secondly, we want to test whether JVM-BidText and CodeQL can exploit information in variable and method names.

To test the exploitation of information in static strings, we develop a simple test case that we present in listing 26. The test case uses the static string "User password is: " that clearly indicates that the data it comes into contact with is sensitive. This string is the only clue to the sensitivity of the data. All variables and methods in the test case have generic names.

We analyze the test case with JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL. JVM-BidText surprisingly fails to detect the sensitive data exposure. We know from the original paper that BidText can handle string concatenation [35]. We left the handling of string concatenation mostly untouched in our rework of BidText. The handling for string concatenation assumes that the + operator is translated to a `StringBuilder` in the bytecode. We want to test whether JVM-BidText in contrast to the original BidText cannot handle the `StringBuilder` or whether the problem has another cause. We translate the program from listing 26 to use a `StringBuilder` instead of the + operator and show the resulting program in listing 27. When we use a `StringBuilder` in the

source of the test case directly, JVM-BidText can detect the sensitive data exposure without problems. As it turns out, newer versions of Java have optimized the `+` operator and do not use a `StringBuilder` as the backing solution anymore. From Java 9 onward, the `+` operator is translated into calls to `StringConcatFactory` methods [53]. We can attribute the failure in the analysis to the lack of specialized support for `StringConcatFactory` in JVM-BidText.

Let us now turn to the evaluation of CodeQL. CodeQL cannot detect the sensitive data exposure in either the original test case or the test case with the `StringBuilder`. We can interpret this result in two ways. First, CodeQL might not be able to exploit information in static strings. Second, CodeQL might not understand the semantics of string concatenation⁵. The latter would indicate that CodeQL does not consider the `+` operator as a fundamental part of the language but as a standard library function.

We want to investigate which of the two interpretations is correct. As a further test, we rename the variable `s` to `password` in the first test program shown in listing 26. Thereby, we still require processing of the `+` operator before the sink. However, we provide an additional clue to the sensitivity of the data in the form of the variable name. We rerun the analysis with the updated test case. This time, CodeQL successfully detects the sensitive data exposure. This result indicates that CodeQL can exploit information in variable names but not in static strings. The result further indicates that CodeQL can handle string concatenation.

We want to test whether JVM-BidText can exploit information in variable names as well. As we discovered the limitation of JVM-BidText with string concatenation with the `+` operator, we will focus on the second test variant in listing 27 with the `StringBuilder`. We rename the variable `sb` to `passwords` and replace the string `"User password is: "` with `"123456"` in the test case. Thereby, we can infer sensitivity information from the variable name but not from the static string.

We analyze the updated test case with JVM-BidText. JVM-BidText does not detect the sensitive data exposure. This result indicates that JVM-BidText cannot exploit information in variable names. As a control for the previous result with CodeQL, we analyze the test case with CodeQL as well. CodeQL successfully detects the sensitive data exposure, which confirms that CodeQL can exploit information in variable names.

Let us summarize the results of this test case with its variants. During the analysis, we discovered a limitation of JVM-BidText in handling string concatenation with the `+` operator. In terms of exploiting information in static strings, CodeQL fails where JVM-BidText succeeds. However, CodeQL can exploit information in variable names, whereas JVM-BidText cannot. We can conclude that both tools have different approaches to detecting the sensitivity of data; while JVM-BidText relies on static strings, CodeQL relies on variable names and possibly more. This difference in approaches can lead to different results in the analysis of sensitive data exposures. Both tools can find sensitive data exposures that the other tool cannot detect.

⁵We already know that CodeQL cannot handle the `StringBuilder` methods because they are standard library functions.

6.4. Discussion of Evaluation Results

We want to answer **RQ 4** with a discussion of the results of our comparison between JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL. We summarize the findings from our evaluations and draw conclusions based on the observed strengths and weaknesses of each tool.

Our evaluations reveal that both JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL have distinct advantages and limitations. First, we look at the scope of supported applications. JVM-BidText, in general, supports all languages that compile to JVM bytecode. GitHub CodeQL supports multiple programming languages, including Java, JavaScript, Python, and more, but not all JVM languages.

JVM-BidText can detect sensitive data exposures in JVM applications or libraries, even those using the Spring framework. It can handle applications where data flow involves standard and third-party library functions where source code or bytecode is not available. We have demonstrated these capabilities in our case studies on a real-world application (section 4.3), and a Spring application (section 4.5). In contrast, we have observed that CodeQL lacks the capability to analyze data flow through standard and third-party library functions. This limitation hinders CodeQL’s effectiveness in detecting sensitive data exposures in real-world applications that heavily rely on libraries. In section 6.2 we hooked into the analysis of the case studies and exposed CodeQL to the same challenges as JVM-BidText. CodeQL cannot detect sensitive data exposures in any of our case studies.

For the evaluation of both tools on the case studies, we did not only focus on the sensitive data exposures but also on the performance of the tools. We noted that CodeQL operates in the range of minutes for the analysis of the case studies. JVM-BidText, on the other hand, can analyze the same codebases in a matter of seconds. We can attribute this difference in performance to the fact that CodeQL is a general-purpose tool that executes a wide range of queries where only one query is relevant for the analysis of sensitive data exposures. JVM-BidText, on the other hand, is a specialized tool that focuses on detecting sensitive data exposures.

When we evaluated CodeQL on the case studies, we briefly mentioned the setup process for CodeQL. We noted that CodeQL is integrated into the GitHub platform and can be used to analyze codebases hosted on GitHub. It requires minimal setup and configuration in the repository settings. While the default configuration is sufficient for most cases, CodeQL provides advanced settings for users who want to customize the analysis. We want to mention that the analysis of sensitive data exposures is only part of the extended query suite of CodeQL.

For JVM-BidText, we have seen in section 3.4.1 that JVM-BidText also supports user configuration in the form of different rule sets. In general, however, JVM-BidText requires no configuration for the analysis, just like CodeQL. In cases where the application code extends classes from third-party libraries, JVM-BidText might require access to the bytecode of the libraries, which a user has to configure. Additional configuration is not required, but can be beneficial for improving the results of the analysis. JVM-BidText is not integrated into a platform like GitHub, but it can be used as a standalone tool. This results in more manual setup work if a developer wants to use the tool in a CI/CD pipeline. JVM-BidText presents the results of the analysis in a text-based format, whereas CodeQL provides a graphical user interface for the analysis results. This difference in presentation together with the integration into the GitHub platform makes CodeQL more user-friendly than JVM-BidText.

After the evaluation on the case studies, we explored specific strengths and weaknesses of JVM-BidText and CodeQL. We saw that JVM-BidText not only has an advantage in the scope

6. Comparison of JVM-BidText and CodeQL

of supported applications. It also has a unique feature in bidirectional analysis. JVM-BidText can perform bidirectional analysis to detect sensitive data exposures that require backward analysis. In such scenarios, the analysis reaches the sink before it can infer the sensitivity of the data. This can be the case for the prominent threat of whole-object logging. CodeQL does not find the data exposures in our test cases that require backward analysis.

We also observed that both tools have different approaches to the detection of the sensitivity of data. JVM-BidText relies on static strings, whereas CodeQL relies on variable names and possibly more. This difference in approaches leads to different results in the analysis of sensitive data exposures. Both tools can find sensitive data exposures that the other tool cannot detect.

Furthermore, we identified limitations of JVM-BidText that CodeQL does not have. We showed that JVM-BidText struggles with dynamic invocations due to limitations in the underlying analysis framework WALA. CodeQL, on the other hand, demonstrates robustness in handling dynamic invocations and lambda expressions.

During our tests, we accidentally discovered that JVM-BidText lacks support for string concatenation using the + operator in newer Java versions. As support for string concatenation is intended, we consider this behavior a bug in JVM-BidText. We can likely fix this bug. CodeQL can handle string concatenation properly.

As mentioned at the beginning of this section, we discover a significant limitation of CodeQL in the lack of support for standard and third-party library functions. JVM-BidText can handle data flow through standard and third-party library functions by modeling data flow on a best-effort basis. This proves to be a significant advantage of JVM-BidText in practice.

We can explain some differences in analysis results with the different approaches to detecting the sensitivity of data. We can attribute other differences to clear advantages of one tool over the other. In addition, we have identified limitations of CodeQL that JVM-BidText does not have and vice versa.

In summary, JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL complement each other in their approaches for detecting sensitive data exposures. Due to their unique capabilities, both tools can find sensitive data exposures that the other tool cannot detect. By leveraging the strengths of both tools, developers can achieve more comprehensive security analysis in their codebases.

7. Threats to Validity

With limited time and resources available, we had to make several decisions that could impact the validity of our results. These threats could impact the reliability and generalizability of our conclusions.

One significant threat is the possibility of bugs in the implementation of JVM-BidText and our evaluation tools. Despite thorough testing, there may be undiscovered issues that affect the accuracy of our analysis. Our reliance on the original BidText, which we refactored for our purposes, introduces another layer of potential errors. We have compared the results of our refactored implementation with the original version in multiple steps to ensure consistency. As the scope of supported applications has changed between the original and refactored versions, we cannot test the complete refactored implementation on original input. Instead, we progressively tested the refactored implementation once we had changed certain components. This approach may have introduced errors that we did not detect. During the adaptation of the approach to JVM applications, we fixed multiple bugs in the original BidText. This process most likely changes the behavior of the refactored BidText compared to the original. Further bugs present in the original BidText could propagate into our refactored version, impacting the results.

The implementation of JVM-BidText uses unsound static analysis techniques. These techniques can lead to false positives and false negatives. In practice, it is often impossible to achieve soundness in static analysis without sacrificing precision and performance. Further, we only analyze the bytecode from an application itself and generally do not consider library or framework code. If the data flow analysis reaches calls to external libraries and no corresponding propagation rules are defined, the analysis models the propagation of sensitive data on a best-effort basis. This approach can lead to both over- and under-approximation of the data flow. We deem the compromises taken in JVM-BidText to be acceptable for the benefits they provide. However, they could still lead to incorrect results in the analysis.

Our approach for the support of the Spring framework is also based on compromises. As discussed in section 5.3.5 we focus on basic support for a very central part of the Spring framework, the dependency injection. The lack of support for other features of the Spring framework and our simplifications in the modeling of dependency injection could lead to incorrect results in the analysis.

JVM-BidText does not only support standard Java applications, but also libraries and applications using the Spring framework. While it is easy to define the entry point for standard Java applications, finding entry points for libraries and framework applications is a non-trivial problem. We implement an algorithm to automatically detect entry points for Spring applications based on annotations. Furthermore, we provide an algorithm based on naming conventions to automatically detect entry points for libraries. However, this algorithm generally does not find all relevant entry points. JVM-BidText will therefore miss some data flows in libraries and Spring applications. This limitation could lead to false negatives in the analysis.

JVM-BidText uses an unsound approach to infer sensitivity from static strings. The detection of sensitivity is based on keywords and an unsound and incomplete approach for the detection of negations. This approach comes with benefits, especially in terms of minimal required user

7. Threats to Validity

input. However, it also introduces the risk of false positives and false negatives.

Apart from the implementation itself, the quality of the configuration used in the analysis could also affect the results. We provide default configurations that users can adapt to their needs. One configurable aspect of JVM-BidText is the set of keywords used to identify sensitive data exposures. The choice of keywords has a large effect on the number of false positives and false negatives. The keywords we selected are based on one real-world application and may not be representative. Furthermore, keywords are likely domain-specific and may not generalize well to other applications.

Another aspect of JVM-BidText that we can configure is the amount of external library code to include in the analysis. As we know, sometimes libraries need to be included in the analysis to provide access to superclass code. If we include too many libraries or do not define enough exclusion rules for parts of the libraries, the analysis can become slower and more memory-intensive than necessary. Ideally, we would find a way to avoid the need to include libraries just for superclass access. The presence or absence of library code in the analysis could also affect whether the analysis finds sensitive data exposures.

There are further threats regarding the evaluation of the approach. The hand-crafted examples do not represent the complexity and diversity of real-world applications. They are designed to test specific aspects of the tools and approaches. As a result, the performance of JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL on these examples may not accurately reflect their performance in more complex scenarios.

The choice of the program for the real-world case study also affects the validity of our findings. We selected `alpaca-java` as an application fitting our criteria, but this choice may introduce bias. We knowingly selected an application that we expected to contain sensitive data exposure vulnerabilities. Different applications with varying architectures and data flows could yield different results. The sample size of one real-world application leads to a lack of generalizability. Thus, our findings may not be representative of the performance of JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL on other applications. A methodologically sound study on a large scale would provide a more comprehensive evaluation.

Our knowledge of our own tool, JVM-BidText, is greater than our knowledge of GitHub CodeQL. This disparity could influence our evaluation and interpretation of the results. We may inadvertently favor JVM-BidText due to our familiarity with its inner workings and limitations. Conversely, our limited understanding of CodeQL's intricacies could lead to an underestimation of its capabilities.

The differing setups and scopes of capabilities between JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL influence how well we can compare both tools. We designed JVM-BidText specifically for JVM applications, with a focus on bidirectional analysis, detection of sensitivity from static strings, and specialized support for the Spring framework. In contrast, GitHub CodeQL offers a broader range of analysis capabilities, including various security vulnerabilities and general issues in codebases. CodeQL lacks specialized support for the Spring framework and libraries.

Additionally, we chose to work with CodeQL integrated into GitHub, as this is the way we commonly use CodeQL. Not using CodeQL as a standalone application limits our ability to compare runtime and memory usage between the two tools. Further, in JVM-BidText runtime and memory measurements themselves might not be accurate. We use the measurement functionality originally implemented in BidText. This mechanism uses the amount of free memory right after the analysis to estimate the memory usage. The garbage collector might heavily influence this measurement.

8. Related Work

We introduce related work grouped into three categories. The list is not exhaustive by any means. Especially once we leave the realm of sensitive data exposure detection, and look into framework support and tools with special analysis techniques, we find a plethora of approaches. All of these approaches can still hold valuable insights for the future development of JVM-BidText.

8.1. Sensitive Data Exposure Detection

First and foremost, we want to mention the work of Huang, Zhang, and Tan on BidText [35]. BidText is the foundation of our work. BidText is a static analysis tool for Android applications that detects sensitive data exposures. It introduces novel techniques for the detection of sensitive data exposures, especially bidirectional analysis and the use of static strings to infer sensitivity without user input. We have discussed the approach of BidText in detail in chapter 2.

GitHub CodeQL¹ [34] is a powerful semantic code analysis engine used to find security vulnerabilities and other issues in codebases. Its capabilities include the detection of sensitive data exposures through log files. GitHub CodeQL is an established commercial tool and available via an integration with the GitHub platform. In contrast to JVM-BidText, CodeQL offers a broader range of analysis capabilities. However, CodeQL lacks specialized support for the Spring framework and libraries, and has no bidirectional analysis capabilities. CodeQL supports automatic detection of sources without any user input, but uses a different approach than JVM-BidText. We have discussed the comparison of JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL in chapter 6.

FlowDroid² [32, 36] is a static taint-analysis tool for Android applications. Although FlowDroid is originally designed for Android applications, it also supports the analysis of other Java applications. It focuses on high recall and precision in detecting sensitive data exposures. FlowDroid achieves precision by employing context-, flow-, field-, and object-sensitive analysis. The analysis is further tailored to Android-specific challenges such as lifecycle management of components. FlowDroid depends on a list of methods that represent sources of sensitive data. In contrast to JVM-BidText and CodeQL, FlowDroid does not support automatic discovery of sources. Both JVM-BidText and FlowDroid use a list of methods that represent sinks. In contrast to FlowDroid, JVM-BidText allows fine-grained control over which parameters of a sink method actually expose data. Both JVM-BidText and FlowDroid provide default lists of methods for sources and sinks.

JOANA [22, 29] is a static analysis tool that focuses on information flow control and security analysis for Java programs. JOANA scales to large programs in the order of 100 kLoC. Like FlowDroid, JOANA uses context-, flow-, field-, and object-sensitive analysis. Similar to JVM-BidText, JOANA builds a system dependence graph (SDG). JOANA's SDG strictly over-approximates the information flow. This enables JOANA to make guarantees to find all

¹See <https://codeql.github.com/>

²See <https://github.com/secure-software-engineering/FlowDroid>

violations of integrity and confidentiality. JOANA comes with a machine-checked soundness proof. JOANA is limited to the analysis of Java programs up to version 7 and excluding reflection, making it unsuitable for analyzing modern Java applications. For comparison, by using WALA as its analysis engine JVM-BidText supports Java 23. The analysis of JVM-BidText is not sound, however. In contrast to JVM-BidText, JOANA requires manual user input in the form of annotations to define sources and sinks. The process of defining sources and sinks is labor-intensive and error-prone. Results are only as good as the annotations the user provides. The requirement for manual input makes JOANA less suitable for practical use.

8.2. Static Analysis Engines

WALA (T.J. Watson Libraries for Analysis)³ is a set of libraries for static analysis of JVM bytecode. It provides a framework for building analysis tools and supports various types of program analysis, including call graph construction and data flow analysis. We use WALA for working with JVM bytecode and for standard program analysis tasks in JVM-BidText.

Instead of WALA we could have chosen other static analysis frameworks like Soot⁴ [13] or DOOP⁵ [21]. Soot is a framework for analyzing and transforming Java and Android applications. It offers a range of analysis and transformation capabilities, including call graph construction and points-to analysis. DOOP focuses on points-to analysis. All three frameworks offer similar basic features like points-to analysis. However, the focus of the frameworks and their support for specific analysis tasks differ. WALA and Soot come with different intermediate representations with distinct capabilities. For example, Soot allows for modification of loaded IR while WALA does only support addition of IR classes. However, WALA includes tools for bytecode instrumentation which other frameworks lack. Sui, Dietrich, Emery, Rasheed, and Tahir compared WALA, Soot and DOOP in terms of soundness. They find that WALA can handle dynamic language features like reflection better than Soot and DOOP [38].

8.3. Static Analysis of Framework Applications

Jasmine [43] extends the Soot analysis framework to support the analysis of Spring applications. Jasmine aims to enhance the completeness of call graphs for Spring applications without greatly increasing the performance of the analysis. Jasmine supports widely used Spring core technologies, including dependency injection and aspect-oriented programming. To accomplish this goal, Jasmine models these features on IR level as a preprocessing step for the actual analysis. Jasmine serves as a template for the JVM-BidText approach to provide support for the Spring framework. Together with Jasmine, Chen, Tu, Zhang, Wen, and Wang present an adapted version of FlowDroid for Spring applications.

F4F (Framework for Frameworks) [27] has a more general approach than Jasmine or JVM-BidText for the support of frameworks. F4F aims to bring effective taint analysis to web applications built on top of different frameworks, including Spring. Sridharan, Artzi, Pistoia, Guarnieri, Tripp, and Berg motivate F4F by criticizing that ad hoc support for specific frameworks in an analysis tool (like JVM-BidText) is not scalable to the support for many frameworks. F4F generates a specification of framework-specific behavior from an application's

³See <https://github.com/wala/WALA>

⁴See <https://github.com/soot-oss/soot>

⁵See <https://github.com/plast-lab/doop>

8. Related Work

code and configuration files. Like Jasmine, F4F performs this analysis as a pre-processing step. The generated specifications serve as input to a taint analysis engine. Among others, F4F comes with a specification generator for Spring.

JackEE [39] is a static analysis framework for enterprise Java applications. JackEE has a similar goal to F4F in that it aims to support the analysis of Java applications built on top of different frameworks. In contrast to F4F, JackEE does not generate specifications for each framework, but instead models the semantics of common concepts underlying all frameworks. Among others, JackEE provides solutions for the discovery of entry points—a challenge that JVM-BidText also faces. As a further contribution, JackEE introduces sound-modulo-analysis modeling of core data structures like maps. This concept allows JackEE to achieve high scalability while also improving the precision of the analysis. JackEE is intended to open up the field of static analysis to enterprise applications.

TAJ (Taint Analysis for Java) [23] is a static taint analysis tool for Java applications and specifically industry-level applications of a large scale. TAJ supports the analysis of applications built on top of different frameworks. It addresses various attack vectors of web applications, including data exposure. TAJ introduces the approach of hybrid thin slicing that is a compromise between context-sensitive analysis and traditional context-insensitive thin slicing; we use the latter in JVM-BidText.

ANDROMEDA [31] is another static taint analysis tool that targets the analysis of large-scale Java applications built on top of different frameworks, including Spring. ANDROMEDA achieves scalability by using a dynamic and incremental approach to tracking vulnerable data flows. Other tools, including JVM-BidText, eagerly analyze the data flow of the entire program.

9. Conclusion

We want to help developers prevent sensitive data exposure vulnerabilities in their software systems. Especially in the context of logging, it is crucial not to expose sensitive information inadvertently. In practice, however, it is often challenging to determine what and how to log, making tools supporting this task all the more important. As a solution, we present JVM-BidText, a tool for the detection of sensitive data exposures in JVM applications, including libraries and applications built on top of the Spring framework. JVM-BidText can help developers identify potential security risks in their code early in the development process.

With JVM-BidText, we generalize the capabilities of the existing tool BidText [35] and make the benefits of BidText available to a broader range of applications. We modernize the codebase of BidText to support Java up to version 23 and adapt the setup of the analysis engine to support JVM applications. We adapt and generalize various components of the analysis, including the text analysis, propagation rules, and sink definitions. Further, we conduct a study on a real-world application to find keywords suitable for inferring the sensitivity of data in JVM applications. We conclude that it is possible to transfer the approach to sensitive data detection used in BidText to JVM applications. However, the heterogeneous nature of JVM applications poses additional challenges for JVM-BidText, that we can partially address, e.g., by implementing different strategies for the detection of entry points.

By supporting JVM bytecode, we extend the scope of supported applications even beyond Java and make JVM-BidText capable of analyzing applications written in other JVM languages like Kotlin. We identify that libraries and frameworks pose additional challenges for static analysis because essential parts of the program flow are hidden in external code. To aid the analysis of libraries and applications built on top of the popular Spring framework, we implement different strategies for the detection of entry points, including the identification of callback methods and controller endpoints. Furthermore, we enhance JVM-BidText to support dependency injection in the Spring framework. To this end, we model Inversion of Control on an intermediate representation level and perform bytecode modification, enabling JVM-BidText to analyze data flow through Spring managed classes. Thereby, we extend JVM-BidText’s applicability to enterprise-grade applications. While we can show the effectiveness of our approach to support dependency injection, we acknowledge that the support for Spring applications is still limited. We aim to extend the support for the Spring framework by addressing other features like aspect-oriented programming in the future.

We evaluate JVM-BidText on multiple case studies and a real-world application to demonstrate JVM-BidText’s capabilities and limitations. The results demonstrate that JVM-BidText detects sensitive data exposures effectively with little manual input. We find, however, that the analysis results often benefit from additional configuration, e.g., in the form of custom propagation rules for important methods from standard or third-party libraries. From our study on keywords, we know that the choice of keywords has a large effect on the number of false positives and false negatives. The choice of keywords allows users to focus the analysis on specific types of sensitive data. The keywords we selected are likely domain-specific and may not generalize well to other applications.

9. Conclusion

To further evaluate strengths and weaknesses, we compare JVM-BidText to GitHub CodeQL, a state-of-the-art static analysis tool. We find that both tools have different approaches to the detection of sensitive data; while JVM-BidText relies on static strings, CodeQL relies on variable names and possibly more. The comparison shows that JVM-BidText has limitations in the analysis of abstract method calls that CodeQL can handle better. However, the comparison also highlights many advantages of JVM-BidText over CodeQL. JVM-BidText’s ability to analyze data flows that involve standard or third-party library methods proves to be very beneficial in practice. Bidirectional analysis enables JVM-BidText to detect sensitive data exposures that CodeQL cannot detect because the data is leaked before its sensitivity can be determined. This capability of JVM-BidText is especially useful for the detection of insecure whole-object logging, which we remember as the most common root cause for sensitive data exposure vulnerabilities [40]. In summary, JVM-BidText and GitHub CodeQL complement each other in their approaches for detecting sensitive data exposures. Due to their unique capabilities, both tools can find sensitive data exposures that the other tool cannot detect. By leveraging the strengths of both tools, developers can achieve more comprehensive security analysis in their codebases.

We conclude that JVM-BidText, even with its limitations and need for future improvements, is a valuable tool that can bring benefits to developers in real-world use. We have witnessed that JVM-BidText can effectively detect sensitive data exposures even in complex scenarios where state-of-the-art static analysis tools fall short. By supporting JVM applications, libraries, and the Spring framework, we meet our main objective to make the benefits of BidText available to a broader range of applications. Therefore, we consider our generalization of the approach to sensitive data exposure detection used in BidText successful.

10. Future Work

At the current stage of development, JVM-BidText is still a prototype which implies that further development and evaluation are necessary. We identify several areas for future work:

- More comprehensive and large-scale evaluation
- Improvements achievable with the current implementation of JVM-BidText
- Major changes to the implementation of JVM-BidText

10.1. Extended Evaluation

Let us begin with the topic of evaluation. The current version of JVM-BidText shows promising results in detecting sensitive data exposures in hand-crafted and real-world case studies. However, a more comprehensive evaluation on a larger scale is necessary to validate the results. Especially the extension for the Spring framework requires further evaluation with real-world applications. A larger evaluation would also allow us to compare the performance of JVM-BidText to other state-of-the-art tools.

Future evaluations should analyze the memory consumption and performance of JVM-BidText in more detail. External memory consumption and performance measurement tools could provide more credible results than the current integrated measurement. A more rigorous measurement of the performance could help to identify bottlenecks in the analysis and optimize the tool.

10.2. Improvements with the Current Implementation

We could improve the results of the current version of JVM-BidText by fine-tuning the propagation rules for important API methods from the standard and third-party libraries. Furthermore, we could improve the versatility of JVM-BidText by looking into the support of more sinks. For this thesis, we focused on sinks in the category of logging, e.g., methods from the classes `java.io.PrintStream` or `org.slf4j.Logger`. Generally, JVM-BidText already supports arbitrary sinks via the configuration file. We could provide more sink definitions for common libraries and frameworks. This could include sinks from other categories like network communication or database access.

We could also look into the integration of JVM-BidText into CI/CD pipelines to make the tool more accessible to developers. In terms of accessibility, we could also improve upon the representation of the analysis results. In comparison to the graphical user interface of the well-integrated and established tool CodeQL, JVM-BidText's text-based reports are not very user-friendly. We could improve the reports generated by JVM-BidText by making the elements of the data flow path easier to understand.

10.3. Major Changes to the Implementation

Let us now turn to more drastic changes that we could make to improve JVM-BidText. JVM-BidText is based on partially unsound and imprecise static analysis techniques. There are good reasons for the compromises taken in the implementation, but they could still lead to incorrect results. We could look into ways to improve the soundness and precision without sacrificing performance. We could try to integrate static analysis techniques that have proven to be useful in other tools. For example, we could investigate hybrid thin slicing [23] that we mentioned for TAJ in chapter 8.

We could also aim to increase the precision of the analysis by improving the approach for the detection of sensitive data. As a first step, we could start by refining the approach for detecting sensitive data from static strings. At the current state, the approach is based on keywords and regular expression. We employ natural language processing only for the detection of negations in a proof-of-concept manner. A more sophisticated approach could involve machine learning techniques. In a second step, we could look into the detection of sensitive data in other parts of the program, e.g., in the names of methods or variables, or in comments. This might require access to the source code of the application. If combined with the information from static strings, this could lead to an advantage over other tools that only rely on variable or method names.

The current implementation of JVM-BidText already has an advantage over many general-purpose tools by supporting the analysis of Spring applications. However, the support for Spring core technologies is limited to a basic level. In the current version, we only support beans and dependency injection. We could extend the support for the Spring framework by addressing other features like aspect-oriented programming. We could also improve the modeling of dependency injection by considering more complex scenarios like bean creation through factory methods.

JVM-BidText aims to support a wide range of JVM applications. We have shown approaches for the analysis of libraries and built support for dependency injection in Spring applications. We could expand the scope of supported applications even further by adding support for other frameworks. To make this task scalable, we could look into the approaches of F4F [27] or JackEE [39] that we discussed in chapter 8.

10.4. Perspective on Future Work

In this thesis, we have shown that JVM-BidText already is a valuable tool that has capabilities that other tools lack. Nonetheless, there is still a lot of potential for further development. Depending on the goals of the project, different areas could be prioritized, e.g., improving the precision of the analysis, extending the support for frameworks, or improving the user-friendliness of the tool. With these ideas for future work, we or other researchers can make JVM-BidText even more valuable for developers in everyday use.

11. Artifact Description

JVM-BidText

We want to enable the community to reproduce our results and to build upon our work. Therefore, we provide the source code of JVM-BidText. The repository contains a README file with instructions on how to build and run the tool. The README file also contains instructions on how to reproduce the results of the evaluation. The source code of JVM-BidText is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/LeoGanz/JVM-BidText>. To guarantee long-term availability, we provide access to JVM-BidText on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14034414>

Test Cases

We make the test cases used in this thesis available in separate repositories.

- LeakyCode used in the case studies with hand-crafted Java examples is available at <https://github.com/LeoGanz/LeakyCode>.
- alpaca-java used in the real-world case study is available at <https://github.com/Petersoj/alpaca-java>. We also provide a version with small modifications for the correct setup at <https://github.com/LeoGanz/alpaca-java>.
- LeakyKotlin used in the Kotlin case study is available at <https://github.com/LeoGanz/LeakyKotlin>.
- LeakySprings used in the Spring case study is available at <https://github.com/LeoGanz/LeakySprings>.
- The test cases for the comparison with GitHub CodeQL are available at <https://github.com/LeoGanz/CodeQL-Tests>.

To guarantee long-term availability, we provide an all-in-one archive of the test cases on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14033511>

License

All our code is licensed under the Apache License 2.0. The library alpaca-java is licensed under the MIT License. We encourage the community to use the code to build upon our work, and to contribute to the development of JVM-BidText.

A. Log for Bug in Typing Graph Construction

```
1 stmt usage: param caller (1) in callee (2)
2 (1): PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ main([Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: Everywhere[53]invokespecial < Application,
  ↳ Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ <init>([Ljava/lang/String;[Lextraction/collector/StringCollector;)V > 29,28,30 @99
  ↳ exception:36 v28
3 (2): PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ <init>([Ljava/lang/String;[Lextraction/collector/StringCollector;)V > Context:
  ↳ Everywhere v2
4 MethodCaller target: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ <init>([Ljava/lang/String;[Lextraction/collector/StringCollector;)V >
5 MethodCallee      : < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ <init>([Ljava/lang/String;[Lextraction/collector/StringCollector;)V >
6 Caller target matches callee: true
7 stmt usage: param caller (1) in callee (2)
8 (1): PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ main([Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: Everywhere[56]invokevirtual < Application,
  ↳ Lextraction/StringExtractor, doAnalysis()V > 29 @104 exception:37 v29
9 (2): PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ <init>([Ljava/lang/String;[Lextraction/collector/StringCollector;)V > Context:
  ↳ Everywhere v1
10 MethodCaller target: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor, doAnalysis()V >
11 MethodCallee      : < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ <init>([Ljava/lang/String;[Lextraction/collector/StringCollector;)V >
12 Caller target matches callee: false
13 stmt usage: param caller (1) in callee (2)
14 (1): PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor, doAnalysis()V >
  ↳ Context: Everywhere[40]invokevirtual < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ handleString(Ljava/lang/String;)V > 1,26 @82 exception:27 v1
15 (2): PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ handleString(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: Everywhere v1
16 MethodCaller target: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ handleString(Ljava/lang/String;)V >
17 MethodCallee      : < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ handleString(Ljava/lang/String;)V >
18 Caller target matches callee: true
19 stmt usage: param caller (1) in callee (2)
20 (1): PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ handleString(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: Everywhere[11]10 = invokevirtual <
  ↳ Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor, isStringRelevant(Ljava/lang/String;)Z >
  ↳ 1,8 @17 exception:9 v1
21 (2): PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ isStringRelevant(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > Context: Everywhere v1
22 MethodCaller target: < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ isStringRelevant(Ljava/lang/String;)Z >
23 MethodCallee      : < Application, Lextraction/StringExtractor,
  ↳ isStringRelevant(Ljava/lang/String;)Z >
```

A. Log for Bug in Typing Graph Construction

```
24 Caller target matches callee: true
25
26 ...
```

Listing 28: Log that shows a mismatched callee and caller target during the construction of a typing graph for a example program that extracts strings from bytecode. The log contains information on how the statements of caller and callee side are matched during parameter passing. Information on the linkage is obtained when the callee is processed, which happens after the caller is processed and cached. Statements of the caller side are tagged with (1) and the callee side with (2). The lines following a caller - callee pair are substrings to aid in comparing the target method of (1) to the invoked method of (2). See lines 7–12 for the mismatch.

B. Keywords extracted from alpaca-java

```
1 # This file has the following format:
2 #
3 # CATERGORY
4 # pattern 1
5 # or pattern n
6 # # -> comment / disabled pattern
7 # blank line or EOF -> end of category
8
9 ACCOUNT
10 account[_\s]?id
11
12 AUTH
13 (bearer|oauth|access|processor) [_/\s]?token
14 key|secret
15
16 PERSONAL_INFO
17 (first|last|given|family|middle|full|nick|account[_\s]?(holder|owner)|applicant|_
18 ↪ transmitter|employer)[_\s]?name
19 date[_\s]?of[_\s]?birth|gender|police[_\s]?record
20 tax[_\s]?id|tax[_\s]?identification[_\s]?number|tax[_\s]?residence|ssn|_
21 ↪ social[_\s]?security[_\s]?number
22 national[_\s]?id|passport|drivers?[_\s]?license|gov[_\s]?id
23 income|net[_\s]?worth|wealth|employment[_\s]?(status|position)
24 (?<!(company|bank)[a-z_\s]{0,15})((e-)?mail|phone|address|residency|country|state|_
25 ↪ province|city|(zip|postal)[_\s]?code|nationality)
26 visa[_\s]?(type|expiration[_\s]?date)
27 politically[_\s]?exposed
28
29 BANKING_INFO
30 account[_\s]?number|iban
31 # bic|swift|routing[_\s]?(code|number)
```

Listing 29: Keyword patterns built from the results of the keyword study on alpaca-java in section 3.4.4

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
1 SINK [org.slf4j.Logger.trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V]
2 in [net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.AlpacaWebSocket.sendMessage(Ljava/lang|
  ↪ /String;)V]
3
4 The following texts reached the sink:
5 - secret_key
6 - authenticate
7 - data
8 - key_id
9 - WebSocket message sent: {}
10 - oauth_token
11 - action
12 In these texts, the following sensitivity indicators (keywords in a non-negated context)
  ↪ appeared:
13 - oauth_token
14 - secret
15 - key
16
17
18 ***** secret_key *****
19 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebSocket,
  ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebSocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↪ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↪ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
20 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebSocket,
  ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebSocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↪ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↪ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
21 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebSocket,
  ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebSocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↪ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↪ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
22 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebSocket,
  ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebSocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↪ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↪ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
23 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
24 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
25
26
27 ***** key_id *****
28 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
29 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
30 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
31 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
32 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
33 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
34
35
36 ***** oauth_token *****
37 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
38 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
39 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
40 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onConnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
41 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
42 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
```

Listing 30: Analysis report from BidText on the alpaca-java library. The report shows a data exposure in method `sendWebsocketMessage` found in the analysis of entry point `onConnection`. The data exposure can be verified in a manual analysis of the source code.

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
1 SINK [org.slf4j.Logger.trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V]
2 in [net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.AlpacaWebsocket.sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang|
  ↳ /String;)V]
3
4 The following texts reached the sink:
5 - listening
6 - authenticate
7 - data
8 - key_id
9 - Websocket message sent: {}
10 - streams
11 - trade_updates
12 - Requested streams: streams={}.
13 - listen
14 - authorization
15 - secret_key
16 - oauth_token
17 - action
18 In these texts, the following sensitivity indicators (keywords in a non-negated context)
  ↳ appeared:
19 - oauth_token
20 - secret
21 - key
22
23
24 ***** secret_key *****
25 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
26 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
27 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
28 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
29 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob|
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
30 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
   ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
   ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
   ↳ ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
   ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
31
32
33 ***** key_id *****
34 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updatees/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↳ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
35 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updatees/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↳ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
36 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updatees/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
37 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updatees/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
38 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
   ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
   ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
   ↳ v2
39 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
   ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
   ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
   ↳ ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
   ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
40
41
42 ***** oauth_token *****
43 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updatees/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↳ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
44 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updatees/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updatees.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↳ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
45 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
46 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
47 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
48 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
```

Listing 31: Analysis report from BidText on the alpaca-java library. The report shows a data exposure in method `sendWebsocketMessage` found in the analysis of entry point `onReconnection`. The data exposure can be verified in a manual analysis of the source code.

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
1 SINK [org.slf4j.Logger.trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V]
2 in [net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.AlpacaWebsocket.sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang|
  ↳ /String;)V]
3
4 The following texts reached the sink:
5 - listening
6 - authenticate
7 - data
8 - key_id
9 - Websocket message sent: {}
10 - streams
11 - trade_updates
12 - Requested streams: streams={}.
13 - listen
14 - authorization
15 - secret_key
16 - oauth_token
17 - action
18 In these texts, the following sensitivity indicators (keywords in a non-negated context)
  ↳ appeared:
19 - oauth_token
20 - secret
21 - key
22
23
24 ***** secret_key *****
25 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
26 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
27 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
28 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
29 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob|
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
30 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
    ↪ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
    ↪ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
    ↪ ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
    ↪ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
31 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
    ↪ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
    ↪ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
    ↪ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
32 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
    ↪ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
    ↪ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
    ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
    ↪ essage()V@69 ]
33 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
    ↪ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
    ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
    ↪ essage()V@69 ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
    ↪ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
34 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
    ↪ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
    ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
    ↪ essage()V@69 ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
    ↪ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
35
36
37 ***** key_id *****
38 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
    ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
    ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
    ↪ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
    ↪ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
39 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
    ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
    ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
    ↪ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
    ↪ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
40 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
    ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
    ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
    ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
    ↪ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
    ↪ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
41 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
42 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
43 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
44 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
45 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ]
46 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
47 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
48
49
50 ***** oauth_token *****
51 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
52 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
53 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
54 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
55 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
56 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
57 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
58 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ]
59 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
60 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ][12]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ trace(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 7,8,2 @23 exception:9 v7
```

Listing 32: Analysis report from BidText on the alpaca-java library. The report shows a data exposure in method `sendWebsocketMessage`. The data exposure alarm is considered a false positive.

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
1 SINK [org.slf4j.Logger.info(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V]
2 in [net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListen
  ↳ Message()V]
3
4 The following texts reached the sink:
5 - listening
6 - authenticate
7 - data
8 - key_id
9 - Websocket message sent: {}
10 - streams
11 - trade_updates
12 - Requested streams: streams={}.
13 - listen
14 - authorization
15 - secret_key
16 - oauth_token
17 - action
18 In these texts, the following sensitivity indicators (keywords in a non-negated context)
  ↳ appeared:
19 - oauth_token
20 - secret
21 - key
22
23
24 ***** secret_key *****
25 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
26 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][34]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,17,18 @66 exception:19 v18
27 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
28 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
29 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
30 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
31 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
32 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ]
33 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
34 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ] v2
35 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ][34]23 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 3 @66 exception:22
36 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ][31]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 3,20,16 @61 exception:21 v3
37 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ][27]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 16,18,8 @54 exception:19 v8
38 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ][39]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
  ↳ info(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 25,26,8 @79 exception:27 v25
39
40
41 ***** key_id *****
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
42 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
43 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][29]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,14,15 @56 exception:16 v15
44 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
45 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
  ↳ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
46 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
47 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
48 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
49 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ]
50 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ][16]12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
51 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
   ↪ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
   ↪ essage()V@69 ] v2
52 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
   ↪ ][34]23 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 3 @66 exception:22
53 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
   ↪ ][31]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 3,20,16 @61 exception:21 v3
54 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
   ↪ ][27]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 16,18,8 @54 exception:19 v8
55 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
   ↪ ][39]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,
   ↪ info(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 25,26,8 @79 exception:27 v25
56
57
58 ***** oauth_token *****
59 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↪ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
60 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↪ ][23]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ addProperty(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/String;)V > 10,20,21 @43 exception:22 v21
61 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↪ ][38]invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 5,23,10 @73 exception:24 v5
62 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
   ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
   ↪ sendAuthenticationMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
   ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@1
   ↪ ][46]30 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
   ↪ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 5 @92 exception:29
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
63 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
  ↳ v2
64 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95
  ↳ ] [16] 12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
65 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [ net.jacob
  ↳ peterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendAuthenticationMessage()V@95 ]
66 NORMAL sendWebsocketMessage:10 = getField < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket, websocket,
  ↳ <Application,Lokhttp3/WebSocket> > 1 Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ]
67 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ] [16] 12 = invokeinterface < Application, Lokhttp3/WebSocket,
  ↳ send(Ljava/lang/String;)Z > 10,2 @33 exception:11
68 PARAM_CALLEE:Node: < Application, Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/AlpacaWebsocket,
  ↳ sendWebsocketMessage(Ljava/lang/String;)V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.sendTradeUpdatesListenM
  ↳ essage()V@69 ] v2
69 NORMAL_RET_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ] [34] 23 = invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ toString()Ljava/lang/String; > 3 @66 exception:22
70 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ] [31] invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 3,20,16 @61 exception:21 v3
71 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,
  ↳ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,
  ↳ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [
  ↳ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25
  ↳ ] [27] invokevirtual < Application, Lcom/google/gson/JsonObject,
  ↳ add(Ljava/lang/String;Lcom/google/gson/JsonElement;)V > 16,18,8 @54 exception:19 v8
```

C. Analysis Reports for the alpaca-java Library

```
72 PARAM_CALLER:Node: < Application,  
  ↪ Lnet/jacobpeterson/alpaca/websocket/updates/UpdatesWebsocket,  
  ↪ sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage()V > Context: CallStringContext: [  
  ↪ net.jacobpeterson.alpaca.websocket.updates.UpdatesWebsocket.onReconnection()V@25  
  ↪ ][39]invokeinterface < Application, Lorg/slf4j/Logger,  
  ↪ info(Ljava/lang/String;Ljava/lang/Object;)V > 25,26,8 @79 exception:27 v25
```

Listing 33: Analysis report from BidText on the alpaca-java library. The report shows a supposed data exposure in method `sendTradeUpdatesListenMessage`. The data exposure alarm is considered a false positive.

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